

INTERACTION OF CHARGES WITH SOLIDS

Marek Tadeusz Michalewicz

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STATEMENT

This dissertation is an account of work carried out in the Department of Theoretical Physics of the Research School of Physical Sciences in the Australian National University between May 1984 and August 1987, under the supervision of Dr J. Mahanty.

The first chapter forms a general and brief overview of the theories and models which are relevant to my research, whereas most of the material presented in the following three chapters comprises my original contribution to the field. The last chapter indicates how existing results on dielectrics can be integrated into the formalism developed in Chapter 2. I have collaborated closely with Dr J. Mahanty at all stages of my research program. None of the work reported here has been submitted to any other institute of learning for any degree. Due reference is made in the text to the works published or written by other persons.

M. T. Nicholas

SYNOPSIS

The interaction potential of the charged particle (electron, ion, positron) in the proximity of the solid-vacuum interface is the main theme of this Thesis. This is a topic of fundamental importance in surface physics and hence it has attracted considerable research interest, especially in the last two decades.

The first chapter sets the perspective view on the relevant experimental scene and on the theoretical approaches prior or complementary to that undertaken in the present work.

The general formalism of the (local) self-energy or the interaction potential of the charge near a solid surface has been derived on the basis of linear response theory (Chapter 2). The expression representing the interaction energy is valid for arbitrary geometry and type of solid as long as the normal modes to which a particle is coupled are known. In metals these modes are *dispersive* surface and bulk plasmons. They are obtained here from the hydrodynamic model of the free electron gas.

The hydrodynamic model is introduced in section 3.2. It is used to evaluate the potential of a charged particle in the gap between two metals (section 3.3). Our results differ substantially from those obtained by the multiple-image method when the gap is small. This is due to dispersion of plasmons and has implications for analysis of the performance of tunnel devices.

The formalism developed in Chapter 2 is then applied to study the interaction of a charge with a minute metal sphere. The plasmon modes of the sphere are evaluated using the hydrodynamic model. There are only a finite number of surface modes on the sphere when the plasmons are dispersive, and these make the dominant contribution to the potential outside the sphere. For $r < R$ the interaction potential is mainly due to the contribution of the bulk modes. The first order quantum correction to the potential is also given.

The three-dimensional potential of a charged particle tunneling between a flat metal surface and a spherical metal tip — a model of the scanning tunneling microscope — is calculated. It is demonstrated that the inclusion of coupling of surface modes in the two electrodes, even for separations as small as 10 times the screening length in either of them, contributes less than 5% of the total potential of a point charge. Hence the potential is obtained as a superposition of contributions from a planar surface and a charge neutral, conducting sphere (and can include a simple classical term for a sphere at a fixed potential).

In Chapter 4 we develop a variational method for studying the interaction potential of a static charge with metals. The method is based on the density functional method. The total electron energy functional is expanded in a functional Taylor expansion about the equilibrium density. The interaction potential both inside and outside the metal is obtained by minimizing the second order energy shift induced by the presence of charge. The electron density in jellium metal is represented as a sum of two terms: an equilibrium, unperturbed part and the first order, three-dimensional density fluctuation. Both terms are assumed here in an analytical form, the first one is a remarkably simple model of a *diffuse* metal surface (so the Kohn-Sham equations are *not* solved); the form of the other term is taken from the known results of the hydrodynamic model. Thus our method uses the known results of the hydrodynamic model in the more exact density functional formalism. Within this formalism we obtain the potential of the electrostatic double-layer, the work function for selected metals and the interaction potential of a charge embedded in a jellium metal or outside the surface. The agreement with other theories is good. The method can be used for other than planar geometries and reflects the diffuse character of a metal surface (not present in the usual hydrodynamic model).

Finally, in Chapter 5, we consider the interaction potential of a charged par-

ticle with the surface of a dielectric. It is demonstrated there how the existing results on the spatially nondispersive dielectrics can be integrated into the formalism developed in Chapter 2. We outline the method for treating, within our self-energy formalism, the spatially dispersive dielectrics.

PUBLICATIONS

1. M.T. Michalewicz and I.L. McLaughlin
On the Gaskell Approximation for structure factors of liquid metals.
Phys. Chem. Liq. **14** (1985) 211-218.
2. M.T. Michalewicz and I.L. McLaughlin
On the density dependence of the mean density approximation. *J. Phys. F: Met. Phys.* **15** (1985) L181-L183.
- 3*. J. Mahanty and M.T. Michalewicz
Interaction of a charged particle with solid surface. A general formalism and spherical geometry. *J. Phys. C: Solid State Phys.* **19** (1986) 5005-5018.
- 4*. M.T. Michalewicz and J. Mahanty
Correction to image potential between metals. *Phys. Letters A* **116** (1986) 392-394.
- 5*. M.T. Michalewicz and J. Mahanty
A minute metallic sphere close to flat metal surface system: a Scanning Tunneling Microscope problem. *Springer Proc. Phys.* **13** (1986) 466.
- 6.* J. Mahanty and M.T. Michalewicz
Interaction potential of a charged particle in a plane-sphere geometry.
Aust. J. Phys. **40** (1987) 413-422.

* works which report the results presented in this Thesis.

BRIDGES BETWEEN SCIENCE AND TRADITION

There are a number of common bridges between the path of science and the path of tradition. The one that I have found most impressive is the process of enlightenment, of learning, the functioning of *vidya*. There is the period of darkness, of non-comprehension, of frustration when it appears that it is eternal and non-ending. Then comes clarity of perception, either through the instruction of a gifted guide or through a spontaneous process. In either case the light that shines on the problem resolves it so completely that it becomes difficult to imagine that you could have ever not seen the resolution. The process of growth is thus a sequence of destructions and creations: and the modality of knowing is the functioning aspect of the great teacher, the *guru*, the remover of darkness. In the functioning of the living teaching there is no student but only the illumined perception.

E.C.G. Sudarshan (1986)

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One thousand and one + 203 days have passed since I started working on the problems reported in this thesis. The personal experiences which enriched my life during this period can not be separated from the learning and research experiences I have gained.

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“Głębia ziewa na powierzchni,
a powierzchnia okazuje się dnem głębi.”

The depth yawns on the surface and the surface becomes the deepest bottom of the depths.”

S.I. Witkiewicz (Witkacy), (1911).

CHAPTER 1. GENERAL FEATURES OF INTERACTION OF CHARGED PARTICLES WITH CONDENSED SYSTEMS.

1.1 General remarks.

The problem of considerable import to the past development and the present day activity of Surface Physics is the determination of the interaction potential of external charged particles (electrons, ions, positrons) or neutral atoms with a solid surface. Surface science is an enormously vast field of research endeavour which embraces a great variety of experimental techniques and explores very many different physical phenomena. It is remarkable, though not always explicitly noted, that the detailed knowledge of the interaction potential of an atom with a surface or a charged particle with a surface (depending on the context, referred to as the image potential, dynamical image potential or self-energy — the precise meaning and distinction will be given later), is necessary for interpretation and analysis of so many of experimental techniques and surface phenomena. In a number of experimental surface-specific methods a solid surface is probed with charged particles or atoms (Roy and Carvette, 1977; Gonser, 1986). A few representative examples include low-energy electron diffraction (LEED) (Pendry, 1974), electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) (Ibach and Mills, 1982; Froitzheim, 1977; Hall *et al.*, 1983), high-resolution electron energy loss spectroscopy (HREELS) (Mills and Tong, 1982), field ion microscopy (Müller, 1951, 1965), ion scattering (Godfrey

and Woodruff, 1979) or atomic and molecular beam diffraction (Engel and Rieder, 1982; Engel, 1984). Some surface phenomena which require the understanding of surface response to an external charge are field emission (Duke and Tucker, 1971), field evaporation (Brandon, 1965; Gadzuk and Plummer, 1973) field desorption (Gomer and Swanson, 1963; Plummer and Rhodin, 1968) chemisorption (Gadzuk *et al.*, 1971) or surface resonance states in metals (McRae, 1979).

The external charge-solid surface interaction potential is of fundamental importance in understanding the *image potential induced surface states* recently discovered experimentally by inverse photoemission spectroscopy (Johnson and Smith, 1983; Dose *et al.*, 1984; Straub and Himpsel, 1984; Goldman *et al.*, 1985; Thörner and Borstel, 1986) and analysed theoretically by Echenique and Pendry (1978) and by Read (1985), Smith (1985), Arnau and Echenique (1987), among many others. The *vacuum electron tunneling* in the scanning tunneling microscope (STM) (Binnig *et al.*, 1982a,b 1983) is another example of great relevance to this problem. We will present an extensive discussion of this second problem in the latter part of this thesis.

1.2 Theoretical setting (background).

Elementary methods of classical electrostatics yield the so-called "image potential" for a stationary, point charge q placed at a distance z from the planar surface of the ideal conductor,

$$W = -q^2/4z \tag{1.1}$$

(Feynman, *et al.*, 1964; Jackson, 1975). This simple expression is also valid asymptotically for real metals in the *limit of large separations*, $z \rightarrow \infty$. However, the response of the solid to the external, perturbing charge or oscillating electric multipole is a truly quantum many-body problem. It is complicated additionally by a

lack of translational symmetry of the solid in the direction normal to the surface and, related to this, inhomogeneity of the equilibrium electronic density.

In the proximity of a solid surface the classical image potential diverges to infinity, whereas the real potential saturates to some finite value. This effect was observed experimentally using high resolution low-energy electron diffraction (Dietz, *et al.*, 1980). It can be theoretically accounted for by invoking approximate methods of the full (unsolvable) many-body theory. By doing this one not only obtains a detailed form of a realistic potential which is able to give accurate interpretation of experiments but one also gains insight into the surface electronic properties and/or the dynamics of the surface excitations.

The famous works of Bardeen (1936, 1940) mark the beginning of a period of extensive theoretical activity devoted to the problem of the interaction of a charged particle or an atom with a polarizable medium. During the last decade the interest in this problem was revived due to experimental advances mentioned earlier, but also due to several controversial reports which questioned the spatial and temporal character or even existence of image potential (see Schaich, 1984 and references therein).

We present here a brief survey of some of the theoretical models found in the literature which derive or utilize the various forms of the interaction potential of a charged particle in the vicinity of a solid surface. Reviews of Kiejna and Wojciechowski (1975) and Mehrotra (1979) can complement our picture of the theoretical activity. This account will be facilitated by introducing categories relating broadly to a philosophy or a method employed. The works cited here are illustrative examples only and are not intended to form a complete list of references.

1.2.1. The classical image potential and its empirical variants.

Despite its known limitations and inability to relate to the surface electronic structure the classical image potential continues to be applied in the more complicated situations involving molecules or adsorbed atoms interacting with one another or with a metal surface (Lennard-Jones, 1932). Mahanty and March (1976) have shown that for a diatomic molecule with a Lennard-Jones type interatomic potential orientated parallel to the metal surface its bond strength can be reduced up to $4/9$ of its vacuum value. The formation of the surface-induced dipole moments of adsorbed closed shell atoms interacting with its instantaneous image charges was studied by Antoniewicz (1974). Kohn and Lau (1976) derived an expression for an adatom dipole moment and the interaction energy of two dipoles situated on the metallic surface. Gadzuk (1967) and Remy (1970) have considered an interaction of an alkali atom with a metal via the image model in order to find the surface induced shifts and broadening in its energy levels.

The classical image potential was used recently in a different context by Lambin *et al.* (1987) to formulate the theory of the electron-energy-loss spectrum of a dielectric target. The image model is also a convenient guiding theoretical vehicle in the systems of a complicated, non-planar geometry. The multiple-image methods (Feynman *et al.*, 1964) were applied to calculate the potential barriers existing in planar metal-vacuum-metal or metal-insulator-metal junctions (Simmons, 1963a,b) and in the hyperboloidal-planar geometry found in metallic point-contact infrared detectors (Miskovsky *et al.*, 1981,1982). Morawitz *et al.*, (1987) and Batra and Morawitz (1986) have carried out calculations of the potential barrier in a plane-sphere model geometry of the scanning tunneling microscope using a multiple image method. The inadequacy of this approach for real metals has been demonstrated on the basis of the hydrodynamic model by Michalewicz and Mahanty (1986) and will be discussed in more detail in Chapter 3. The high lateral

resolution and focusing property of the STM which does not depend on the exact numerical values of the potential barrier, but on the geometry properties, was studied lately by semi-classical method and the classical image derived barrier by Das and Mahanty (1987).

In order to include the higher-order quantum corrections (Bardeen, 1940; Sachs and Dexter, 1950) and to allow for a continuity in the surface region, the classical image potential was modified on a semi-quantitative basis and various simple analytical model potentials were tested numerically by Cutler and co-workers (Cutler and Davies, 1964; Cutler and Nagy, 1964; Engle and Cutler, 1967) and Modinos (1967). However, these studies were of a comparative and empirical character and did not provide new understanding of the surface response to a perturbing, external charge distribution.

1.2.2. *The semi-classical Thomas-Fermi approximation.*

The semi-classical Thomas-Fermi electrostatic theory has the advantage over the classical treatment that, while preserving the simplicity of the formalism, it allows for a finite screening of electrostatic interactions in the electron gas, with a Thomas-Fermi screening length $\lambda_{TF}^{-2} = 6\pi n e^2 / E_F$, where n is the equilibrium electron density, e — electron charge and E_F — Fermi energy (Newns, 1969; Antoniewicz, 1972; Heinrichs, 1973). The main results of Newns (1969) are the following. An equivalent of the classical point image charge exists in the form of an oscillatory line charge distribution extending from the image point along the inward pointing normal to the surface; the screening of a perturbing charge placed a short distance outside the metal surface is very effective and the perturbation is large only within a thin surface layer of the order of a few screening lengths; the potential energy of a point charge Q at a distance z from the metal surface is

given by,

$$W_N = -\frac{Q^2}{2} \lambda_{TF}^{-1} \int_0^\infty \exp(-2kz) [k - (1 + k^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}]^2 dk \quad (1.2)$$

where k is in units of λ_{TF}^{-1} and z in units λ_{TF} . At the surface W_N attains the value, $W_N(z = 0) = -\frac{Q^2 \lambda_{TF}^{-1}}{3}$.

It is important to notice that the Thomas-Fermi method is equivalent to a static limit ($\omega = 0$) of the hydrodynamic model and the above results can be obtained within the hydrodynamic model (Mahanty and Michalewicz, 1987, Eq.17). We will return to this point later in Chapter 3. Expression (1.2) leads to the classical image potential (1.1) in the case of an ideal conductor ($\lambda_{TF} \rightarrow \infty$). Gadzuk (1970) has compared the Thomas-Fermi results of Newns with the computations based on his quantum screening theory. He found a good agreement between the two formulations apart from the fact that the Thomas-Fermi model slightly overestimates the screening.

1.2.3. *The semi-classical plasmon field from the hydrodynamic model*

Although the surface and bulk plasmons (Bloch, 1933; Ritchie, 1973; Barton, 1979) are genuine quantum modes and constitute a quantized Boson field (Tomonaga, 1950; Nakamura, 1983) the hydrodynamic model of electron gas in metal admits a semi-classical treatment of the interaction potential of a local charge with a metal and an atom or a molecule with a metal (van der Waals interaction). Unlike the Thomas-Fermi method it provides an understanding of the role of the dynamical, collective behaviour of the electron gas in metal and enables identification of the surface *and* bulk plasmon contributions to the interaction potential and van der Waals interaction energy (Summerside and Mahanty, 1978). We will discuss the hydrodynamic model in greater detail in Chapter 3 and the use of its quantized version in self-energy formalism in Chapter 2.

On the semi-classical level, the hydrodynamic model has been applied to

calculate the van der Waals interaction between a molecule and a metal surface (Mahanty and Paranjape, 1977; Summerside and Mahanty, 1978) and the force on the charge moving parallel to a metal surface (Mahanty and Summerside, 1980). Michalewicz and Mahanty (1986) have used this method to demonstrate that the potential of a charged particle in the gap between two metals is substantially different from that obtained by the multiple-image method. We will return to this problem in Chapter 3.

It should be emphasized here that the semi-classical approach based on the hydrodynamic model for electrons is formally relatively simple and at the same time it affords to treat the *dispersive* plasmons in a rather straightforward manner, whereas more elaborate quantum many-body theories (discussed in the following paragraphs) are very often limited in application to (a single) nondispersive surface plasmon excitation. As will be seen later the semi-classical treatment with dispersion is frequently more illuminating than nondispersive quantum models (Equiluz, 1981). An example of this effect is given by Summerside and Mahanty (1978) who have demonstrated that *only* when spatial dispersion is neglected ($\beta = 0$, where β is the usual dispersion parameter in hydrodynamic model) do the bulk contributions to the image force vanish and the statements advanced, for example by Mahan (1972) and Ritchie (1972) that surface plasmons alone give rise to the image force become correct.

1.2.4. The linear dielectric response methods

A large number of papers appeared in the literature in which the dielectric linear response theory (see e.g. Hedin and Lundqvist, 1969) is used to calculate the interaction between a point charge and the jellium surface. In the response theory the induced charge density in the system, $\rho_1(\mathbf{r}, t)$, is related to a (small)

external potential $V_{ext}(\mathbf{r}', t')$ by the following expression

$$\rho_1(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int d\mathbf{r}' dt' R(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - t') V_{ext}(\mathbf{r}', t') \quad (1.3)$$

where $R(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - t')$ is the linear response function. It follows from the causality requirements that $R(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}', t - t') \neq 0$ only for $t > t'$. The semi-classical "image potential" is just the interaction energy between the test charge Q which is the source of V_{ext} , and the induced charge,

$$W(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{r} V_{ext}(\mathbf{r}, t) \rho_1(\mathbf{r}, t). \quad (1.4)$$

This theory is particularly appealing from the formal point of view since, in principle, the main quantity of interest — the retarded response function — contains information on both the "classical", long-wavelength collective response of the electron gas (hydrodynamic plasmons) and the retarded part describing the particle-hole excitations as well (Mukhopadhyay and Lundqvist, 1975). Unfortunately when this general formalism is applied to particular problems, it is necessary to resort to further simplifications and the final results are not always very instructive.

The quantum linear response method was used for the numerical evaluation of the response of a jellium metal to an external charge by Beck and Celli (1970) and to an internal charge impurity by Beck *et al.*, (1970). In their work the random phase approximation (RPA) was utilized to obtain the response function and the exchange interactions were neglected. Peuckert (1971) was able to carry out analytical calculations within the RPA response model using the Green functions techniques. In 1970 Sidyakin offered a rather general calculational scheme, but in the final stage of his work he took some approximations, including the Thomas-Fermi dielectric function and his final results (Eq.18 in his work) was just the semi-classical Thomas-Fermi expression derived also by Newns (1969) (our

Eq.1.2). Newns (1970) has presented a more general theoretical foundation for his earlier work (Newns, 1969) using the Hartree approximation for the dielectric response.

In all the works based on the linear response theory described so far the boundary conditions are assumed within the infinite barrier model (IBM). It implies that the jellium surface is impenetrable for the electronic wave functions (the single-particle potential in the Hamiltonian at the jellium surface and outside is infinite). The approaches based on the IBM were analysed and compared with "dielectric approximation" (DA) by Heinrichs (1973), where the surface response is modelled with the help of the *bulk* dielectric function. He has also presented a time-dependent generalization of the dielectric response, but within the IBM approximation.

Another approach, taken by Das Sarma and Quinn (1979), is based on the linear response function evaluated from the hydrodynamic model for metallic electrons. The advantage of this method is that the calculations within the hydrodynamic model can be carried out to a great extent analytically and at the same time the qualitative features of the system can be directly studied. The longitudinal response function obtained by these authors was separated into the bulk and surface parts. The latter contains the most information on the surface effects. It was evaluated for a single-step density model and the two-step density model.

The density response function specific for the surface region with the diffuse electronic density profile was obtained by Equiluz (1983) on the basis of the RPA and the Kohn-Sham-Lang wave functions. The inadequacy of the IBM method was demonstrated as well. This density response function was later applied by Equiluz *et al.*, (1984) in the determination of the static response of the jellium surface to an external local charge and the modification of the indirect interaction between two charges.

1.2.5. The dynamic image potential.

It is often desirable to know the effect the finite velocity of the probing particle and its direction of motion has on the surface response (the dynamical image potential). This is important for analysing experimental data from techniques such as low-energy electron diffraction (LEED), photoelectron spectroscopy, ion scattering spectroscopy, positron scattering and the like, where the energetic charge penetrates the surface barrier. Mahan (1973, 1974) has formulated the dynamic image problem in terms of a model Hamiltonian,

$$H = H_{electron} + H_{solid} + H_{int} \quad (1.5)$$

$$H_{solid} = \sum_{\kappa} a_{\kappa}^{\dagger} a_{\kappa} \hbar \omega_s \quad (1.6)$$

$$H_{int} = \sum_{\kappa} \Gamma_{\kappa} e^{-\kappa z} (a_{\kappa} + a_{-\kappa}^{\dagger}) e^{i\kappa \cdot \rho} \quad (1.7)$$

where the coupling constant $\Gamma_{\kappa} = \left(\frac{\pi e^2 \hbar \omega_s}{kA} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, A is the surface area.

He assumed that the only normal mode present in the solid and interacting with the moving electron is the (dispersionless) surface plasmon ($\omega_s = \omega_p / \sqrt{2}$). The coupling constant Γ_{κ} was obtained by equating the classical image potential form with the second order energy perturbation (Wang and Mahan, 1972). These two steps have naturally precluded the saturation of the potential to a finite value at the jellium surface both in the static and the dynamic case.

The same model has been applied by Shah and Mukhopadhyay (1983) to study the additional effect of the acceleration of an electron on the dynamic image potential. Wu and Mahan (1983) addressed a problem of the field emission current computation, where the Hamiltonian (1.5–1.7) was supplemented by an external field term ($V_0 \sim -eFz$) and the classical (shifted) image potential ($U(z) = \frac{-e^2}{4(z^2 + a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}}$) was explicitly built into the Hamiltonian.

The linear response function method was also extended to treat the dynamic image problem. The RPA response function obtained with the help of IBM bound-

ary conditions (called SCIB — the semi-classical infinite barrier as well) was used by Rao *et al.*, (1984). Das Sarma (1982) employed the response function calculated within the hydrodynamic model in the nonretarded limit. He calculated the dynamic image potential for single-step and double-step model for the electron density profile (diffusive surface profile). He found that three mechanisms suppress the divergence of the classical image potential at the jellium surface: (1) screening by inhomogeneous electron gas ($\beta \neq 0$), (2) diffuseness of the metal surface and (3) finite velocity of the external point charge.

In the models for the dynamic image potential described above it is assumed that an electron is localized at any instant of time — these are effectively the semi-classical models.

The quantum mechanical treatment was offered by Jonson (1980). He begins with the Schrödinger equation for the quasi-particles of the electron-plasmon system. The non-local term in this equation, the self-energy, is cast in the form of one-body, energy-dependent exchange-correlation potential, $V_{ex}(z, E)$. The $V_{ex}(z, E)$ is identified as the image potential in the appropriate limits (see Bardeen, 1940, 1980). The one-body Schrödinger equation is then solved exactly using Green's functions for an electron tunnelling across a rectangular barrier (tunneling in Al-SiO₂ interface). The resulting dynamic image potential of Jonson is *complex*. This was not the case in the semi-classical treatments of Mahan and other workers mentioned earlier. The imaginary part of $V_{ex}(z, \omega)$ is related to a finite lifetime of the quasiparticle states described by the initial Schrödinger equation. However the real part of $V_{ex}(z, \omega)$ outside the barrier is identical to the Mahan's form. This is due to the assumption essential to both works (as well as the work of Shah and Mukhopadhyay) that *only the surface plasmons* are responsible for the interaction with a charge and that the plasmons are *dispersionless*. This is effectively a single, surface-plasmon model.

We wish to stress that in the general self-energy formalism (to be presented later) there is no need to separately treat a *moving* charge and the potential is always complex and “dynamic” unless appropriate limits are taken (Mahanty *et al.*, 1986).

1.3 Miscellaneous comments

Two methods of considerable importance were omitted in the overview of theoretical activity presented above. The first is the self-energy formalism, and the second the self-consistent density functional method. Each of them is essential to our own work and we will discuss them separately at greater length in the following chapters. The concepts and origins of the self-energy formalism will be reviewed in the first part of Chapter 2. The systematic derivation of this formalism based on the linear response theory and the generalization to the systems at finite temperatures was given by Mahanty and Michalewicz (1986). Our theory will be presented in the second part of Chapter 2. It will be applied to study the interaction potential of a charged particle with metals (Chapter 3) and with dielectrics (Chapter 5).

It should be emphasized that the self-energy method can only be applied when the *normal modes* of the particular system under study are known *a priori* (e.g. plasmons in metals, optical phonons in dielectrics). The plasmon modes in metals are evaluated here within the hydrodynamic model for electron gas in the nonretarded limit ($c \rightarrow \infty$). The extension to the retarded case could be achieved in a rather straightforward manner (Fetter, 1973). The hydrodynamic equation is usually solved subject to somewhat unphysical *boundary conditions* of vanishing normal component of the density current at the jellium surface (equivalent to IBM in the dynamic response case). The physical implications of these boundary conditions and possible relaxation of them will be discussed in Chapter 3. It is also due to the boundary conditions that the self-consistency of the solutions can not always

be guaranteed. The role of the *exchange and correlation* potential in modifying the form of the image potential in close proximity to the surface has been repeatedly emphasised in the literature (beginning with Bardeen, 1940, 1980). Although the exchange and correlation effects are not explicitly present in the hydrodynamic description, it has been demonstrated by Ying (1974) that they are buried in the pressure term of the hydrodynamic equation (and consequently in the dispersion parameter β). It was already noted by other workers (e.g. Das Sarma, 1982) that the *nonlocal effects* of exchange and correlation potential are also retained in the hydrodynamic model by virtue of the dispersion parameter β being finite. We will provide a transparent illustration of this point in Chapter 4. By using the hydrodynamic model we neglect an excitation spectrum of *electron-hole pairs*. However, as was observed earlier (e.g. Gadzuk, 1977; Eguiluz, 1981) these effects are only important for $z < \lambda$, where z is the position of a charge measured from a jellium edge and λ is the screening length ($\lambda \sim k_{TF}^{-1} \sim 1 \text{ \AA}$). The limitations of the hydrodynamic model in treating this part of the spectrum are well known but the great advantage of using it is that, owing to its relative simplicity, most of the calculations can be carried out analytically giving a great deal of physical insight about the system under study. Alternative approaches like the ones based on the linear response function (Eguiluz, 1981; Eguiluz *et al.*, 1984) were not as yet applied to analyzing systems more complicated than a jellium thin film or a jellium flat half-space. The hydrodynamic model, on the contrary, was applied to a problem of the interaction potential of a charge and metallic sphere (Mahanty and Michalewicz 1986), a charge in a vacuum gap between two metallic half-spaces (Michalewicz and Mahanty, 1986) and a charge between a metallic sphere and metal half-space (a model geometry for the scanning tunneling microscope (STM), Mahanty and Michalewicz, 1987). We will report on these results in Chapter 3.

In Chapter 4, a further step is attempted, the first one being the work of

Ying (1974), to bring a hydrodynamic model closer to a density functional method (DF). First we present a brief review of DF theory and then we introduce a one-parameter equilibrium electronic density profile for a jellium metal surface. This is a remarkably simple profile, in the spirit of Smith's (1969) work (so the Kohn-Sham equations *are not* solved). However our choice gives slightly better agreement with experimental data on surface energy than Smith's density profile, and also our variational parameter has the direct physical meaning of the half-width of the electronic surface inhomogeneity. When an extra charge is placed inside or outside the metal, the first order, *three-dimensional* density fluctuation is derived from the hydrodynamic model. The *diffuse surface* profile of the electronic density is the important feature of both the zeroth and the first order electronic densities. The total energy of the metal-particle system is expanded in functional Taylor expansion about the equilibrium density. The first order terms represent the chemical potential and the double-layer contribution. The second order terms depend on the position of the extra charge. We minimize them with respect to a one-parameter family of trial (hydrodynamic) electronic density functions. Our method is applied to the flat semi-infinite metal slab only, however the formalism can incorporate the non-local form of the density functional and nearly any geometry of practical importance can be treated within this method.

It is demonstrated in Chapter 5 how the interaction potential of a charge with the surface of a dielectric solid can be evaluated on the basis of the self-energy formalism. The dispersive polarization modes could also be incorporated in this formalism. We discuss such a possibility in the last section of this work.

CHAPTER 2. THE SELF-ENERGY FORMALISM

2.1 Introduction.

The full complexity of the problem of a charge interacting with a many-body target can be understood only within the framework of the many-body theory. The development, structure and content of many-body theory and its success in explaining the properties of homogeneous systems is the subject of numerous excellent textbooks and monographs.

In this section we limit ourselves to introducing some basic concepts of the many-body formalism. We attribute physical meaning to the quantities which are of direct relevance to our work. We also summarize the results of some other workers who advanced the method of self-energy to surface physics applications. A comprehensive exposition of the formalism and concepts discussed here is provided in a well known paper by Hedin and Lundqvist (1969); we follow it in this introduction.

Let us consider the N -fermion system (e.g. electrons in metal lattice), perturbed by a small external potential $\phi(\mathbf{x}, t)$ such as an experimental probe. The Hamiltonian for this system is

$$\begin{aligned}
 H &= H_0 + H_1 \\
 H_0 &= \int \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}) h(\mathbf{x}) \psi(\mathbf{x}) \, d\mathbf{x} + \frac{1}{2} \int \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}) \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}') v(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \psi(\mathbf{x}') \psi(\mathbf{x}) \, d\mathbf{x} \, d\mathbf{x}' \\
 H_1 &= \int \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}) \psi(\mathbf{x}) \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \, d\mathbf{x} .
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

Here $\psi(\mathbf{x}), \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x})$ are the fermion field operators. They satisfy the usual anticommutation relations,

$$[\psi(\mathbf{x}), \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}')]_+ = \delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \quad [\psi(\mathbf{x}), \psi(\mathbf{x}')]_+ = [\psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}), \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}')]_+ = 0 . \tag{2.2}$$

The variable $\mathbf{x}$ represents both space and spin coordinates $\mathbf{x} = (\mathbf{r}, \xi)$. The term $h(\mathbf{x})$ represents the electronic kinetic energy part and the interaction potential

with a rigid ionic lattice (or a jellium background),

$$h(\mathbf{x}) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\nabla^2 - \sum_n Z_n v(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{R}_n). \quad (2.3)$$

Z_n is the valence of the ion situated at $\mathbf{R}_n$ and v is the Coulomb potential,

$$v(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = \frac{e^2}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}.$$

The Heisenberg equation of motion for $\psi(\mathbf{x})$ is

$$i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) = [\psi(\mathbf{x}, t), H]. \quad (2.4)$$

This can also be written

$$\begin{aligned} i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) &= [h(\mathbf{x}) + \phi(\mathbf{x}, t)]\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \\ &+ \int v(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')\psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}', t)\psi(\mathbf{x}', t)\psi(\mathbf{x}, t) d\mathbf{x}'. \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

After performing simple manipulations one readily arrives at the equation of motion for the one-electron Green's function $G(\mathbf{x}t, \mathbf{x}'t')$,

$$\left[i\hbar\frac{\partial}{\partial t} - h(\mathbf{x}) - \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) \right] G(\mathbf{x}t, \mathbf{x}'t') \quad (2.6a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ i \int v(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}'') \langle N | \mathbf{T} \{ \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}'', t) \psi(\mathbf{x}'', t) \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}', t') \} | N \rangle d\mathbf{x}'' \\ &= \hbar\delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')\delta(t, t') \end{aligned} \quad (2.6b)$$

where the one-particle Green's function (at $T = 0$) is defined by

$$G(\mathbf{x}t, \mathbf{x}'t') = -i\langle N | \mathbf{T} \{ \psi(\mathbf{x}, t) \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}', t') \} | N \rangle. \quad (2.7)$$

$\mathbf{T}$ defines the time ordering operator and $|N\rangle$ in the N -fermion ground state. By inspection of eq.(2.6) it is easy to notice that it separates naturally into a noninteracting one-particle term (2.6a) and the interaction term (2.6b) involving the two-body correlations (the two-body Green's function) in the system. At this

stage the nonlocal time- (or energy-) dependent *self-energy operator* Σ is introduced to formally describe the interaction between a particle and the rest of the system, through the equation,

$$\left[i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} - h(\mathbf{x}) - V(\mathbf{x}, t) \right] G(\mathbf{x}t, \mathbf{x}'t') - \int \Sigma(\mathbf{x}t, \mathbf{x}''t'') G(\mathbf{x}''t'', \mathbf{x}'t') d\mathbf{x}'' dt'' = \delta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \delta(t, t'). \quad (2.8)$$

In the above, the total average one-particle potential in the system $V(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the sum of the external potential and the Hartree potential,

$$V(\mathbf{x}, t) = \phi(\mathbf{x}, t) + \int v(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') \langle N | \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}', t) \psi(\mathbf{x}', t) | N \rangle d\mathbf{x}'. \quad (2.9)$$

The profound feature of the self-energy is its time-dependence (or the energy-dependence of its Fourier transform). The Hartree and Hartree-Fock approximations can be obtained from eq.2.8 if the self-energy Σ is assumed energy-independent. It can also be shown from eq.2.8 that the self-energy represents the shift in the position of the poles of the noninteracting Green's function G_0 . It is expressed symbolically,

$$G^{-1} = G_0^{-1} - \Sigma. \quad (2.10)$$

The self-energy can be interpreted as the contribution to the energy of the excitations of the system arising from the interaction effects. The Schrödinger equation for a quasi-particle state $\varphi_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x})$ is given in terms of self-energy,

$$[E_{\mathbf{k}} - h(\mathbf{x}) - V(\mathbf{x})] \varphi_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}) - \int \Sigma(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', E_{\mathbf{k}}) \varphi_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}') d\mathbf{x}' = 0. \quad (2.11)$$

Thus the main quantity of interest is the self-energy, since it contains information on the many-body interaction effects such as exchange and correlation and also the spectrum of the excitations (self-energy is itself a function of G , i.e. $\Sigma = \Sigma[G]$). Inkson (1971, 1973) and Jonson (1980) cast eq.2.11 into a form resembling an

effective (self-consistent) single-particle equation. The non-local self-energy term is replaced by a local, energy-dependent exchange and correlation potential $V_k(\mathbf{x})$ such that,

$$V_k(\mathbf{x})\varphi_k(\mathbf{x}) = \int \Sigma(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', E_k)\varphi_k(\mathbf{x}') d\mathbf{x}' . \quad (2.12)$$

The self-energy calculation presented by Inkson (1971, 1973) was based on a first order approximation which neglects the vertex corrections,

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \omega) = \frac{i}{2\pi} \int_c e^{-i\delta\omega'} G(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \omega - \omega') W(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}', \omega') d\omega' . \quad (2.13)$$

Here W is the dynamically screened interaction, in $(\mathbf{x}, t)$ space. It is given by relation,

$$W(\mathbf{x}_1 t_1, \mathbf{x}_2 t_2) = \int v(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_3) \epsilon^{-1}(\mathbf{x}_3 t_3, \mathbf{x}_2 t_2) d\mathbf{x}_3 dt_3 \quad (2.14)$$

and ϵ^{-1} is the inverse dielectric function.

For most practical purposes the full Green's function G in (2.13) is approximated by the noninteracting Green's function G_0 . The validity of the approximation (2.13) was discussed at length by Hedin and Lundqvist (1969, see especially p.81).

The screened electron-electron interaction W (eq.2.14) was evaluated by Inkson (1971) for an electron near an interface. When an electron is in medium 1, at $z = a > 0$, $W(\rho, z; a, \omega)$ was identified as the effective potential at a field point (ρ, z) ; W being the sum of a potential due to an electron at 'a' and the induced potential caused by medium 2. Inkson's calculation was based on the premise that the dielectric functions in both media can be represented by their *bulk* forms. The non-locality effects at the interface were ignored, and the potential and tangential field were kept continuous across the boundary. The extra poles of the screened interaction W obtained that way corresponded to surface type excitations. This method depends on the form of the bulk dielectric function extracted from some

independent model. Inkson (1971) employed a hydrodynamic dielectric function and his result for the interaction potential for distances greater than a few Fermi wavelengths was (using the notation as in eq.1.2),

$$-V(z) = -\frac{e^2}{2} \lambda_{TF}^{-1} \int_0^\infty \exp(-2kz) \frac{(k - (k^2 + 2)^{\frac{1}{2}})^2}{(k^2 + 2)^{\frac{1}{2}} (k + (k^2 + 2)^{\frac{1}{2}})} dk \quad (2.15)$$

which naturally reduced to classical image potential far out of the metal surface. In his later paper, Inkson (1973) evaluated the Green's function for an electron in the metal-vacuum system in a more detailed manner. Consequently the exchange and correlation potential (or simply the interaction potential) acquired an imaginary part which describes the finite lifetime of the excitations in the solid and the dissipation of energy of the probe (i.e. inelastic losses in scattering experiments). The real part of the potential arises from the exchange of virtual excitations. We will not reproduce Inkson's final results for the interaction potential since the real part outside the metal is essentially the result of Newns' (eq.1.2) and inside the metal it saturates rapidly to the usual hydrodynamic value $V_b = -\frac{1}{2} e^2 \lambda_{TF}^{-1}$. It was confirmed again that the predominant part of the potential outside is due to a contribution from surface plasmons. The relation between the self-energy and the exchange and correlation potential adopted in Inkson's work is (Hedin and Lundqvist, 1969),

$$V_{\mathbf{k}_0}(\mathbf{x}) := \int e^{-i\delta\omega'} \frac{e^{i\mathbf{q}\cdot\mathbf{x}} W(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{q}, \omega') d\mathbf{q} d\omega'}{E(\mathbf{k}_0) - E(\mathbf{k}_0 - \mathbf{q}) - \omega' \pm i\delta} \quad (2.16)$$

The further progress in the use of the self-energy concept was made by Manson and Ritchie (1981) who defined a space-dependent *local*, complex self-energy $\Sigma(\mathbf{r})$ through perturbation theory. It is in fact the exchange and correlation potential in Inkson's vocabulary.

The connection of $\Sigma(\mathbf{r})$ with the shift in the energy of the metal-particle system ΔE_0 is given by a definition,

$$\Delta E_0 = \int d\mathbf{r} \langle \mathbf{k}_0 | \mathbf{r} \rangle \Sigma(\mathbf{r}) \langle \mathbf{r} | \mathbf{k}_0 \rangle \quad (2.17)$$

where $|k_0\rangle$ is the state of the particle moving with momentum $\hbar k_0$ and the energy shift is caused by the interaction V . On the other hand perturbation theory gives the second-order energy shift in the form,

$$\Delta E_0 = \left\langle k_0 \left| \sum'_{n,k} \frac{\langle 0|V|n,k\rangle \langle n,k|V|0\rangle}{E_{0,k_0} - E_{n,k} + i\delta} \right| k_0 \right\rangle \quad (2.18)$$

where a mixed representation $|n,k\rangle := |n\rangle|k\rangle$ is used, $|n\rangle$ representing the n th excited state of the target (for all practical purposes — the collective mode).

If the matrix element $\langle r|0|v|n,k\rangle$ is unfolded and the identity $\int d^3r |r\rangle \langle r| = 1$ is used, the comparison of eq.2.17 and 2.18 gives the expression for the self-energy,

$$\Sigma(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n,k} \frac{\langle 0|v(\mathbf{r})|n\rangle \langle n,k|v|0,k_0\rangle}{E_{0,k_0} - E_{n,k} + i\delta} \frac{\langle \mathbf{r} | k \rangle}{\langle \mathbf{r} | k_0 \rangle}. \quad (2.19)$$

It should be stressed that the term “self-energy” here and in the following represents a *local*, energy-dependent quantity related to the change in energy of the solid-probe system due to the interaction.

Equation 2.19 forms the basis for a number of studies of the self-energy of a charged projectile and a solid surface or interface. In their original work, Manson and Ritchie (1981) adopted a plane-wave basis set and a rather simple model of a perturbing potential V . V was assumed to arise from dispersionless surface plasmons (as in Mahan, 1973). The self-energy obtained on the basis of this simple approximation to the surface collective response was nevertheless able to show many important qualitative (and to a certain degree of accuracy, quantitative) features. The *complex* solution took different forms depending on whether or not the particle had sufficient energy to excite a surface plasmon. The detailed results were presented only in the case above the threshold. The effect of three-dimensional recoil was accounted for and manifested itself in the $Re(\Sigma(z \rightarrow 0^\pm))$ value, which was twice the value obtained from dynamic image method or semi-classical calculations. An interesting result was presented in the limit $v \rightarrow 0$, for

a stationary particle. The self-energy is real in such a case and given by,

$$\Sigma(z) = -\frac{e^2}{4|z|} (1 - \exp(-Q_s|z|) + Q_s|z|E_2(Q_s|z|)) \quad (2.20)$$

where $E_2(y)$ is the associated exponential integral and $Q_s^2 = 2m\omega_s/\hbar$, $\omega_s = \omega_p/\sqrt{2}$ is the surface plasmon frequency, m is the mass of particle. This expression produces a saturation of Σ at the surface and shows that for large z the correction terms to the classical image potential decay faster than any inverse power of z .

Recently the self-energy method was applied by Sols and Ritchie (1986) in the more extensive study of the interaction potential of a charge near metal-vacuum, insulator-vacuum and metal-insulator planar interfaces. The contributions from the dispersionless bulk as well as surface plasmons were taken into account for a metal surface and from excitons and optical phonons (both bulk and surface) for an insulator surface. Echenique *et al.*, (1987) made use of the self-energy expression (2.19) to calculate the image potential appropriate for an electron tunneling from a metal into the conduction band of an insulator. The interaction potential was taken as being due solely to dispersionless plasmons. The basis set describing the particle's motion and used for evaluating the matrix elements in eq.2.19 was obtained from the solutions of one-dimensional, attractive δ -potential.

An exhaustive study of the self-energy of an energetic charge *outside* and *inside* the planar jellium metal was presented by Mahanty *et al.*, (1986, and also 1985). The general expressions for the self-energy valid for an arbitrary angle of incidence and for the incoming particle energies both below and above the threshold plasmons energies were given. The recoil arising out of real or virtual exchange of quanta of the collective charge oscillations was accounted for. The effect of the *spatial dispersion* in both *surface* and *bulk* plasmons was included through the use of the quantized hydrodynamic forms for the coupling coefficients in the interaction part of the many-body Hamiltonian. A plane-wave basis set appropriate for the treatment of a propagating particle was chosen.

2.2 Self-energy and linear response theory

2.2.1 Formalism

The self-energy method proposed by Manson and Ritchie (1981) gives the self-energy in terms of various orders in perturbation theory. However, it is possible to reinforce the conceptual foundations and widen the prospects for applications of the self-energy formalism by way of deriving it in a rigorous manner from the general linear response theory (Kubo, 1957). In this section we develop such a general formalism for the self-energy* using linear response theory. The results presented here were reported in Mahanty and Michalewicz (1986). The limitations of this approach to particular physical systems or materials and the necessity to resort to the models of collective modes will be discussed in the next section.

Tomonaga (1950) had pointed out that the interaction of a local charge with the metal electrons may be considered as one with the electron density fluctuations represented by a Boson field. This approach can obviously be generalised to include the case of interaction with an insulator where the Boson field will represent the polarisation fluctuations associated with optical phonons. In this model the Hamiltonian for a charged particle of mass M and charge Q interacting with a solid would be

$$H = H_0 + H_I \quad H_0 = H_S + H_P \quad (2.21a)$$

$$H_S = \sum_{\lambda} \hbar\omega_{\lambda} (a_{\lambda}^{\dagger} a_{\lambda} + \frac{1}{2}) \quad (2.21b)$$

$$H_P = p^2 / 2M \quad (2.21c)$$

$$H_I = Q\hat{\Phi} = Q \sum_{\lambda} (\varphi_{\lambda}^{\dagger} a_{\lambda}^{\dagger} + \varphi_{\lambda} a_{\lambda}). \quad (2.21d)$$

Here λ is the label of the particular mode of charge oscillation and $a_{\lambda}^{\dagger}$, a_{λ} are the creation and annihilation operators thereof. The potential operator $\hat{\Phi}$ has the

* Note the comment following (2.19).

representation

$$\langle \mathbf{r} | \hat{\Phi} | \mathbf{r}' \rangle = \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') \sum_{\lambda} [\varphi_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{r}) a_{\lambda}^{\dagger} + \varphi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r}) a_{\lambda}] \quad (2.22)$$

where $\varphi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r})$ is the potential due to the λ th charge oscillation mode of the solid. We shall restrict ourselves here to the electrostatic limit, although the formalism can readily be extended to include retardation effects (Fetter, 1973).

According to linear response theory (Kubo, 1957) the change in any physical quantity A due to a perturbation $H_I(t)$ is given by,

$$\langle \Delta A \rangle = \frac{1}{i\hbar} \int_{-\infty}^t dt' \exp(\eta t') \langle [A(t-t'), H_I(t')] \rangle \quad \eta \rightarrow 0^{\dagger} \quad (2.23)$$

with

$$A(t) = \exp(iH_0 t/\hbar) A \exp(-iH_0 t/\hbar). \quad (2.24)$$

When H_I is time-independent, as in the above example, (3) becomes,

$$\langle \Delta A \rangle = \frac{1}{i\hbar} \int_0^{\infty} dt \exp(-\eta t) \langle [A(t), H_I] \rangle. \quad (2.25)$$

Depending on the problem under study $\langle \dots \rangle$ in equations (2.23) and (2.25) represents either the expectation value in a given state of the system or, more usually, a thermal average over the states of the solid combined with the expectation value in a given state of the particle. The state of the system in the mixed representation is the product $|\{n_{\lambda}\}\rangle |\mathbf{k}\rangle$, where $|\{n_{\lambda}\}\rangle$ is the state of the solid with n_{λ} quanta in the λ th mode, and $\mathbf{k}$ is the wavenumber of the particle.

When $A = H$, the only non-vanishing term in (2.25) will be $\langle [H_I(t), H_I] \rangle$. This leads to the second-order energy shift if we multiply by a factor $\frac{1}{2}$. This factor comes from the Hellmann-Feynman theorem when applied to perturbation theoretic wavefunctions. Thus the second-order energy shift is,

$$(\Delta E)_2 = \frac{1}{2i\hbar} \int_0^{\infty} dt \exp(-\eta t) \langle [H_I(t), H_I] \rangle. \quad (2.26)$$

Let us consider a physical quantity A having the form

$$A = \sum_{\lambda} [A_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{R})a_{\lambda}^{\dagger} + A_{\lambda}(\mathbf{R})a_{\lambda}] . \quad (2.27)$$

To evaluate $A(t)$ from (2.24) we must distinguish among a few cases. Firstly, if $\mathbf{R}$ is not the coordinate of the particle (as would be the case, for instance, if $\mathbf{R}$ were a field point), the time evolution of A will occur only through H_S of (2.21b). Secondly, if the mass of the charged particle is very large so that the effect of H_P of equation (2.21c) is negligible, then also the time evolution of A will occur mainly through H_S , irrespective of whether or not $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{r}$, the coordinate of the particle. This gives the classical limit for the response as measured through $\langle \Delta A \rangle$. Finally, if $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{r}$ and M is not too large, both H_S and H_P will determine the time evolution. In the first two cases,

$$A(t) = \sum_{\lambda} [A_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{R})a_{\lambda}^{\dagger} \exp(i\omega_{\lambda}t) + A_{\lambda}(\mathbf{R})a_{\lambda} \exp(-i\omega_{\lambda}t)] \quad (2.28)$$

so that

$$[A(t), H_I] = Q \sum_{\lambda} [-A_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{R})\varphi_{\lambda} \exp(i\omega_{\lambda}t) + A_{\lambda}(\mathbf{R})\varphi_{\lambda}^{\dagger} \exp(-i\omega_{\lambda}t)] . \quad (2.29)$$

Then (2.25) becomes,

$$\langle \Delta A \rangle = - \sum_{\lambda} \left(\frac{Q}{\hbar\omega_{\lambda}} \right) \langle \{A_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{R})\varphi_{\lambda} + A_{\lambda}(\mathbf{R})\varphi_{\lambda}^{\dagger}\} \rangle . \quad (2.30)$$

When the expectation value is taken in a mixed representation $|\{n_{\lambda}\}|\mathbf{k}\rangle$, using (2.22) we get

$$\langle \Delta A \rangle = \int d\mathbf{r} \langle \mathbf{k}|\mathbf{r} \rangle A_I(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{r}) \langle \mathbf{r}|\mathbf{k} \rangle \quad (2.31)$$

where

$$A_I(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{r}) = - \sum_{\lambda} \left(\frac{Q}{\hbar\omega_{\lambda}} \right) 2\text{Re}[A_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{R})\varphi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r})] . \quad (2.32)$$

This depends on the particle coordinate $\mathbf{r}$ and the field point $\mathbf{R}$, and its expectation value in the particle state $\langle \mathbf{r} | \mathbf{k} \rangle$ gives the induced change $\langle \Delta A \rangle$. If $A_\lambda(\mathbf{R}) \equiv \varphi_\lambda(\mathbf{R})$ for instance, $A_I(\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{r})$ would give the induced potential at $\mathbf{R}$ when the particle is at $\mathbf{r}$.

If A is set equal to H_I and (2.26) is used, we get in the same approximation as above (i.e. neglecting the time evolution of H_I through H_P),

$$(\Delta E)_2 = \int d\mathbf{r} \langle \mathbf{k} | \mathbf{r} \rangle \Sigma_c(\mathbf{r}) \langle \mathbf{r} | \mathbf{k} \rangle, \quad (2.33)$$

where the classical self-energy of the charge, i.e., its interaction potential with the solid is given by,

$$\Sigma_c(\mathbf{r}) = -Q^2 \sum_\lambda \left(\frac{1}{\hbar \omega_\lambda} \right) |\varphi_\lambda(\mathbf{r})|^2. \quad (2.34)$$

This is independent of the state of the particle and represents the interaction potential of a static particle. When the normalized quantum expressions for $\varphi_\lambda(\mathbf{r})$ are substituted, the relation (2.34) reduces to the classical result of the form given by eq.(1.4).

Finally, in the general case when the time evolution of A is determined by both H_S and H_P , we can write

$$\langle \Delta A \rangle = \int d\mathbf{r} \langle \mathbf{k} | \mathbf{r} \rangle V_A(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{k}) \langle \mathbf{r} | \mathbf{k} \rangle \quad (2.35)$$

where the generalised potential whose expectation value in the particle state $|\mathbf{k}\rangle$ gives $\langle \Delta A \rangle$ is,

$$V_A(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{k}) = \frac{1}{i\hbar} \int_0^\infty dt \exp(-\eta t) \left(\frac{1}{\langle \mathbf{r} | \mathbf{k} \rangle} \int d\mathbf{r}' \langle \mathbf{r} | \langle [A(t), H_I] \rangle_s | \mathbf{r}' \rangle \times \langle \mathbf{r}' | \mathbf{k} \rangle \right). \quad (2.36)$$

$\langle \dots \rangle_s$ stands for the expectation value in a state $|\{n_\lambda\}\rangle$ of the solid.

When $\langle \Delta A \rangle$ is the second-order energy $(\Delta E)_2$, the corresponding interaction potential is the self-energy of the particle,

$$\Sigma_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) \equiv \frac{1}{2} V_{H_I}(\mathbf{r}; \mathbf{k}). \quad (2.37)$$

Using (2.36) and some straightforward algebra we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) = & \left(\frac{Q^2}{2}\right) \exp(-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \sum_{\lambda} \left[n_{\lambda} \varphi_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{r}) \int \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}') G\left(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'; \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2M} + \hbar\omega_{\lambda}\right) \right. \\ & \times \varphi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' + (n_{\lambda} + 1) \varphi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r}) \\ & \left. \times \int \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}') G\left(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'; \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2M} - \hbar\omega_{\lambda}\right) \varphi_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.38)$$

Here $G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'; E)$ is the Green function of the particle,

$$\begin{aligned} G(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'; E) & \equiv \sum_{\mathbf{k}'} \frac{\langle \mathbf{r} | \mathbf{k}' \rangle \langle \mathbf{k}' | \mathbf{r}' \rangle}{E - (\hbar^2 k'^2 / 2M)} \\ & = -\left(\frac{M}{2\pi\hbar^2}\right) \frac{\exp[-|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|(2M|E|/\hbar^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}]}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} \quad E < 0 \quad (2.39a) \end{aligned}$$

$$= -\left(\frac{M}{2\pi\hbar^2}\right) \frac{\exp[i|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|(2ME/\hbar^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}]}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} \quad E > 0. \quad (2.39b)$$

If the solid is in thermal equilibrium, n_{λ} in (2.38) is replaced by its thermal average,

$$\bar{n}_{\lambda} = 1/[\exp(\hbar\omega_{\lambda}/k_B T) - 1]. \quad (2.40)$$

In the ground state of the solid, or at $T = 0$ only the second term in (2.38) contributes to the interaction potential,

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{r}) = & \left(\frac{Q^2}{2}\right) \exp(-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \sum_{\lambda} \left[\varphi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r}) \int G\left(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'; \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2M} - \hbar\omega_{\lambda}\right) \right. \\ & \left. \times \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}') \varphi_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.41)$$

For the massive particle the semi-classical expression (2.34) can be simply extended to include the quantum correction. This is done by expanding the Green function (2.39) in inverse powers of the particle mass M ,

$$\lim_{M \rightarrow \infty} G\left(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'; \frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2M} - \hbar\omega_{\lambda}\right) \rightarrow -\frac{1}{\hbar\omega_{\lambda}} \left(\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') + \frac{\hbar}{2M\omega_{\lambda}} [k^2 \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') + \nabla^2 \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')] \right) \quad (2.42)$$

and substituting it in expression (2.41). This leads to the correction to the self-energy of the form

$$\Sigma_Q(\mathbf{r}) = -Q^2 \sum_{\lambda} \frac{1}{M\omega_{\lambda}^2} \{i\varphi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r})\mathbf{k} \cdot \nabla \varphi_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{r}) + 2\pi e\varphi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r})n_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{r})\} \quad (2.43)$$

which, in the static limit $\mathbf{k} = 0$ reduces further to

$$\lim_{\mathbf{k} \rightarrow 0} \Sigma_Q(\mathbf{r}) = -Q^2 \sum_{\lambda} \frac{2\pi e}{M\omega_{\lambda}^2} \varphi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r})n_{\lambda}^*(\mathbf{r}). \quad (2.44)$$

We shall use equations (2.38) to (2.41), together with their classical limit (2.34) in the next chapter to evaluate the interaction of a charged particle with a metal sphere, the collective charge oscillation modes of which are evaluated in the electrostatic limit in the hydrodynamic model of the metallic electrons. We shall also determine the quantum corrections (2.44) due to both bulk and surface plasmons there.

2.2.2 Discussion

There are a number of important observations and comments which relate to the formalism just presented. The structure of the Hamiltonian (2.21) as well as the definition of the state of the system in terms of the mixed representation $|\{n_{\lambda}\}\rangle|\mathbf{k}\rangle$ implies that all well defined modes or excitations of the system are known. In practice, however, only the long-wavelength collective modes can be evaluated, so that the state $|\{n_{\lambda}\}\rangle$ of the solid signifies such a collective mode. It should be kept in mind that the Landau damping type of processes such as the effects of plasmon decay into electron-hole pairs in the high- q part of the spectrum is not accounted for in this model. This weakness is well known in many-body theory where a proper evaluation of a quasi-particle state poses a substantial problem. It is also well known in the hydrodynamic model, employed by us, where a cut-off wave-vector q_c must be introduced in order to preserve (only) well defined

plasmons (Barton, 1979). Apart from plasmon decay into an electron-hole pair there is a range of other effects (to be discussed later) related to lattice periodicity, diffuse equilibrium electronic density profile at the surface and non-local exchange and correlation, which should be included in a full and exhaustive quantitative treatment. We believe, however that these effects play only a secondary role and will manifest themselves as corrections to the self-energy at separations less than about a few times the screening length for a charge outside the solid.

The other subtle problem concerns the basis set for the projectile, $|k\rangle$. While our use of plane waves for the incoming charge on the vacuum side of the solid-vacuum interface seems to be well justified, one has to be aware of other possible choices, especially in the insulator-insulator or metal-insulator interfaces (Echenique *et al.*, 1987).

The interaction of a charge with a *metal* surface is very well described by the model Hamiltonian (2.21). The dynamic mechanism responsible for the interaction is the coupling with the plasmons in a metal. The same model Hamiltonian will be applicable to an insulator surface, where the polarisation fluctuations associated with optical phonons will produce the coupling Boson field. But the model valid for insulators cannot be extended without caution to semiconductors. In semiconductors we expect a charge will couple to both optical and acoustic phonons, the later mechanism occurring through the deformation potential (Bardeen and Shockley, 1950; Herring and Vogt, 1956).

CHAPTER 3. INTERACTION OF CHARGES WITH METALS

3.1 Plasmon modes in the hydrodynamic model

A single semi-infinite planar jellium surface was the model system in nearly all previous theoretical studies on the interaction of charges with metals. Our object here is to apply the self-energy formalism developed in the previous chapter and also the simpler semi-classical plasmon field method to a few other geometries. The practical importance of each of the non-planar cases studied will be emphasized in the appropriate paragraph. We base our treatment of plasma modes in metal on the hydrodynamic model for metallic electrons.

The idea of treating the ground-state properties of an inhomogeneous electronic system as being determined by the ground state electronic density $n_0(\mathbf{r})$ is the basis of the Thomas-Fermi method (March, 1957, 1983). The hydrodynamic model derived by Bloch in 1933 may be considered as an extension of the static Thomas-Fermi method to the electronic systems in which the total density $n(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is allowed to deviate slightly from the Thomas-Fermi equilibrium density $n_0(\mathbf{r})$. Bloch's model was applied to problems of atomic physics such as the stopping power, photoabsorption and scattering cross sections (Bloch, 1933; Jensen, 1937; Wakano, 1961; Ball *et al.*, 1973). The hydrodynamic model is also commonly applied in some problems of metal, semiconductor and surface physics.

An exhaustive account and discussion of various applications of the hydrodynamic model in surface physics can be found in works of Summerside (1979), Mehrotra (1979), Barton (1979) and Lundqvist (1983).

The basic hydrodynamic equations of motion can be derived from Hamilton's variational principle

$$\delta I = \delta \int_{t_1}^{t_2} L dt = 0 \quad (3.1)$$

applied to the hydrodynamic Lagrangian function, $L = \int d\mathbf{r} \mathcal{L}$, (Bloch, 1933).

These equations can also be obtained from the statistical moments method (see e.g. Balescu, 1975). In 1974 Ying offered a generalization of the original Bloch's model, in which the ground state equilibrium electron density $n_0(\mathbf{r})$ is given by the Hohenberg-Kohn-Sham theory of the inhomogeneous electron gas (Hohenberg and Kohn, 1964; Kohn and Sham, 1965).

We present a derivation of the hydrodynamic equations in the remainder of this section, following the approach of Ying (1974).

Consider an inhomogeneous electronic system in the hydrodynamic limit. It is characterized by the density $n(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and the hydrodynamic velocity field $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)$. We assume that the flow is irrotational and hence the velocity can be derived from the scalar velocity potential $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$,

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t) = -\nabla\psi(\mathbf{r}, t). \quad (3.2)$$

We require further that no magnetic fields are present in the system.

The Hamiltonian function for the electronic system (in atomic units with the electron charge = -1) is given by

$$H = \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{r} |\nabla\psi|^2 n(\mathbf{r}, t) + \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \frac{n(\mathbf{r}, t)n(\mathbf{r}', t)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} - \int d\mathbf{r} V(\mathbf{r}, t)n(\mathbf{r}, t) + G[n(\mathbf{r}, t)] \quad (3.3)$$

where the first term is the *hydrodynamic* kinetic energy, the second term represents the Coulomb self-interaction, the third term describes the interaction of electrons with the nuclei and with the external potentials. $G[n(\mathbf{r}, t)]$ is the functional of the electronic density known from the density functional theory, and represents the *microscopic* kinetic energy and exchange and correlation energies, $G[n(\mathbf{r}, t)] = \int d\mathbf{r} g[n(\mathbf{r}, t)]$. Treating n and ψ as canonically conjugate variables, i.e., $n = \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \psi}$ we can write the Lagrangian as,

$$L = \int d\mathbf{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} n(\mathbf{r}, t) - H. \quad (3.4)$$

The Lagrangian density is

$$\mathcal{L} = n \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi - \frac{1}{2} |\nabla \psi|^2 n - \frac{n(\mathbf{r})}{2} \int d\mathbf{r}' \frac{n(\mathbf{r}', t)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} + V(\mathbf{r}, t)n - g[n]. \quad (3.5)$$

The corresponding Euler-Lagrange equations are,

(a) for the generalized coordinate ψ , the equation of continuity

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} n - \nabla \cdot (n \nabla \psi) = 0 \quad (3.6)$$

(b) for the generalized coordinate n , the Bernoulli equation (commonly known also as the Euler equation)

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi - \frac{1}{2} |\nabla \psi|^2 - \int d\mathbf{r}' \frac{n(\mathbf{r}', t)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} + V - \frac{\delta G[n]}{\delta n} = 0. \quad (3.7)$$

Here $\frac{\delta G[n]}{\delta n}$ is the functional derivative (Goldstein, 1953, def.11.19). The non-linear hydrodynamic equations in the form given by (3.6)–(3.7) are extremely difficult to solve. They are substantially simplified by linearization. This is done by assuming that all quantities can be expanded for small-amplitude motion in the following way

$$n(\mathbf{r}, t) = n_0(\mathbf{r}) + n_1(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (3.8a)$$

$$V(\mathbf{r}, t) = V_0(\mathbf{r}) + V_{ext}(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (3.8b)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = 0 + \psi_1(\mathbf{r}, t). \quad (3.8c)$$

The consequence of these assumptions on $\frac{\delta G[n]}{\delta n}$ is that it can be expanded in a functional Taylor series and only the first order term is retained.

The linearized hydrodynamic equations are obtained upon substituting (3.8) in (3.6) and (3.7), this gives

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} n_1 = \nabla \cdot (n_0 \nabla \psi_1) \quad (3.9)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi_1 = \int d\mathbf{r}' \frac{n_1(\mathbf{r}, t)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} - V_{ext}(\mathbf{r}, t) + \int \frac{\delta^2 G[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r}) \delta n(\mathbf{r}')} \Big|_{n_0} n_1(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}'. \quad (3.10)$$

This system of equations can be solved for the function $n_1(\mathbf{r}, t)$ if the following steps are performed.

(i) take the time derivative of (3.9); this yields

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} n_1 = \nabla \cdot \left(n_0 \nabla \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi_1 \right) \quad (3.11)$$

(ii) take the gradient, then multiply by n_0 and finally take the divergence of both sides of (3.10); this yields

$$\nabla \cdot \left(n_0 \nabla \frac{\partial \psi_1}{\partial t} \right) = \nabla n_0 \cdot \nabla \mathcal{F}_v + n_0 \nabla^2 \mathcal{F}_v \quad (3.12)$$

where $\mathcal{F}_v$ represents the right hand side of eq.(3.10). Substituting (3.11) into (3.12) gives finally the equation for n_1

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} n_1 = \nabla n_0 \cdot \nabla \mathcal{F}_v + n_0 \nabla^2 \mathcal{F}_v. \quad (3.13)$$

We are interested in free oscillations of the electronic system, hence the external potential $V_{ext}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is dropped out. We introduce the notation,

$$\mathcal{F} := -\varphi_1(\mathbf{r}, t) + \int \frac{\delta^2 G[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r}) \delta n(\mathbf{r}')} \Big|_{n_0} n_1(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' \quad (3.14)$$

where

$$\varphi_1(\mathbf{r}, t) = - \int d\mathbf{r}' \frac{n_1(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}. \quad (3.15)$$

The potential $\varphi_1(\mathbf{r}, t)$ satisfies the Poisson equation,

$$\nabla^2 \varphi_1(\mathbf{r}, t) = 4\pi n_1(\mathbf{r}, t). \quad (3.16)$$

The *exact* (up to the first order $\equiv$) linearized hydrodynamic equation of motion describing the free-oscillations of the electronic system is written in the form,

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} n_1(\mathbf{r}, t) = \nabla n_0(\mathbf{r}) \cdot \nabla \mathcal{F} + n_0(\mathbf{r}) \nabla^2 \mathcal{F}. \quad (3.17)$$

In the following, we consider only those electronic systems in which the *local* spatial variation of n_0 is small so that the term involving ∇n_0 will be neglected. We require also that the normal mode solutions have the oscillatory form, $n_1(\mathbf{r}, t) = n_1(\mathbf{r})e^{i\omega t}$. Equation (3.17) is now simplified to yield

$$-\omega^2 n_1 = n_0 \nabla^2 \mathcal{F}. \quad (3.18)$$

The term on the right hand side of this equation represents a complicated expression involving the functional $G[n]$ (as yet unspecified). $G[n]$ is a unique functional of the ground state density n (Hohenberg and Kohn, 1964) and it describes all the intrinsic many body effects (intrinsic kinetic energy, exchange and correlation). There is a certain degree of arbitrariness as to the most appropriate and convenient choice of $G[n]$ in various situations (Lang, 1973; Kohn and Vashishta, 1983; Callaway and March, 1984; Gunnarson and Jones, 1980; Williams and von Barth, 1983; Kohn, 1985). The study of a form of $G[n]$ is an important subject on its own and we will not go into any details here.

The simplest (Thomas-Fermi) form of $G[n]$ is,

$$G[n] = \int d\mathbf{r} \frac{3}{10} (3\pi^2)^{2/3} n^{5/3}(\mathbf{r}). \quad (3.19)$$

It describes the intrinsic kinetic energy of a (locally) uniform free-electron gas. For this choice of the functional $G[n]$ expression (3.18) can readily be reduced to the form,

$$[\omega^2 - \omega_P^2 + \beta^2 \nabla^2] n_1(\mathbf{r}) = 0 \quad (3.20)$$

where $\omega_P^2 = \frac{4\pi e^2 n_0}{m}$ (in dimensional units), ω_P is the plasma frequency. This is the linearized hydrodynamic equation of motion which is essential to our ensuing

studies. β is called the *dispersion parameter* and for the Thomas-Fermi form of $G[n]$, (3.19), it is given by

$$\beta^2 = \frac{1}{3}v_F^2 \quad (3.21)$$

where v_F is the Fermi velocity.

The crucial assumption is now advanced, that the parametrization in terms of the dispersion parameter β , leading to eq.(3.20) is valid also for more realistic models of the functional $G[n]$.

Assuming the plane wave solutions, equation (3.20) can be immediately solved in the case of an infinite homogeneous electron gas. This gives the hydrodynamic dispersion relation for the longitudinal bulk plasmons,

$$\omega^2 = \omega_P^2 + \beta^2 k^2 . \quad (3.22)$$

The possible choices of parametrization of β can now be deduced by comparing (3.22) with the random phase approximation (RPA) dispersion relation (Pines, 1964; Mahan, 1981). It is seen that the Thomas-Fermi choice (3.21) corresponds to the static ($\omega = 0$) or low frequency limit of long wavelength RPA dielectric response, whereas for the high frequency, typical of metals ($\omega_P \sim 10^{15} \text{ sec}^{-1}$), long wavelength response the parametrization of β should be

$$\beta^2 = \frac{3}{5}v_F^2 . \quad (3.23)$$

Bloch proved (Bloch, 1933; Barton, 1979; Lundqvist, 1983) that the normal mode solutions (n_1, ψ_1) to the variational problem (3.1) form a biorthogonal system, defined by the property (after normalization)

$$\int d\mathbf{r} n_\lambda(\mathbf{r}) \psi_\tau(\mathbf{r}) = \delta_{\lambda\tau} \quad (3.24)$$

where the subscripts (1) are dropped here and in the following from the first order quantities n, ψ , etc.

A linear superposition of normal mode solutions gives a general solution for free oscillations

$$n(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{\lambda} a_{\lambda} n_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\omega_{\lambda} t} \quad (3.25a)$$

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sum_{\lambda} b_{\lambda} \psi_{\lambda}(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\omega_{\lambda} t} . \quad (3.25b)$$

Having obtained the normal, plasmon modes in a given geometry, the plasmon field can be quantized by a standard canonical quantization procedure (see e.g. Barton, 1979).

The hydrodynamic equation (3.17) is solved in the present work (in various geometries) subject to a boundary condition of a vanishing normal current at the abrupt, step-like jellium surface of a metal. This represents highly idealized model, however “we adopt it (without further apologies beyond this subsection) because it yields a tractable problem and has a distinguished history as a first approximation” (Barton, 1979). It has to be recorded that the attempts to employ a more realistic diffuse surface profile have been made by a number of workers. Within the realms of hydrodynamic model Boardman *et al.*, (1974) have demonstrated that, irrespective of the surface profile, the local surface mode with $\omega = \omega_P/\sqrt{2}$ is always present. A double-step-function model has facilitated an analytical solution of hydrodynamic equations in a planar case (Boardman *et al.*, 1975) and for a metallic sphere (Boardman and Paranjape, 1977; Ogale *et al.*, 1978). Equiluz and Quinn (1975) have included retardation effects as well as the double step surface profile in their analysis of plasmon dispersion on the metallic planar surface. We will consider a diffuse electronic surface profile in conjunction with the hydrodynamic model *and* the density functional theory in Chapter 4. It should be noted that the hydrodynamic theory describing the propagation of plasmons in periodic lattices has been developed by March and Tosi (1972).

This concludes the formal setting for studying the long-wavelength, collective

plasma modes in electronic systems. The method for evaluating the self-energy presented in Chapter 2 and the hydrodynamic formalism will now be applied to study self-energy of an external charge in various geometries.

The problem of a charged particle in close proximity to a semi-infinite metal surface has been studied in great detail. Some of that work has already been commented on in Chapter 1. The complete semi-classical analysis of normal modes and the image potential based on the hydrodynamic model and carried through along the line indicated in this chapter has been provided by Summerside and Mahanty (1978) and in the static case ($\omega = 0$) in quantized version by Barton (1979). Hence the problem of a charge near a semi-infinite metal surface will not be dealt with any further.

There is one important aspect of the *total potential* of a charged particle in the surface region that has to be briefly addressed. This relates to the existence of the positron bound states at the metal surface (Nieminen and Hodges, 1978). In this work we are concerned solely with the interaction potential ('image potential') arising due to an *induced* charge density and representing the response of the electron gas to an external perturbation. If however the charged particle crosses the surface, additional work is done by (or against, depending on the charge sign) the field of a surface *double layer*. The double layer formed by the equilibrium electron density profile will produce a positive (negative) shift in energy of a positron (electron) inside the metal. Hence, for positron there will appear a surface potential well, capable of forming a true bound state. The situation is presented schematically on Fig.3.1.

The first problem to be examined is the interaction potential of a charged particle placed in a vacuum gap between two metal surfaces.

Fig. 3.1. Schematic representation of the total surface potential for a positively charged particle near the jellium surface (after Nieminen and Hodges, 1978).

3.2 Correction to the image potential between metals

In this section we demonstrate, on the basis of the hydrodynamic model, that the potential of a charged particle in the gap between two metals is substantially different from that obtained by the multiple-image method; (Simmons, 1963a,b; Miskovsky *et al.*, 1982) when the gap is small. This is due to dispersion of plasmons, and has implications on analysis of tunnel devices. The results of this section were communicated in Michalewicz and Mahanty (1986).

The potential of a charged particle between two solid surfaces is of interest in analysis of experiments on tunneling. The conventional multiple-image method (Simmons, 1963a,b; Miskovsky *et al.*, 1982) of evaluating this potential when the particle is between two metals would work if the separation between the surfaces is large compared with the Thomas-Fermi screening lengths in them. But since tunneling experiments are done with very small gaps, image theory will not be

applicable. In this section the problem is examined for two parallel metal surfaces including the effect of plasmon dispersion in them.

Let us consider a system of two parallel metal surfaces as depicted in Figure 3.2.

Fig.3.2. The charge is at z_0 in a vacuum gap between two jellium metals.

The origin is chosen on surface 1 with the z -axis normal to it, and the second surface is at $z = l$. The plasma frequencies and dispersion parameters are $\omega_{p(j)}$ and β_j , $j = 1, 2$, with $\beta_j^2 = \frac{3}{5}v_{F(j)}^2$, $v_{F(j)}$ being the Fermi velocity of the j -th metal. The contribution of the plasmons to the potential of the charged particle in the gap can be evaluated in the manner suggested in §3.1 and §2.2.1 (eq.2.34), first solving the equation for the fluctuation number density of the metallic electrons in the hydrodynamic model using the boundary condition of the vanishing of the normal current at the two surfaces, and then evaluating the induced potential using the Poisson equation.

The equation for the fluctuation number density of the electrons in the presence of a static charged particle with charge Q located at z_0 , $0 < z_0 < l$, can be

written in the form,

$$(\nabla^2 - k_1^2)n = 0, \quad z < 0; \quad (3.26a)$$

$$(\nabla^2 - k_2^2)n = 0, \quad z > l. \quad (3.26b)$$

Here $k_j = [\omega_{p(j)}/\beta_j]$, k_j^{-1} being the Thomas-Fermi screening length in the j -th metal.

The boundary conditions of the vanishing of the normal current at the surfaces are,

$$\beta_j^2 \frac{\partial n}{\partial z} + \frac{\omega_{p(j)}^2}{4\pi} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left\{ \int \frac{n(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}'}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} - \left(\frac{Q}{e} \right) \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{z}_0|} \right\} = 0, \quad (3.27)$$

at $z = 0$ with $j = 1$, and at $z = l$ with $j = 2$.

Let,

$$n(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \int d^2\kappa \{ \Theta(-z) C_1(\kappa) \exp(\gamma_1 z) + \Theta(z-l) C_2(\kappa) \exp[-\gamma_2(z-l)] \} \exp(i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \boldsymbol{\rho}), \quad (3.28)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ is a wave vector parallel to the surfaces and $\boldsymbol{\rho}$ is the corresponding component of $\mathbf{r}$, and $\gamma_j = (\kappa^2 + k_j^2)^{1/2}$. This choice for n satisfies equation (3.26). The coefficients $C_j(\kappa)$ can be evaluated by substituting equation (3.28) in (3.27) and we get,

$$C_1(\kappa) = \left(\frac{Q}{e} \right) \frac{(\gamma_1 + \kappa) [k_1^2 A_2(\kappa) \exp(-\kappa z_0) - k_1^2 k_2^2 \exp\{-\kappa(2l - z_0)\}]}{A_1(\kappa) A_2(\kappa) - k_1^2 k_2^2 \exp(-2\kappa l)}, \quad (3.29a)$$

$$C_2(\kappa) = \left(\frac{Q}{e} \right) \frac{(\gamma_2 + \kappa) [k_2^2 A_1(\kappa) \exp\{-\kappa(l - z_0)\} - k_1^2 k_2^2 \exp\{-\kappa(l + z_0)\}]}{A_1(\kappa) A_2(\kappa) - k_1^2 k_2^2 \exp(-2\kappa l)}, \quad (3.29b)$$

with

$$A_j(\kappa) = 2\gamma_j(\gamma_j + \kappa) - k_j^2. \quad (3.30)$$

The induced potential in the region $0 < z < l$ is,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_I(\mathbf{r}) &= -e \int \frac{n(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}'}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} \\ &= -\left(\frac{e}{2\pi} \right) \int \frac{d^2\kappa}{\kappa} \left[C_1(\kappa) \frac{\exp(-\kappa z)}{(\gamma_1 + \kappa)} + C_2(\kappa) \frac{\exp\{-\kappa(l - z)\}}{(\gamma_2 + \kappa)} \right]. \quad (3.31) \end{aligned}$$

The potential of the charged particle is then,

$$\begin{aligned}
 V(z_0) &= (Q/2)\phi_I(z_0) \\
 &= -(Q^2/2)\frac{1}{2\pi} \int \frac{d^2\kappa}{\kappa} [k_1^2 A_2(\kappa) \exp(-2\kappa z_0) + k_2^2 A_1(\kappa) \exp(-2\kappa l + 2\kappa z_0) \\
 &\quad - 2k_1^2 k_2^2 \exp(-2\kappa l)] / [A_1(\kappa)A_2(\kappa) - k_1^2 k_2^2 \exp(-2\kappa l)] . \quad (3.32)
 \end{aligned}$$

In the non-dispersive limit of $\beta_j \rightarrow 0$ or $k_j \rightarrow \infty$, the above formula reduces to the usual multiple-image result for a charged particle between two ideally conducting plates (Simmons, 1963a,b; Miskovsky *et al.*, 1982)

$$V_{Im}(z_0) = -(Q^2/2)\frac{1}{2\pi} \int \frac{d^2\kappa}{\kappa} \frac{[\exp(-2\kappa z_0) - 2 \exp(-2\kappa l) + \exp(-2\kappa l + 2\kappa z_0)]}{[1 - \exp(-2\kappa l)]} . \quad (3.33)$$

Fig. 3.3 gives the graphs for the potentials calculated from equations (3.32) and (3.33) for the case when $k_1 l = 10$ and $k_2/k_1 = 1.2$. It may be noted that the difference in the curves is substantial, the actual potential being higher than that obtained from image theory throughout the gap. Also, there will be asymmetry in the curve about the middle of the gap for two dissimilar metals. The necessity of using the correct potential for interpreting data such as the current-voltage characteristics of metal-vacuum-metal tunneling junctions cannot be over-emphasized (Simmons, 1963a,b; Miskovsky *et al.*, 1982) and computations similar to that given above for other electrode geometries in use in tunnel devices are important.

3.3 Interaction of a charged particle with a metallic sphere

3.3.1 Introduction

In recent years interest in the metallic systems of spherical geometry and the dimensions of the order of tens of nanometers and less, has grown enormously. The activity has been stimulated by the peculiar structural, (Smith *et al.*, 1986) electronic (Kubo, 1962, 1968; Gorkov and Eliashberg, 1965) and optical (Smithard,

Fig.3.3. The potential of the charged particle (in units of $Q^2 k_1$) as a function of z_0 (in units of k_1^{-1}). The solid curve is for the present calculation of eq.(3.32) and the dashed curve is the potential evaluated by multiple imaging (3.33).

1973; Schmidt-Ott *et al.*, 1980) properties of such systems (Halperin, 1986). On the practical level the properties of minute metallic spheres are of substantial importance in problems of catalysis, colloid science and aerosol physics and for monitoring the industrial pollution in environmental sciences (Anderson, 1975; Collis

and Russel, 1976; McNulty *et al.*, 1980; Baltes and Šimanek, 1982). Arrays of metallic micro-hemispheres have been fabricated for possible future opto-electronic applications (Craighead and Nicklasson, 1984). Metallic spheres embedded in a dielectric matrix provide an example of a non-linear optical system with important practical electronic applications (Flytzanis *et al.*, 1986).

Experiments on small particles in gas suspension have been reviewed by Burtcher and Schmidt-Ott (1985) and the same group reported recently the first measurement of gas (O_2) adsorption to free ultrafine particles of Ag (Müller *et al.*, 1987).

Our emphasis and motivation in studying the minute metal spheres is different. We focus our attention first on the hydrodynamic, collective plasmon modes of the metallic sphere. Subsequently we use the results relating to plasmon frequencies and density fluctuations to obtain the interaction potential of a charged particle in close proximity to a metal sphere in a manner indicated in section 2.2.

Both of these undertakings bring new results and understanding. The plasmon modes on a small sphere or spheroid are well known from experiments (Fujimoto *et al.*, 1967; Kreibig and Zacharias, 1970; Petersen, 1977; Warmack and Humphrey, 1986). They were also analysed theoretically previously on the basis of hydrodynamic model (see e.g. Ferrel *et al.*, 1985; Fujimoto and Komaki, 1968; Crowell and Ritchie, 1968; Boardman and Paranjape, 1977; Ruppin, 1978; Ogale *et al.*, 1978; Agarwal and O'Neil, 1983). Recently other methods, such as the time-dependent local density approximation, have also been used in studying multiple collective excitations in small metal spheres (Ekardt, 1985; Beck, 1987).

Our treatment however, allows us to evaluate and classify the plasma modes in a straightforward, analytical manner, which is both physical and illustrative. We find that only a finite number of surface modes exist in the dispersive sphere, a point that had not been noticed in the commonly adopted classification of the

modes in terms of $l = 1, 2, \dots$. The second and primary task here is the evaluation of the interaction potential of a charged particle near a metal sphere. This problem, to the best of the author's knowledge, has not been as yet treated by other than classical methods (see e.g. Landau *et al.*, 1984; Wood, 1981). Its solution is essential in the studies of the inter-electrode potential barrier in the model of the scanning tunneling microscope (STM). We will present the full analysis of this latter topic in section 3.4. The results presented in this section are published in Mahanty and Michalewicz (1986).

3.3.2 The plasmon modes of a metallic sphere

We consider a jellium sphere of radius R with an equilibrium electron density which is a constant n_0 within the sphere and drops to zero at the surface. The linearised equation of motion for the density fluctuation $n(\mathbf{r}, t)$ in the time-independent form is given by (3.20)

$$(\omega_p^2 - \beta^2 \nabla^2)n = \omega^2 n \quad \omega_p^2 = 4\pi n_0 e^2 / m. \quad (3.34)$$

ω_p is the plasma frequency and β is the parameter describing the dispersion of plasmons. The eigenvalue ω_λ obtained for a solution $n_\lambda(\mathbf{r})$ of (3.34) with the boundary condition of vanishing of the radial current at the surface gives the frequency of the λ th plasmon mode. The parameter β^2 equals $\frac{3}{5}v_F^2$ at high frequencies (Jackson, 1962), and is $\frac{1}{3}v_F^2$ at low frequencies — here we shall treat it as a parameter.

In (3.34) there are two distinct frequency regions $\omega^2 < \omega_p^2$ and $\omega^2 > \omega_p^2$. With the above boundary condition, which in terms of n can be written as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[-n_0 e^2 \int_{r' \leq R} \frac{n(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}'}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} - m\beta^2 n(\mathbf{r}) \right]_{r=R} = 0 \quad (3.35)$$

we get the following solutions and dispersion relations in the two regions, assuming that

$$n(\mathbf{r}) \equiv n_{l,m}(\mathbf{r}) = n_l(r) Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) \quad 0 < r < R. \quad (3.36)$$

(i) For $\omega^2 < \omega_p^2$,

$$n_l^S(r) = N_l^S m_l(\kappa_l r) \quad \kappa_l^2 = \frac{\omega_p^2 - \omega^2}{\beta^2} \quad m_l(z) \equiv \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2z}} I_{l+\frac{1}{2}}(z). \quad (3.37)$$

The corresponding frequency ω_l is the root of the equation

$$\frac{m_l(\kappa R)}{\kappa R} = \left[1 - \left(\frac{2l+1}{l+1} \right) \frac{\kappa^2 \beta^2}{\omega_p^2} \right] \frac{m_l'(\kappa R)}{l} \quad \kappa^2 = \frac{\omega_p^2 - \omega^2}{\beta^2}. \quad (3.38)$$

N_l^S is a normalisation factor. It is easy to show that $l=0$ does not give a root for ω in (3.38) and the solutions start with $l=1$. It can also be shown that for finite β there is an upper limit l_{max} ,

$$l_{max} \cong \frac{(36 + 16y^2)^{1/2} - 6}{8} \quad y^2 = \frac{\omega_p^2}{\beta^2} R^2 \equiv k_0^2 R^2 \quad (3.39)$$

beyond which solutions of (3.38) for $\omega^2 < \omega_p^2$ cannot arise. $k_0^{-1} = (\beta/\omega_p)$ is the Thomas-Fermi screening length. In the non-dispersive limit $\beta \rightarrow 0$ the frequencies obtained from (3.38) are the well known result,

$$\lim_{\beta \rightarrow 0} \omega_l^2 = \omega_p^2 \left(\frac{l}{2l+1} \right). \quad (3.40)$$

We shall call these solutions the surface modes, denoted by the superscript S , since $m_l(\kappa_l r)$ vanishes at the centre of the sphere and monotonically goes to a maximum at the surface for all l in the range $1 \leq l < l_{max}$.

The potential $\varphi_{l,m}^S(r)$ corresponding to the mode (l, m) is obtained by solving Poisson's equation

$$\nabla^2 \varphi_{l,m}^S(\mathbf{r}) = 4\pi e n_{l,m}^S(\mathbf{r}) \equiv 4\pi e n_l^S(r) Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi). \quad (3.41)$$

The normalisation of $n_{l,m}^S$ and of $\varphi_{l,m}^S$ can be done exactly as indicated by Barton (1979), and we get

$$\varphi_{l,m}^S(\mathbf{r}) = 4\pi e \left(\frac{\hbar n_0}{2mR} \right)^{1/2} [\kappa_l R (\omega_l \Delta_l^S)^{1/2}]^{-1} \left[\frac{m_l(\kappa_l r)}{m_{l-1}(\kappa_l R)} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \left(\frac{l+1}{2l+1} \right) \left(a_l + \frac{\kappa_l R b_l}{l+1} \right) \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^l \Big] Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) \quad r < R \quad (3.42a) \\
& = -4\pi e \left(\frac{\hbar n_0}{2mR} \right)^{1/2} [(2l+1)(\omega_l \Delta_l^S)^{1/2}]^{-1} \\
& \quad \times \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^{l+1} Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) \quad r > R. \quad (3.42b)
\end{aligned}$$

Here

$$\Delta_l^S = \frac{b_l}{l} - \frac{1}{2}(a_l^2 - c_l) \quad (3.43a)$$

and a_l , b_l and c_l are defined through the equations

$$m_l(\kappa_l R) = a_l m_{l+1}(\kappa_l R) \quad (3.43b)$$

$$m_l'(\kappa_l R) = b_l m_{l+1}(\kappa_l R) \quad (3.43c)$$

$$m_{l-1}(\kappa_l R) = c_l m_{l+1}(\kappa_l R). \quad (3.43d)$$

Using (3.38) and the recursion relations for modified spherical Bessel functions we can write

$$a_l = \frac{\kappa_l R}{l} \left[\left(\frac{l+1}{2l+1} \right) \frac{k_0^2}{\kappa_l^2} - 1 \right] \quad (3.44a)$$

$$b_l = \left(\frac{l+1}{2l+1} \right) \frac{k_0^2}{\kappa_l^2} \quad (3.44b)$$

$$c_l = \left(\frac{l+1}{l} \right) \left(\frac{k_0^2}{\kappa_l^2} - 1 \right). \quad (3.44c)$$

(ii) For $\omega^2 \geq \omega_P^2$,

$$n_{l,\nu}^B(r) = N_{l,\nu}^B j_l(k_{l,\nu} r) \quad k_{l,\nu}^2 = \frac{\omega_{l,\nu}^2 - \omega_P^2}{\beta^2} \quad 0 < r < R. \quad (3.45)$$

Here, j_l being spherical Bessel functions, the modes have nodes between the centre and the surface of the sphere. We shall denote these modes as bulk modes with the superscript B . The frequencies $\omega_{l,\nu}$ are roots of the equation

$$\frac{j_l(kR)}{kR} = \left[1 + \frac{\beta^2 k^2}{\omega_P^2} \left(\frac{2l+1}{l+1} \right) \right] \frac{j_l'(kr)}{l} \quad k = \frac{\omega^2 - \omega_P^2}{\beta^2}. \quad (3.46)$$

This equation has an infinite number of solutions for each l , and hence the second index ν is introduced in (3.45).

It may be mentioned here that unlike the surface modes, bulk modes also exist for $l = 0$. They are the roots of

$$j'_0(kR) = j_1(kR) = 0. \quad (3.47)$$

One root occurs at $k = 0$, i.e., for $\omega^2 = \omega_P^2$. The other roots correspond to the zeros of $j_1(kR)$.

The corresponding normalised potential for $l \neq 0$ is,

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{l,\nu;m}^B(\mathbf{r}) = & -4\pi e \left(\frac{\hbar n_0}{2mR} \right)^{1/2} [k_{l,\nu} R (\omega_{l,\nu} \Delta_{l,\nu}^B)^{1/2}]^{-1} \\ & \times \left[\frac{j_l(k_{l,\nu} r)}{j_{l+1}(k_{l,\nu} R)} - \left(\frac{l+1}{2l+1} \right) \left(\frac{k_{l,\nu} R \beta_{l,\nu}}{l+1} + \alpha_{l,\nu} \right) \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^l \right] \\ & \times Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) \quad r < R \end{aligned} \quad (3.48a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} = & -4\pi e \left(\frac{\hbar n_0}{2mR} \right)^{1/2} [(2l+1)(\omega_{l,\nu} \Delta_{l,\nu}^B)^{1/2}]^{-1} \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^{l+1} \\ & \times Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) \quad r > R. \end{aligned} \quad (3.48b)$$

Here

$$\Delta_{l,\nu}^B = \frac{1}{2}(\alpha_{l,\nu}^2 - \gamma_{l,\nu}) - \frac{\beta_{l,\nu}}{l} \quad (3.49a)$$

and $\alpha_{l,\nu}$, $\beta_{l,\nu}$ and $\gamma_{l,\nu}$ are defined through the equations

$$j_l(k_{l,\nu} R) = \alpha_{l,\nu} j_{l+1}(k_{l,\nu} R) \quad (3.49b)$$

$$j'_l(k_{l,\nu} R) = \beta_{l,\nu} j_{l+1}(k_{l,\nu} R) \quad (3.49c)$$

$$j_{l+1}(k_{l,\nu} R) = \gamma_{l,\nu} j_{l+1}(k_{l,\nu} R). \quad (3.49d)$$

Using (3.46) and the recursion relations for spherical Bessel functions we get,

$$\alpha_{l,\nu} = \frac{k_{l,\nu} R}{l} \left[1 + \frac{k_0^2}{k_{l,\nu}^2} \left(\frac{l+1}{2l+1} \right) \right] \quad (3.50a)$$

$$\beta_{l,\nu} = \frac{k_0^2}{k_{l,\nu}^2} \left(\frac{l+1}{2l+1} \right) \quad (3.50b)$$

$$\gamma_{l,\nu} = \left(\frac{l+1}{l} \right) \left(1 + \frac{k_0^2}{k_{l,\nu}^2} \right). \quad (3.50c)$$

For $l = 0$, the bulk mode potential is

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{0,\nu}^B(\mathbf{r}) &= -4\pi e \left(\frac{\hbar n_0 k_{0,\nu}}{m\omega_{0,\nu}} \right)^{1/2} [k_{0,\nu}R - \frac{1}{2} \sin(2k_{0,\nu}R)]^{-1/2} \\ &\quad \times \left[\frac{\sin(k_{0,\nu}r)}{k_{0,\nu}r} - \cos(k_{0,\nu}R) \right] \quad r < R \end{aligned} \quad (3.51a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= -4\pi e \left(\frac{\hbar n_0 k_{0,\nu}^3}{m\omega_{0,\nu}} \right)^{1/2} [k_{0,\nu}R - \frac{1}{2} \sin(2k_{0,\nu}R)]^{-1/2} \\ &\quad \times j_l(k_{0,\nu}R)(R^2/r) \equiv 0 \quad r > R. \end{aligned} \quad (3.51b)$$

The last result follows from (3.47) which implies $j_l(k_{0,\nu}R) \equiv 0$ for all ν .

Figures 3.4(a) and (b) give the variation of some of the surface and bulk plasma frequencies with the radius of the sphere.

3.3.3 The interaction potential

We shall consider first the interaction potential between the charged particle and the sphere in the classical limits given by (2.34). Using the potentials given in equations (3.42), (3.48) and (3.51) we get for the surface mode and volume mode contributions to the interaction potential the following expressions.

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_c^S(r) &= -Q^2 \sum_{l=1}^{l_{max}} \sum_{m=-l}^l \left(\frac{1}{\hbar\omega_l} \right) |\varphi_{l,m}^S(\mathbf{r})|^2 \\ &= -\frac{Q^2}{2R} \sum_{l=1}^{l_{max}} \left(\frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_l^2} \right) \frac{1}{(2l+1)\Delta_l^S} \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^{2(l+1)} \quad r > R \end{aligned} \quad (3.52a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= -\frac{Q^2}{2R} \sum_{l=1}^{l_{max}} \left(\frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_l^2} \right) \frac{1}{\kappa_l^2 R^2 \Delta_l^S} \left[\frac{m_l(\kappa_l r)}{m_{l+1}(\kappa_l R)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left(\frac{l+1}{l(2l+1)} \right) \kappa_l R \left(\frac{k_0^2}{\kappa_l^2} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^{l+2} \right] \quad r < R. \end{aligned} \quad (3.52b)$$

This vanishes at $r = 0$ and at $r = \infty$, and has a minimum at the surface. For large r the value converges to that of the interaction potential of Q with a charge-neutral insulated sphere obtained by image theory (Stratton, 1941).

Fig 3.4(a) The bulk mode eigen-frequencies ($\omega_{i,\nu}^2/\omega_p^2 - 1$) against radius of the sphere R for the first $l = 1, 2$ and $\nu = 1, 2, 3$ bulk modes of the sphere. For curve A: $l = 1, \nu = 0$; for C: $l = 1, \nu = 1$; for E: $l = 1, \nu = 2$; for B: $l = 2, \nu = 0$; for D: $l = 2, \nu = 1$; and for F: $l = 2, \nu = 2$. For a fixed radius the eigen-frequencies of increasing order interlace in the same ways as the zeros of the spherical Bessel functions.

Fig.3.4(b) The surface mode eigen-frequency ω_l^2/ω_p^2 against radius of the sphere R for the $l = 1$ (line A), $l = 2$ (line B), $l = 3$ (line C), $l = 4$ (line D) and $l = 5$ (line E) modes. The screening length $\lambda = \beta/\omega_p = 0.8$ nm corresponds to an Al sphere. The horizontal lines for $(\omega_l^2/\omega_p^2) = \frac{1}{2}$ and $\frac{1}{3}$ indicate the non-dispersive limit of surface plasmons ($\beta = 0$) which is formally equivalent to the limit $R \rightarrow \infty$ (flat surface). All the eigen-frequencies are then contained in the interval $(\frac{1}{3}, \frac{1}{2})$.

The contribution to the classical interaction potential from the bulk modes is

$$\begin{aligned}\Sigma_c^B(r) &= -Q^2 \sum_{l=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-l}^l \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1}{\hbar\omega_{l,\nu}} \right) |\varphi_{l,\nu;m}^B(\mathbf{r})|^2 \\ &= -\frac{Q^2}{2R} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_{l,\nu}^2 \Delta_{l,\nu}^B} \left(\frac{1}{(2l+1)} \right) \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^{2l+2} \quad r > R \quad (3.53a)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}&= -\frac{Q^2}{2R} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_{l,\nu}^2 \Delta_{l,\nu}^B} \frac{(2l+1)}{(k_{l,\nu}R)^2} \left[\frac{j_l(k_{l,\nu}r)}{j_{l+1}(k_{l,\nu}R)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \left(\frac{l+1}{l(2l+1)} \right) k_{l,\nu}R \left(\frac{k_0^2}{k_{l,\nu}^2} + 1 \right) \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^{l+2} \right]^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{Q^2}{R} \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_{0,\nu}^2} \right) \frac{\{j_0(k_{0,\nu}r) - \cos(k_{0,\nu}R)\}^2}{\{1 - j_0(2k_{0,\nu}R)\}} \quad r < R. \quad (3.53b)\end{aligned}$$

The second term in (3.53b) is the contribution from the $l = 0$ mode. At the centre of the sphere the value of the potential is given only by the $l = 0$ mode and has the form

$$\Sigma_c^B(r \rightarrow 0) = -\frac{Q^2}{R} \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_{0,\nu}^2} \right) \frac{[1 - \cos(k_{0,\nu}R)]^2}{[1 - j_0(2k_{0,\nu}R)]}. \quad (3.54)$$

For a large sphere this tends to the value,

$$\lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} \Sigma_c^B(r \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow \lim_{R \rightarrow \infty} \left(-\frac{Q^2 k_0}{2} \tanh(Rk_0) \right) = -\frac{Q^2 k_0}{2} \quad (3.55)$$

which is the well known value of the self-energy of a charged particle embedded in a homogeneous dispersive plasma. Figure 3.5 gives a plot of the contributions of various mode types to the total self-energy. The self-energy of a static charge outside and inside the sphere, for different sphere radii R is plotted in figure 3.6.

3.3.4 The interaction potential: quantum correction

The quantum correction to the self-energy of a massive particle has been obtained in section 2.2.1 (equations (2.43)–(2.44)). The contribution of the surface modes in the correction term calculated for the case of a charged particle interact-

Figure 3.5. The contributions from different types of modes to the total self-energy of a static charge against distance from the centre of the sphere r/R , for an Al sphere of radius $R = 2$ nm. B , bulk modes' contribution; C , $l = 0$ bulk modes' contribution; D , surface modes' contribution; A , total self-energy. The units are eV/n^2 , where $n = Q/e$ is the multiple of the electronic charge.

Figure 3.6. The interaction potential of a static charged particle outside the Al sphere against distance from the centre r/R for spheres of various radii; $R = 2$ nm (A); $R = 6$ nm (B); $R = 10$ nm (C); $R = 60$ nm (D). The inset figure shows the interaction potential inside the sphere. The description is the same as that of the main figure.

ing with the plasmons in the sphere represented by (2.44) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_Q^S(r) = & -\frac{Q^2}{2R}(Rk_P)^{-2} \sum_{l=1}^{l_{max}} \frac{\omega_P^3}{\omega_l^3} \frac{(2l+1)}{\Delta_l^S} \\ & \times \left[\frac{m_l(\kappa_l r)}{m_{l+1}(\kappa_l R)} - \frac{(l+1)}{l(2l+1)} \kappa_l R \left(\frac{k_0^3}{\kappa_l^3} - 1 \right) \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^l \right] \frac{m_l(\kappa_l r)}{m_{l+1}(\kappa_l R)} \end{aligned} \quad (3.56a)$$

and for the contribution of the bulk modes,

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_Q^B(r) = & -\frac{Q^2}{2R}(Rk_P)^{-2} \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \sum_{\nu=0}^{\infty} \frac{\omega_P^3}{\omega_{l,\nu}^3} \frac{(2l+1)}{\Delta_{l,\nu}^B} \\ & \times \left[\frac{j_l(\kappa_{l,\nu} r)}{j_{l+1}(k_{l,\nu} R)} - \frac{(l+1)}{l(2l+1)} k_{l,\nu} R \left(\frac{k_0^2}{k_{l,\nu}^2} + 1 \right) \left(\frac{r}{R} \right)^l \right] \frac{j_l(\kappa_{l,\nu} r)}{j_{l+1}(k_{l,\nu} R)} \\ & - \frac{Q^2}{R}(Rk_P)^{-2} \sum_{\nu=1}^{\infty} \frac{\omega_P^3}{\omega_{0,\nu}^3} (Rk_{0,\nu})^2 j_0(k_{0,\nu} r) \\ & \times \frac{[j_0(k_{0,\nu} r) - \cos(k_{0,\nu} R)]}{[1 - j_0(2k_{0,\nu} R)]} \end{aligned} \quad (3.56b)$$

where $k_P^{-2} = \hbar/(2M\omega_P)$. The second term in (3.56b) describes the contribution due to the $l = 0$ mode.

The relative magnitude of the quantum correction for a stationary particle, $k_P^2 \Sigma_Q(r) / \Sigma_c(r)$, is plotted in figure 3.7 for different sphere radii R .

3.3.5 Discussion

Using the formalism developed in subsection 2.2.1 we have studied the case of a charged particle interacting with a metallic sphere.

The two distinct types of normal plasma modes of the sphere were classified and the dispersion relations were given in some detail, to stress some features not given in existing literature (Ogale *et al.*, 1978; Agarwal and O'Neil, 1983). It was found that only a finite number of surface modes exist in the dispersive sphere.

We have computed all the eigen-frequencies for the surface modes (up to 299 solutions for the sphere $R = 60$ nm). In the case of bulk modes the first 1200 eigen-frequencies were computed ($l = 30$, $\nu = 40$), and for the bulk $l = 0$ mode terms up to $\nu = 3000$ were included in the sums for self-energy.

Figure 3.7. The relative quantum contribution $k_p^2 \sum_Q(r) / \sum_c(r)$ of self-energy for a static charge inside the Al sphere of radius; $R = 2$ nm (A), 6 nm (B), 10 nm (C), 60 nm (D) against distance from the centre of the sphere r/R . The correction is less than 0.05% at the centre of the smallest sphere of radius $R = 2$ nm.

The main results depicted in figures 3.5 and 3.6 are exact outside the sphere, due to a finite sum in the surface part contribution to self-energy. However the error range in the numerical values of the self-energy inside the sphere are 30% for small r and 10% near the surface for spheres of radii $R < 10$ nm whereas for a sphere of radius $R = 60$ nm (line D in the inset of figure 3.6) the calculated values are far from their saturation. This is due to the truncation of the sum in expression (3.53b) after the first $l = 30$, $\nu = 40$ terms. The effect of truncation is less drastic for a smaller sphere (2–6 nm) but is quite large for a bigger sphere ($R = 60$ nm) (inset of figure 3.6).

It should be emphasised that the hydrodynamic model breaks down for very high frequencies and so the sum in (3.53b) is not infinite; there should be cut-off indices l_c and ν_c , where the sum is to be terminated. By inspection of figure 3.4(a) one notices that for bigger spheres the number of terms in the sum (3.53b) will be drastically higher:

$$l_c(R_1) \ll l_c(R_2) \quad \text{and} \quad \nu_c(R_1) \ll \nu_c(R_2) \quad \text{for} \quad R_1 < R_2 .$$

The quantum correction introduces the additional screening parameter $k_P^{-1} = (\hbar/2M\omega_P)^{1/2}$ in analogy with the polaron problem and with the case of planar geometry with non-dispersive surface plasmons (Manson and Ritchie 1981). The complete quantum result for $\Sigma(r)$ can, of course, be worked out from equations (2.38) and (2.39). But as has been pointed out in the case of planar geometry (Mahanty *et al.*, 1985), the effect of screening due to plasmon dispersion on $\Sigma(r)$ near the surface of a metal is more dominant than polaronic screening, and hence we have given only the leading order quantum correction term. The full quantum correction can of course be obtained by using eq.(2.38), and this has not been attempted here. The screening parameter $k_P^{-1} \simeq 1.4 \times 10^{-2}$ Å for a proton incoming to an Al target, therefore the quantum correction is found to be less than 0.05% even for the smallest sphere of radius 2 nm.

The discontinuity of the quantum correction at the surface (figure 3.7) results from the boundary condition of abrupt vanishing of the electronic density fluctuation at the surface (see (2.44)). By relaxing this boundary condition and allowing diffuse electronic density at the surface the continuity of the quantum correction is recovered. However its magnitude is smaller by one order and it rapidly vanishes in the close proximity of the surface.

3.4 Interaction potential of a charged particle in a plane-sphere geometry

3.4.1 Introduction

In this section the three-dimensional potential of a charged particle tunneling between a flat metal surface and a spherical metal tip is calculated within the framework of the hydrodynamic description of metallic electrons. It is demonstrated that the inclusion of coupling of surface modes in the two electrodes, even for separations as small as 10 times the screening length in either of them contributes less than 5% of the total potential of a point charge. Hence the potential is obtained as a superposition of contributions from a planar surface and a charge neutral, conducting sphere (and can include a simple, classical term for a sphere at a fixed potential). This should enable accurate determination of 3-dimensional tunnel currents in Scanning Tunneling Microscope geometry.

The successful development of the scanning tunneling microscopy (STM) by the IBM Zürich group (Binnig *et al.*, 1982a,b, 1983) has stimulated vigorous research activity in recent years. This promising experimental technique has already facilitated the study of the surface structure of metals, metallic glasses and semiconductors with atomic resolution (Scheel *et al.*, 1982; Binnig and Rohrer, 1982; Gimzewski *et al.*, 1985; Binnig *et al.*, 1986; Feenstra *et al.*, 1986a,b; Weisendanger *et al.*, 1987). The effort of experimentalists led to the STMs which can operate in

air at ambient pressure and in liquids (Park and Quate, 1986; Drake *et al.*, 1986). The principle of STM operation has been utilized to build prototype instruments for scanning tunneling potentiometry (Muralt and Pohl, 1986) and atomic force measurements (Binnig *et al.*, 1986).

The problems of the tunneling conductance of electrons, the lateral resolution of the STM and other theoretical issues have been treated using the transfer matrix, perturbation or direct methods in a number of papers (Tersoff and Hamann, 1983; Garcia *et al.*, 1983; Feuchtwang *et al.*, 1983; Baratoff, 1984; Garcia and Flores, 1984; Stoll *et al.*, 1984; Stoll, 1984; Tersoff and Hamann, 1985; Das and Mahanty, 1987). The tunneling occurs through a potential barrier consisting of the bias voltage and the 'image' potential.

The image potential arises from the interaction of the external charge with the charges induced in the metal due to the collective response of the electrons. The latter can be estimated using the hydrodynamic model which gives the response in terms of the plasmons (both surface and bulk). In this section we demonstrate that the image potential of a charged particle between a flat metal surface and a spherical metal tip arises mainly from surface plasmons on the planar surface and a finite number of surface plasmons on the sphere. The coupling of the surface modes in the two electrodes has a very small effect on the potential when the minimum separation is larger than about ten times the screening length. Therefore the multiple-image method for generating image potential (Simmons, 1963a,b; Miskovsky *et al.*, 1981, 1982) is not necessary for dispersive metals.

In the semi-classical model of a static charge between the two electrodes, we obtain a three-dimensional axially symmetric potential, which is everywhere finite and saturates to two different values on the surfaces of the electrodes. This result resolves the problem of classical image potential divergence at the surface discussed recently in the present context by Binnig *et al.*, (1984) and Payne and Inckson

(1985).

A study which addressed the same question of the charged particle potential in a model STM geometry identical with ours has been presented recently by Morawitz *et al.*, (1987) and Batra and Morawitz (1986). In that sense, our work is complementary to that of Morawitz *et al.* However, they use the classical, multiple-image method which, in our opinion, limits their results to ideal conductors. On the other hand, our treatment takes into account the dynamics of the collective modes of conduction electrons, including their spatial dispersion, and is thus specific to the metallic samples used.

3.4.2 The problem of plane-sphere coupling

The magnitude of the contribution to the total potential due to coupling between surface plasmons on a plane and a sphere is estimated using a general approach presented in section 3.2. The probing tip in the STM can be modelled as a minute metal sphere (Kuroda *et al.*, 1985; Drechsler and Bermond, 1986). It is assumed that the continuous hydrodynamic model of the electron gas in a small metal sphere is applicable. This assumption, however, must be treated with caution (Kubo, 1962, 1968).

Let us consider a metal sphere of radius R (medium 2) and a flat metal surface (medium 1) at a distance $z_0 - R$ from the surface of the sphere. The z -axis is normal to the planar surface and has its origin at the centre of a sphere. An external, stationary point charge Q is confined, for simplicity, to the axial line at z_1 , $R \leq z_1 \leq z_0$ (Fig.3.8).

We assume that the density of conduction electrons in both metallic jellium media obey the hydrodynamic equation of motion (3.20). In cylindrical coordinates the solutions for ($l = 1$ and $m = 0$) electronic densities are:

$$n_{sp}(\mathbf{r}) = D \left(\frac{3}{4\pi} \right)^{1/2} \cos \theta m_1(k_2 r) \quad (3.57a)$$

Figure 3.8. The geometry of the sphere-plane coupling problem.

$$n_{pi}(\mathbf{r}) = (2\pi)^{-2} \int d^2k C(k) J_0(k\rho) \exp\{-\gamma(z - z_0)\}. \quad (3.57b)$$

In these expressions, $m_1(x) = (\pi/2x)^{-1/2} I_{3/2}(x)$ is the modified spherical Bessel function of the first kind and the first order, $J_0(x)$ is the Bessel function of the first kind and the zeroth order. $\gamma^2 = k^2 + k_1^2$, and k_i^{-1} is the Thomas-Fermi screening length in the i th metal, $k_i = \omega_{p(i)}/\beta_i$, where $\omega_{p(i)}$ is the plasma frequency and β_i is the dispersion parameter. The high and low frequency values of β_i^2 are $3/5v_{F(i)}^2$ and $1/3v_{F(i)}^2$ respectively, $v_{F(i)}$ being the Fermi velocity. The density fluctuations in both media are mutually orthogonal with respect to the number m . The predominant contribution to the charged particle-metallic sphere interaction potential is due to the dipole mode ($l = 1$) and is of order $\sim (R/\tau)^4$ outside the sphere. The higher, multipole modes contribute by terms of the smaller order $O((R/\tau)^6)$, where R is the radius and r the position of the charge measured from the centre of the sphere (see section 3.3). This justifies our choice of dipole mode on the sphere, $l = 1$, and $m = 0$ solution in the plane as the principal solutions for the density fluctuations (3.57a) and (3.57b) in the coupling problem.

The coupling occurs in the normalization constants $C(k)$ and D which are solved from the boundary conditions. To this end we require that the normal currents in metal 1 and the radial current in metal 2 vanish at the respective surfaces. This is written

$$\left\{ -m\beta_1^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial z} n_{pl} + en_{01} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \phi_{pl} + en_{01} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \phi_{sp} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \frac{Qen_{01}}{|\mathbf{r} - z_1|} \right\}_{z=z_0} \quad (3.58a)$$

$$\left\{ -m\beta_2^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} n_{sp} + en_{02} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \phi_{pl} + en_{02} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \phi_{sp} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \frac{Qen_{02}}{|\mathbf{r} - z_1|} \right\}_{z=R} \quad (3.58b)$$

where $n_{0(i)}$ is the equilibrium electron number density in i th metal. The boundary conditions lead to equations for the coefficients $C(k)$ and D ,

$$C(k) = A(k) + DB(k) \quad (3.59a)$$

$$D\Gamma = \int dk \Delta(k)C(k) + \int dk \Lambda(k) \quad (3.59b)$$

where

$$A(k) = \frac{Q}{e} \omega_{p1}^2 \frac{(\gamma + k) \exp(k(z_1 - z_0))}{[2\beta_1^2 \gamma(\gamma + k) - \omega_{p1}^2]} \quad (3.60a)$$

$$B(k) = -\left(\frac{4\pi}{3}\right)^{1/2} (\omega_{p1}^2 R^3 / k_2) m_2(k_2 R) \frac{k(\gamma + k) \exp(-kz_0)}{[2\beta_1^2 \gamma(\gamma + k) - \omega_{p1}^2]} \quad (3.60b)$$

$$\Gamma = -(1/3)m_2(k_2 R) - \frac{m_1(k_2 R)}{k_2 R} \quad (3.60c)$$

$$\Delta(k) = 1/2 \left(\frac{3}{4\pi}\right)^{1/2} k_2 \frac{k \exp(-kz_0)}{(\gamma + k)} W(k, R) \quad (3.60d)$$

$$\Lambda(k) = -(1/2) \left(\frac{3}{4\pi}\right)^{1/2} \frac{Q}{e} k_2 k \exp(-kz_0) W(k, R). \quad (3.60e)$$

Here

$$W(k, R) = \int_0^\pi d\theta \sin \theta \cos \theta \exp(kR \cos \theta) [\cos \theta J_0(kR \sin \theta) - \sin \theta J_1(kR \sin \theta)]. \quad (3.61)$$

Let us now choose the units of z_0 , z_1 and R to be k_1^{-1} , and let k be in units of k_1 . This is equivalent with the change of variables: $k \rightarrow k = k/k_1$, $k_1 \rightarrow 1$, $k_2 \rightarrow k_2/k_1$, $z_1 \rightarrow z_1 k_1$, $z_0 \rightarrow z_0 k_1$, $R \rightarrow Rk_1$, $\gamma \rightarrow \gamma = \sqrt{k^2 + 1}$.

Now, the coefficient D is found to be,

$$D = 1/2 \left(\frac{3}{4\pi} \right)^{1/2} \frac{Q}{e} k_1^2 k_2 (I_1 - I_2) / \{ \Gamma + 1/2 R^3 m_2(k_2 R) I_3 \} \quad (3.62)$$

where the dimensionless integrals I_1 , I_2 and I_3 are,

$$I_1 = \int_0^\infty dk k \frac{\exp\{-k(2z_0 - z_1)\}}{2\gamma(\gamma + k) - 1} W(k, R) \quad (3.63a)$$

$$I_2 = \int_0^\infty dk k \exp(-kz_1) W(k, R) \quad (3.63b)$$

$$I_3 = \int_0^\infty dk k^2 \frac{\exp(-2kz_0)}{2\gamma(\gamma + k) - 1} W(k, R). \quad (3.63c)$$

It is interesting to note that the expressions (3.62), (3.63a) and (3.63c) are analytically solved in the dispersionless case ($\beta \rightarrow 0, \gamma \rightarrow 1$).

The integral I_1 takes, then, the form of I_2 ,

$$I(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty dk k \exp(-k\alpha) W(k, R) = 2/3\alpha^{-2} \quad (3.64)$$

and

$$I_3(\beta = 0) = \frac{d}{d\alpha} I \Big|_{\alpha=2z_0}. \quad (3.65)$$

Hence in the *dispersionless case*

$$I_1 = 2/3(2z_0 - z_1)^{-2} \quad (3.66)$$

$$I_2 = 2/3z_1^{-2} \quad \text{in all cases} \quad (3.67)$$

$$I_3 = -4/3(2z_0)^{-3} \quad (3.68)$$

and, using (3.66)–(3.68) all subsequent expressions lead to the multiple-image type of result (divergent at surface of the plane). To recover full multiple-image interaction energy one has also to sum all the higher modes on the dispersionless sphere.

The induced potential in the sphere-plane system is,

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_I(\mathbf{r}) = \phi_{pl}(\mathbf{r}) + \phi_{sp}(\mathbf{r}) = & -\frac{e}{2\pi} \int \frac{d^2k}{k} \frac{C(k) J_0(k\rho) \exp(k(z - z_0))}{\gamma + k} \\ & - \left(\frac{4\pi}{3} \right)^{1/2} e \frac{m_2(k_2 R)}{k_2} D R^3 \frac{\cos \theta}{r^2} \end{aligned} \quad (3.69)$$

consequently, the self-energy of a charge Q is,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum(z_1) = \frac{Q}{2} \phi_I(z_1) = & -\frac{Q^2 k_1}{2} \int dk \frac{\exp\{2k(z_1 - z_0)\}}{[2\gamma(\gamma + k) - 1]} \\ & + \frac{Q^2 k_1}{2} \frac{m_2(k_2 R)}{2} \frac{R^3}{z_1^2} I_2 / \Gamma + C.T. . \end{aligned} \quad (3.70)$$

The first and second term in (3.70) are the classical interaction potential of a charged particle with the dispersive plane and the dispersive sphere with only dipole mode present, respectively. The coupling term is

$$\begin{aligned} C.T. = \frac{Q^2 k_1}{2} \frac{m_2(k_2 R)}{2} \frac{R^3}{z_1^2} & \left((I_1 - I_2) I_4 z_1^2 + \frac{m_2(k_2 R)}{2} R^3 I_2 I_3 + \Gamma I_1 \right) \\ & \times \left\{ \Gamma \left(\Gamma + R^3 \frac{m_2(k_2 R)}{2} I_3 \right) \right\}^{-1} \end{aligned} \quad (3.71)$$

and the integral I_4 is,

$$I_4 = \int_0^\infty dk k \frac{\exp\{-k(2z_0 - z_1)\}}{2\gamma(\gamma + k) - 1} . \quad (3.72)$$

The interaction potential $\sum(z_1)$ and its separate contributions are depicted in Fig.3.9. The most important result is that the correction term does not exceed 5% of the total potential. In obtaining these results we used expressions (3.63) in a general case of dispersive media. Fig.3.10 shows the potential of a charged particle in a plane-sphere geometry, along the axial line, when all the higher surface modes are included (in the example at hand there are 6 surface modes).

Inclusion of all modes on the sphere in our computation of the coupling term would result in a considerable computational complication, since then a bigger matrix equation, instead of equations (3.59) would have to be solved. However, since the coupling terms with higher modes of the sphere diminish rapidly with the plane-sphere distance of separation, we conclude that the coupling contributions for all higher modes will not be higher than $\sim 5\%$ of the principal, decoupled plane and multipole terms.

Figure 3.9. The potential barrier along the axial line in the coupled sphere (W)-plane (Ag) problem. The geometry is as depicted in Fig.3.8. The surface of the sphere is at $zk_1 = 10$ and the surface of the plane at $zk_1 = 20$. The distance z is in units of Thomas-Fermi screening length in the sample, $k_1^{-1} = a_0(r_s/2.44)^{1/2}$. The energy units are $Q^2 k_1 = 2a_0 k_1 [Ry]$. The solid line represents the total potential; broken line — the contribution from the plane; dash-dotted line — the contribution from the dipole mode on the sphere; dotted line — the coupling contribution ($< 5\%$ of total).

Figure 3.10. The potential of a charged particle, along the axial line in a sphere-plane geometry including all surface modes on the sphere (solid line) and only dipole mode (broken line). The units and geometry are as in Fig.3.9.

3.4.3 The plane-sphere potential barrier

The potential of a static charge Q , tunneling between a metal plane and a spherical tip is constructed as a superposition of decoupled contributions from the sphere and the plane. It is a matter of straightforward application of a method presented in section 3.2 to obtain the potential in a charge-plane system,

$$\Sigma_{pl}(z) = -\frac{Q^2 k_1}{2} \int_0^\infty dk \exp(-2kz)/(\gamma + k)^2 \quad (3.73)$$

where z is measured from the planar surface in units of k_1^{-1} and $\gamma = (k^2 + 1)^{1/2}$.

The calculation of the potential in a charge-sphere system is a problem that has been exhaustively treated in section 3.3. As observed therein, the contribution from the bulk modes can be ignored outside the sphere, and then the potential is written

$$\Sigma_{sp}(r) = -\frac{Q^2 k_1}{2R} \sum_{l=1}^{l=\max} \left(\frac{\omega_p^2}{\omega_l^2} \right) \frac{1}{(2l+1)\Delta_l^S} \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^{2(l+1)} ; \quad r > R \quad (3.74)$$

where ω_l are the eigenfrequencies of the surface modes which are found from the dispersion equation (3.38).

The results for the interaction potential computed from (3.39) were tabulated for the sizes of the sphere $R \in \{10, 20, 50, 100\}$ and for different metals represented by a parameter $k_2/k_1 \in \{1.0, 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4\}$, the value of k_1 was taken for Ag. The Tables are given in Appendix.

The principal results of this work are depicted in Figures 3.11 and 3.12. Figures 3.11a and 3.12a show the axially symmetric potential barrier in the tip-sample geometry, for two inter-electrode separations $10k_1^{-1}$ and $20k_1^{-1}$, respectively.

The three-dimensional relief of the barrier is presented in Figures 3.11b and 3.12b for the same separations. The barrier is much lower for the narrower tip-sample gap. This is an important effect which might show up in the onset of tunneling at the fixed applied bias; it has not received much attention so far.

It should be pointed out that the metal tip in our model is the charge neutral, insulated, conducting sphere. In order to include the effect of a fixed potential V at the surface of the sphere the classical term (Jackson, 1975), $\sum_V(r) = VRQ/2r$ should be added to expression (3.74).

3.4.4 Conclusions

In this section we have calculated the interaction potential of a stationary, point charge in the model scanning tunneling microscope geometry. The sample has been taken as a flat, free-electron jellium metal, and the probing tip has been modelled by a charge neutral, insulating, conducting sphere. It has been assumed that the conduction electrons obey the hydrodynamic equation of motion. In most experimental situations the probing tip is made of tungsten, although other metals, like iridium or molybdenum, have also been used. J.R. Smith (1969) pointed out that many surface properties of the transition metals had been successfully described within the free-electron model, and certainly his calculations of the work functions and surface potentials show good agreement with experiment. Assured by this agreement we have treated the sphere as being a jellium and free-electron-like, with the effective Wigner-Seitz radius for tungsten $r_S = 1.62$ (Mehrotra, 1979). The only parameters of the theory are therefore the electronic densities in the probe and the sample.

We have demonstrated that coupling of the surface modes in the two electrodes has negligible effect on the potential barrier for the typical separations encountered in experiments, of the order of 10 times Thomas-Fermi screening length. It contributes less than 5% to the total potential and hence can be ignored.

In principle, the shape of the tunneling potential barrier can be estimated in the same manner as has been done here if the independent potentials due to the plane and the sphere are obtained by other methods. There are many estimates in

Figure 3.11a. The induced potential contours of a charged particle in the model scanning tunneling microscope. The probe (W)-sample (Ag) separation is $10k_1$. The units are the same as in Fig.3.9.

Figure 3.11b. The potential barrier of Fig.3.11a as a three-dimensional relief.

Fig. 3.12a.

Fig. 3.12b.

Figures 3.12a and 3.12b. The same as in Figs.3.11a and 3.11b respectively. The separation here is $20k_1$. Notice the lowering of the barrier.

literature of the image potential due to a plane using other methods, such as the density functional method (Appelbaum and Hamann, 1972; Lang and Kohn, 1973) or the dielectric response method (Eguiluz *et al.*, 1984). Similar calculations for the image potential due to a sphere are not available, to the best of our knowledge.

The effective potential barrier in a plane-sphere geometry has an obvious rotational symmetry about the line normal to the surface and joining the centre of the sphere. It displays "a valley" centred along the axial line where strong enhancement of the tunnel current should be expected. The spherical model of the tip shows that STM is an excellent local probe of the electronic structure of the sample, since the tunnel current will decrease rapidly in lateral distances of about half the tip radius. This effect has been discussed by Morawitz *et al.*, (1986) and Das and Mahanty (1987).

CHAPTER 4. THE IMAGE POTENTIAL NEAR A METAL: A VARIATIONAL APPROACH LINKING THE DENSITY FUNCTIONAL METHOD WITH THE HYDRODYNAMIC MODEL

4.1 Introduction

In this chapter we investigate again the problem of the response of the electron gas to (a stationary, perturbing) external or internal charge Q .

As we stressed before this is an immensely complex and difficult problem. In the first two chapters we have presented some of the theoretical methods applied to treat this problem. Here we utilize another theoretical approach — the density functional theory (DFT) (Hohenberg and Kohn, 1964; Kohn and Sham, 1965). DFT is perhaps the best and certainly the most successful theoretical scheme to deal with the problem of equilibrium density distributions of inhomogeneous electron gas in solids (especially at the solid surfaces) and even in atoms and molecules.

The image potential has been studied by density functional methods before. Lang and Kohn (1970, 1973) performed fully self-consistent calculations of the induced charge density and the image potential. Their method, which utilizes the local form of the exchange and correlation energy, leads to the exponential z -dependence of the image potential outside the metal (Serena *et al.*, 1986). It is also heavily dependent on involved numerical computations and hence difficult to reproduce.

Smith (1969) and Appelbaum and Hamann (1972) used a somewhat simplified version of the density functional scheme, based on minimizing the energy with respect to a parameter occurring in the assumed form of the electron equilibrium density. The 'image' potential obtained by Smith (1969) in a non-self-consistent way shows the exponential behaviour outside the metal surface, instead of the

$[4(z - z_0)]^{-1}$ relation.

The formalism we present in this chapter can be considered as an intermediate approach between the fully self-consistent method of Lang and Kohn (1970, 1973) and the variational method of Smith (1969) and Appelbaum and Hamann (1972).

In our method the electron density is explicitly separated out into the equilibrium part and the first order response part induced in a metal. This separation allows us to study the importance of various contributions to the work function and the image potential for selected metals. Due to a particularly simple model of the ionic background (the jellium model) and the simple, yet physical form of the equilibrium, zeroth order electron density profile the calculations can be carried analytically to a large extent, giving a better physical picture.

The response of the electron gas or the first order density fluctuation is obtained, using the results of the hydrodynamic model, thus bridging the gap between the DFT and the hydrodynamic model in the spirit of Ying's (1974) work.

We begin with an introduction to the density functional theory. Since an extensive exposition of the DFT can be found in many review articles (for example Gupta and Rajagopal, 1982; Ghosh and Deb, 1982; Kohn and Vashishta, 1983; Williams and von Barth, 1983; Langreth, 1984; von Barth, 1984; Callaway and March, 1984) we will be very brief here.

Let us consider (after Hohenberg and Kohn, 1964) a system of N interacting electrons in its (nondegenerate) ground state Ψ . The electrons are embedded in a static external potential $v(\mathbf{r})$ due to compensating positive ion background. The Hamiltonian of this system is*

$$H = T + U + V \quad (4.1)$$

* In this chapter we use atomic units, with $|e| = m = \hbar = 1$. The unit of energy, in this system, is 27.2 eV.

where the operators T , U and V represent the electron kinetic energy, the electron-electron Coulomb interaction and the interaction of electrons with the external potential. The ground state energy is denoted by E_N and the density $n(\mathbf{r})$ satisfies the condition $N = \int n(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r}$. Hohenberg and Kohn (1964) treat the electron density $n(\mathbf{r})$ as the main quantity of their theory, in the spirit of the Thomas-Fermi method (see e.g. March, 1983). On the basis of the variational theorem which states that

$$E_N := \langle \Psi | H | \Psi \rangle \leq E'_N := \langle \Psi' | H | \Psi' \rangle$$

for all states Ψ' , the equality holding iff $\Psi' = \Psi$ is the true ground state of the (nondegenerate) electron system, Hohenberg and Kohn prove that $v(\mathbf{r})$ is a unique functional of $n(\mathbf{r})$ (apart from an additive constant). It follows immediately from this fact, that the ground state Ψ (determined from H via the Schrödinger equation) is also a unique functional of $n(\mathbf{r})$. It is then natural to construct the total-energy functional $E_v[n]$, uniquely determined by an external potential $v(\mathbf{r})$, in the form

$$E_v[n] = \int v(\mathbf{r})n(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} + \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{n(\mathbf{r})n(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' + G[n] \quad (4.2)$$

where $G[n]$ is the universal functional of n and it is defined by

$$G[n] = \langle \Psi | [T + U] | \Psi \rangle - \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{n(\mathbf{r})n(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' . \quad (4.3)$$

$E_v[n]$ represented by (4.2) will be equal to the ground state energy E_N , for the correct density $n(\mathbf{r})$ associated with the potential $v(\mathbf{r})$. Hence the energy functional has the stationary property

$$\delta E_v[n] = 0 \quad (4.4a)$$

subject to the condition that $n(\mathbf{r})$ is varied keeping the number of electrons fixed,

$$\int d\mathbf{r} n(\mathbf{r}) = N . \quad (4.4b)$$

It is convenient to introduce a Lagrange multiplier μ to combine (4.4a) with the constraint (4.4b),

$$\delta \left\{ E_v[n] - \mu \int d\mathbf{r} n(\mathbf{r}) \right\} = 0. \quad (4.5)$$

It is immediately seen, that for a density $n(\mathbf{r})$ satisfying (4.5) μ has a meaning of the chemical potential,

$$\mu = \frac{\delta E_v[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})}. \quad (4.6)$$

The formulae (4.1)–(4.6) are exact, but so far nothing can be said about the functional $G[n]$. In fact it is practically impossible to derive an exact many-body expression for $G[n]$. Hohenberg and Kohn have considered $G[n]$ for the electron gas of nearly constant density: $n(\mathbf{r}) = \tilde{n} + \tilde{n}(\mathbf{r})$ where $\tilde{n}(\mathbf{r})/\tilde{n} \ll 1$ and $\int \tilde{n}(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} = 0$, and for the electron gas of slowly varying density (on the scale of the local value of $k_F^{-1}(\mathbf{r})$): $|\partial_{x_i} n(\mathbf{r})| \times |n(\mathbf{r})|^{-1} \ll k_F(\mathbf{r})$, $|\partial_{x_i x_j}^2 n(\mathbf{r})| \times |\partial_{x_k} n(\mathbf{r})|^{-1} \ll k_F(\mathbf{r})$, etc., where $k_F(\mathbf{r}) = [3\pi^2 n(\mathbf{r})]^{1/3}$ is the 'local' Fermi momentum.

The details of the forms of $G[n]$ for various expansions can be found in e.g. Kohn and Vashishta (1983) or Lang (1973). In the present work we use the following form (see Smith, 1969),

$$\begin{aligned} G[n] = & \frac{3}{10} (3\pi^2)^{2/3} \int n^{5/3} d\mathbf{r} - \frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{3}{\pi} \right)^{1/3} \int n^{4/3} d\mathbf{r} \\ & - 0.056 \int \frac{n^{4/3}}{0.079 + n^{1/3}} d\mathbf{r} + \frac{1}{72} \int \frac{(\nabla n)^2}{n} d\mathbf{r}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.7)$$

The integrands in this expression represent the kinetic, exchange, and correlation energy densities (in Wigner approximation), and the last term is the first of the inhomogeneity terms of the gradient expansion. We wish to stress that our general method to be soon presented will be also applicable for other choices of $G[n]$, including the nonlocal forms of the exchange and correlation potential. We have used (4.7) to represent $G[n]$ in order to compare our results for unperturbed surface with those of Smith (1969).

Kohn and Sham (1965) derived the *Kohn-Sham self-consistent equations*:

$$\left\{-\frac{1}{2}\nabla^2 + v_{eff}(\mathbf{r})\right\}\psi_i(\mathbf{r}) = \epsilon_i\psi_i(\mathbf{r}) \quad (4.8)$$

where $v_{eff}(\mathbf{r})$ is the *local*, effective potential

$$v_{eff}(\mathbf{r}) = \phi(\mathbf{r}) + v_{xc}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (4.9)$$

with

$$\phi(\mathbf{r}) := v(\mathbf{r}) + \int \frac{n(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r}' \quad (4.10)$$

and

$$v_{xc}(\mathbf{r}) := \frac{\delta E_{xc}[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})}. \quad (4.11)$$

$E_{xc}[n]$ is the exchange and correlation energy. For self-consistency the set of equations (4.8)–(4.11) is closed with

$$n(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{i=1}^N |\psi_i(\mathbf{r})|^2 \quad (4.12)$$

where summation is carried out over the N lowest occupied eigenstates. The exchange and correlation energy is commonly regarded within the *local density approximation* (LDA), which states that for an electron gas of slowly varying density, $E_{xc}[n]$ can be written as

$$E_{xc}[n] = \int \epsilon_{xc}(n(\mathbf{r})) n(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \quad (4.13)$$

where $\epsilon_{xc}(n)$ is the exchange and correlation energy per particle of a uniform electron gas of density n . The total energy of electron system, on the basis of Kohn-Sham equations and in LDA, is

$$E_{tot} \approx \sum_i \epsilon_i - \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{n(\mathbf{r})n(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' + \int n(\mathbf{r})\{\epsilon_{xc}(n(\mathbf{r})) - \mu_{xc}(n(\mathbf{r}))\} d\mathbf{r} \quad (4.14)$$

where $\mu_{xc}(n(\mathbf{r})) := v_{xc}(\mathbf{r})$ (in LDA).

The generalisation of the DFT for finite temperatures was obtained by Mermin (1965). The formalism has also been extended to relativistic cases and for particles with spin (for a review see Callaway and March, 1984). In recent years a number of works questioning the appropriateness of the LDA have appeared (Harris and Jones, 1974; Gunnarson and Jones, 1980; Ossicini and Bertoni, 1985; Ossicini *et al.*, 1986; von Barth, 1984). It can be shown (Kohn and Vashishta, 1983 and references therein) that in general, the non-local exchange and correlation energy is given by

$$E_{xc}[n] = \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} n(\mathbf{r}) \bar{h}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') n(\mathbf{r}') \quad (4.15)$$

where $\bar{h}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is related to the electron pair correlation function $g_\lambda(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ by

$$\bar{h}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = \int_0^1 d\lambda [g_\lambda(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') - 1]. \quad (4.16)$$

The index λ (≤ 1) refers here to a reducing factor of the Coulomb repulsion ($\frac{1}{r} \sim \frac{\lambda}{r}$).

4.2 The density functional method for the electron gas with a perturbing charge

In this section we introduce a formalism, based on the density functional theory, which is particularly suitable for studying the static linear response of the *inhomogeneous* electron gas to some external perturbing charge.

Consider a system of N electrons in its ground state bound together by the fixed distribution of positive ions, $n_+(\mathbf{r})$, (n_+ is not specified here). Assume that this system is perturbed by a small additional charge Q , at position $\mathbf{r}_1$ (within or outside of the electron density distribution). According to DFT the total energy of this new system is given by

$$\begin{aligned} E_v[n] = & \int \bar{v}(\mathbf{r}) n(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} - Q \int \frac{\delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} n_+(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r}' d\mathbf{r} \\ & + \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{n(\mathbf{r}) n(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' + G[n] \end{aligned} \quad (4.17)$$

where $G[n]$, defined by eq.(4.3), is the unique functional of density n , and

$$\bar{v}(\mathbf{r}) = v(\mathbf{r}) + v_1(\mathbf{r}) = - \int \frac{n_+(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r}' + Q \int \frac{\delta(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r}_1)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r}'. \quad (4.18)$$

The first term in (4.17) represents the interaction of electron gas with the positive ions background *and* an extra charge Q . The second term in (4.17) is the interaction of an external charge with positive ions, and the third term is the Coulomb self-interaction energy of electron gas. Since we assumed that an external charge produces only 'small' perturbation, the energy functional (4.17) is expanded in functional Taylor series about the equilibrium, unperturbed density n_0 , and the terms up to the second order are retained. This leads to an expression,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{\bar{v}}[n_0 + n_1] \cong E_{\bar{v}}[n_0] + \int \left. \frac{\delta E_{\bar{v}}[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})} \right|_{n=n_0} n_1(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \\ + \frac{1}{2} \iint \left. \frac{\delta^2 E_{\bar{v}}[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r}) \delta n(\mathbf{r}')} \right|_{n=n_0} n_1(\mathbf{r}) n_1(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \end{aligned} \quad (4.19)$$

where $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ is the disturbance in an electron gas induced by the presence of an external charge Q . $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ satisfies the condition of overall charge neutrality of the system

$$\int d\mathbf{r} n_1(\mathbf{r}) = -Q. \quad (4.20)$$

Each of the three terms on the righthand side of (4.19) is rewritten. This is done as follows (for the zeroth order term),

$$E_{\bar{v}}[n_0] = E_v[n_0] + Q \int \frac{n_0(\mathbf{r}) - n_+(\mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}|} d\mathbf{r}. \quad (4.21)$$

$E_v[n_0]$ is just the energy of the original system in the *absence* of any additional charges, the second term in (4.21) is, in the surface problem, the double-layer contribution. It should be noted, that (4.21) does not depend on the form of the response n_1 .

The term linear in n_1 in the Taylor expansion (4.19) is

$$\begin{aligned} \int \frac{\delta E_v[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})} \Big|_{n=n_0} n_1(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} &= Q \iint \frac{\delta(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r}_1)}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} n_1(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \\ &\quad + \int \frac{\delta E_v[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})} \Big|_{n=n_0} n_1(\mathbf{r}) d\mathbf{r} \\ &= Q \int \frac{n_1(\mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}|} d\mathbf{r} - Q\mu. \end{aligned} \quad (4.22)$$

We used definition of chemical potential (4.6) and the condition of neutrality (4.20) in arriving at (4.22). Finally the third term in (4.19) is simply

$$\frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{\delta^2 E_v[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r}) \delta n(\mathbf{r}')} \Big|_{n=n_0} n_1(\mathbf{r}) n_1(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \quad (4.23)$$

since

$$\frac{\delta^2 E_v[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r}) \delta n(\mathbf{r}')} \Big|_{n=n_0} = \frac{\delta^2 E_v[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r}) \delta n(\mathbf{r}')} \Big|_{n=n_0}. \quad (4.24)$$

The energy functional (4.19) can be expressed in the form

$$E_v[n_0 + n_1] \cong E_v[n_0] \quad (4.25a)$$

$$+ Q \int \frac{n_0(\mathbf{r}) - n_+(\mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}|} d\mathbf{r} - Q\mu \quad (4.25b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &+ Q \int \frac{n_1(\mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}|} d\mathbf{r} + \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{n_1(\mathbf{r}) n_1(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{\delta^2 G[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r}) \delta n(\mathbf{r}')} \Big|_{n=n_0} n_1(\mathbf{r}) n_1(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}'. \end{aligned} \quad (4.25c)$$

This equation forms the basis of our subsequent study of a response of an electron gas in metal to a perturbing charge. It should be emphasised that (4.25) is independent of the particular form of the functional $G[n]$. For example if the exchange and correlation energy is given by the non-local representation (4.15) then the second order contribution (4.25c) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_2[n_0 + n_1] &= Q \int \frac{n_1(\mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}|} d\mathbf{r} + \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{n_1(\mathbf{r}) n_1(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{6} (3\pi^2)^{2/3} \int d\mathbf{r} \frac{n_1^2(\mathbf{r})}{n_0^{1/3}} \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \iint \frac{\bar{h}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} n_1(\mathbf{r}) n_1(\mathbf{r}') d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \end{aligned} \quad (4.26)$$

where the third term on the righthand side of (4.26) is the kinetic energy contribution and $\bar{h}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ is given by (4.16).

A useful analytical form for $\bar{h}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}')$ due to Gunnarson and Jones (1980) is,

$$\bar{h}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}') = C \left[1 - \exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{\lambda}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} \right)^5 \right\} \right], \quad (4.27)$$

where parameters C and λ are to be adjusted for every value of the density $n(\mathbf{r})$, so the sum rule analogous to our eq.(4.20) is satisfied. We will now minimize the energy functional (4.25) in a manner similar to that of Smith (1969) or Appelbaum and Hamann (1972) in that we use the assumed form of the equilibrium part of density, n_0 . There is however a crucial difference in our approach because we explicitly separate the induced density n_1 in (4.25). (There was *no* response part of the density in Smith's (1969) work.) In order to make connection with the results of previous workers (Smith, 1969; Appelbaum and Hamann, 1972) we use the form of $G[n]$ given by (4.7).

4.3 The equilibrium density profile and surface energy

The energy functional given by expression (4.25) can be minimized independently in two stages, provided the total electronic density separates into two terms: $n(\mathbf{r}) = n_0(\mathbf{r}) + n_1(\mathbf{r})$ and neither of these terms has common variational parameter. In this section we minimize the zeroth order part (4.25a) with respect to the assumed form of density n_0 . We follow here a method presented by Smith (1969). The essential difference between this work and the calculations of Smith is in our choice of the model equilibrium density profile. The electronic density $n_0(\mathbf{r}) := n_0(z; L)$ adopted in this work has a particularly simple analytical form

$$n_0(z; L) = \begin{cases} n_+ & z < -L \\ \frac{1}{2}n_+ \{1 - \sin(\frac{\pi}{2L}z)\} & |z| \leq L \\ 0 & z > L \end{cases} \quad (4.28)$$

whereas Smith chose an exponential profile

$$n_0^{(S)}(z; \beta) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}n_+ \{2 - \exp(\beta z)\} & z < 0 \\ \frac{1}{2}n_+ e^{-\beta z} & z > 0. \end{cases} \quad (4.29)$$

$n_+(z) = n_+\theta(z)$ is the positive background density profile which represents the jellium metal (Frenkel, 1928; Bardeen, 1936).

The most important feature of our profile (4.28) is a complete saturation of n_0 to the value of positive background n_+ beyond some depth $-L$ from the jellium edge and vanishing of $n_0(z)$ for $z > L$. The exponential (4.29) and sinusoidal (4.28) equilibrium density profiles are presented in Fig.4.1 for Au jellium ($r_s = 3.01$).

The direct experimental verification of the density profile n_0 is not available and there is no *a priori* better or worse choice of n_0 , provided certain boundary conditions are satisfied (Smith, 1969; Lang, 1969). Hence only the values of quantities of experimental significance (e.g. surface energy, work function) derived on the basis of n_0 can provide a test of correctness of any model family of functions. It is to be noted that the equilibrium density profile obtained self-consistently by Lang and Kohn (1970) exhibits exponential decay to zero value as $z \rightarrow \infty$. This fact does not preclude a possibility that a *real* density profile saturates to zero value at *finite* distance from the jellium edge. It is interesting to observe that the input trial density $n_0(z)$ in Lang and Kohn's (1970) self-consistent procedure was assumed to be "an exponential decaying toward n_+ in a Thomas-Fermi length inside the metal, matched to a linear combination of two exponentials with adjustable decay length outside." One should expect then that even a well converging self-consistent procedure will generate a result that will be similar to a type of trial input. For example the first Friedel oscillation, known to occur in an electron gas, was superimposed on trial input density 'by hand', and this feature was obviously preserved upon successful completion of self-consistent computation (Lang and Kohn, 1970). Our expression (4.28) represents clearly an idealized density profile. We believe however that it is a very suitable choice for approximate evaluation of a number of properties depending on n_0 . Furthermore the variational parameter L has a direct physical meaning of half-width of the surface inhomogeneity. We

Fig.4.1. The number densities of a jellium background (step function, dotted line), the equilibrium electronic densities in our model (4.28) (solid line) and in Smith's (1969) work (4.29) (dashed curve). The values are for Au, $r_s = 3.01$ and the variational parameter, the half-width of the surface inhomogeneity is $L = 2.5$ a.u.

have neglected the Friedel oscillations in $n_0(z)$, as has been done in Smith (1969) and Appelbaum and Hamann (1972). The simple density profile (4.28) leads to slightly better agreement ($\sim 3\%$) with the experimental data on the surface energy than is obtained from Smith's model (Table 4.1).

Table 4.1. Surface energies for K, Li and Na — comparison of our results (e.g. (4.36)) with results given by Smith (1969) (S).

Metal	Surface energy [J/m^2]		
	(4.36)	(S)	Experiment*
K	0.0727	0.0688	0.146
Na	0.118	0.111	0.240
Li	0.146	0.132	0.510

* as given by Smith (1969) (from Juretschke (1960))

The zeroth order energy functional $E_v[n_0]$ (4.25a) is now minimized with respect to a family of functions (4.28). Since for any value of L , $n_0(z)$ given by (4.28) satisfies the charge neutrality condition

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz \{n_0(z) - n_+(z)\} = 0 \quad (4.30)$$

then the stationary property of $E_v[n_0]$ is given simply by

$$\frac{dE_v[n_0]}{dL} = 0. \quad (4.31)$$

It is considerably more practical to express the stationary property (4.31) of the energy functional $E_v[n_0]$ in terms of the minimum of surface energy, σ :

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dL} = 0 \quad (4.32)$$

where the surface energy σ of a crystal is the energy required, per unit area of new surface formed, to split the crystal in two along a plane (Lang and Kohn, 1970). σ is given by (Smith, 1969)

$$\sigma = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz \{ \epsilon_v[n_0] - \epsilon_v[n_+(z)] \} \quad (4.33)$$

where $\epsilon_v[n]$ is the energy density. The Coulomb potential due to a charge distribution $n_0(z)$ at the jellium surface is

$$\varphi(\mathbf{r}') = \int d\mathbf{r} \frac{n_0(\mathbf{r}) - n_+(\mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} \quad (4.34)$$

or using (4.28)

$$\varphi(z) = \begin{cases} 2\alpha\varphi_0 & z < -L \\ -\varphi_0 \{ 4\pi^{-2} \sin(\frac{\pi z}{2L}) + zL^{-1} [\frac{1}{2} \text{sgn}(z) zL^{-1} - 1] - \alpha \} & |z| \leq L \\ 0 & z > L \end{cases} \quad (4.35)$$

where $\varphi_0 = 2\pi n_+ L^2$ and α is the numerical factor, $\alpha = 4\pi^{-2} - \frac{1}{2}$.

The surface energy σ corresponding to the energy functional (4.2) with the functional $G[n]$ given by (4.7) and for the density $n_0(z)$ represented by (4.28) is obtained *analytically* as a sum

$$\sigma = \sigma_{pot} + \sigma_{kin} + \sigma_x + \sigma_{corr} + \sigma_{grad} \quad (4.36a)$$

where the terms on the righthand side of (4.36) are:

i) σ_{pot} is the Coulomb double-layer potential energy contribution

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{pot} &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-L}^L dz \varphi(z) \{ n_0(z) - n_+(z) \} \\ &= \pi n_+^2 \left\{ \frac{2}{\pi^2} \left(1 - \frac{8}{\pi} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \right\} L^3 := \omega_1 L^3 \end{aligned} \quad (4.36b)$$

ii) σ_{kin} is the kinetic energy contribution

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{kin} &= \frac{3}{10} (3\pi^2)^{2/3} \int_{-L}^L dz \{ n_0^{5/3}(z) - n_+^{5/3}(z) \} \\ &= \frac{3}{10} (3\pi^2)^{2/3} n_+^{5/3} \left\{ \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\Gamma(13/6)}{\Gamma(8/3)} - 1 \right\} L := \omega_2 L \end{aligned} \quad (4.36c)$$

iii) σ_x is the exchange contribution

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x &= -\frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{3}{\pi}\right)^{1/3} \int_{-L}^L dz \{n_0^{4/3}(z) - n_+^{4/3}(z)\} \\ &= -\frac{3}{4} \left(\frac{3}{\pi}\right)^{1/3} n_+^{4/3} \left\{ \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \frac{\Gamma(11/6)}{\Gamma(7/3)} - 1 \right\} L := \omega_3 L\end{aligned}\quad (4.63d)$$

iv) σ_{corr} is the correlation energy contribution

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{corr} &= 0.056 \left\{ \frac{n_+^{4/3}}{0.079 + n_+^{1/3}} - \frac{4}{\pi} n_+ \int_0^{\pi/2} dz \frac{\cos^{8/3} z}{0.079 n_+^{-1/3} + \cos^{2/3} z} \right\} L \\ &:= \omega_4 L\end{aligned}\quad (4.36e)$$

v) σ_{grad} is the term due to the first order gradient correction in (4.7)

$$\sigma_{grad} = \frac{1}{72} \frac{\pi^2}{4} \frac{n_+}{L} := \omega_5 L^{-1} . \quad (4.36f)$$

The stationary property of surface energy (4.32) is now expressed as a problem of finding a root of a polynomial in L

$$\frac{d\sigma}{dL} = 3\omega_1 L^2 + \omega_2 + \omega_3 + \omega_4 - \omega_5 L^{-2} = 0 . \quad (4.37)$$

Equation (4.37) was solved numerically and the values of L_{min} , the half-width of surface inhomogeneity, are presented in Table 4.2 for a number of metals.

The electrostatic double layer $\Delta\varphi$ is defined by

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta\varphi &= 4\pi \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dz z \{n_0(z) - n_+(z)\} \\ &= \varphi(\infty) - \varphi(-\infty) .\end{aligned}\quad (4.38)$$

From (4.28) and (4.38) we immediately find

$$\Delta\varphi = -4\pi n_+ \alpha L^2 \quad (4.39)$$

where α is defined following eq.(4.35). This result can be compared with the double layer due to an exponential profile (Smith, 1969)

$$\Delta\varphi_S = 4\pi n_+ \beta^{-2} \quad (4.40)$$

Table 4.2 Electrostatic double layer $\Delta\varphi$ for selected metals computed from our density profile (4.28) and from Smith's (1969) density profile (4.29) (S).

Metal	n_+ [10^{-3} a.u.]	β^{-1} (S) [a.u.]	L_{min} [a.u.]	$\Delta\varphi$ [eV]	
				(4.28)	(S)
Cs	1.33	0.752	2.478	0.264	0.258
Rb	1.67	0.758	2.478	0.331	0.327
K	1.95	0.758	2.478	0.388	0.386
Na	3.77	0.787	2.498	0.762	0.794
Li	6.92	0.806	2.510	1.41	1.55
Ag	8.73	0.813	2.507	1.78	1.99
Au	8.80	0.813	2.507	1.79	2.01
Cu	12.6	0.813	2.489	2.53	2.91
Ca	6.90	0.806	2.510	1.40	1.55
Mg	12.8	0.820	2.488	2.56	2.95
Cd	13.8	0.820	2.482	2.75	3.18
Zn	19.5	0.820	2.446	3.78	4.45
Be	35.8	0.794	2.352	6.41	7.76
La	12.0	0.820	2.492	2.41	2.77
Tl	15.4	6.820	2.472	3.05	3.55
In	17.0	0.820	2.462	3.34	3.90
Ga	22.3	0.813	2.428	4.26	5.06
Al	26.9	0.806	2.400	5.02	6.00
Sn	17.4	0.820	2.460	3.41	3.98
Pb	19.4	0.820	2.446	3.76	4.43
Ta	41.3	0.787	2.326	7.23	8.78
Nb	41.6	0.787	2.324	7.28	8.84
W	56.2	0.769	2.264	9.32	11.4
Mo	57.4	0.769	2.259	9.48	11.6
Re	70.4	0.758	2.215	11.2	13.8
Ir	84.2	0.746	2.175	12.9	15.9

Table 4.3 Electrostatic double layer $\Delta\varphi$ for jellium metals ($r_s = 2, 3, 5$) calculated from density profile (4.28) and compared with results of Appelbaum and Hamann (1972) (AH) and Lang and Kohn (1970) (LK). L_{min} is the minimum half-width of surface inhomogeneity obtained from (4.37).

r_s	L_{min} [a.u.]	β^{-1} [a.u.] (AH)	$\Delta\varphi$ [eV]		
			(4.28)	AH	LK
2	2.384	1.183	5.49	5.97	6.8
3	2.507	1.183	1.80	1.77	2.32
5	2.478	1.153	0.38	0.36	0.35

The numerical values of the electrostatic double layer expressed by (4.39) and (4.40) are given in Table 4.2 for various metals. Table 4.3 gives the values of double layer associated with $r_s = 2, 3$ and 5 as obtained from (4.39) and it is compared with results of Appelbaum and Hamann (1972) and Lang and Kohn (1970). Overall agreement of results for $\Delta\varphi$ for various model profiles is good ranging from 5% (for low densities) up to 8% (for high density) difference between our results and those of Appelbaum and Hamann (1972) and from 2% to 18% (low to high densities) between the results of Smith (1969) and ours. The more pronounced disagreement (18%) in the high density range has an important implication on the difference in the values of theoretical work function calculated by Smith and in this work. We will return to this problem later in this chapter. Summarizing, we express the opinion that despite its striking simplicity the equilibrium density profile (4.28) agrees rather well with other models of this type and hence can be treated as a good first approximation for calculating the properties of reference jellium surface.

In Table 4.4 we present the results for surface energy computed from our expression (4.36) and compare them with the results obtained from Smith's (1969) model and the self-consistent computations for jellium by Lang and Kohn (1970). **Table 4.4** Surface energy of jellium metal obtained from (4.36) and compared with results of Smith (1969) (S) and Lang and Kohn (1970) (LK).

r_s	σ [J/m ²]		
	(S)	(4.36)	(LK)
2.0	-1.1502	-1.0187	-1.010
2.5	-0.0725	-0.0293	0.040
3.0	0.1169	0.1360	0.200
3.5	0.1305	0.1412	0.190
4.0	0.1099	0.1170	0.160
4.5	0.0869	0.0919	0.120
5.0	0.0677	0.0714	0.100
5.5	0.0528	0.0558	0.075
6.0	0.0416	0.0439	0.060

The important conclusion (Lang and Kohn, 1970) is that the jellium model fails to account for observed surface energies for $r_s < 3.5$. In fact all studies (Lang and Kohn, 1970; Smith, 1969; also the present work) show that the surface energy of jellium metal becomes negative for $r_s < 2.5$. The only way to overcome this failure (inherent in jellium description) is to include the effects of discrete ionic positions. This was done by Lang and Kohn (1970), who used Ashcroft's (1966) local pseudo-potential to account for the effect of discrete ions.

4.4 A charge near a surface: the induced density fluctuation

4.4.1 The second order energy shift

In the previous section we minimized the first term $E_v[n_0]$ of expansion

(4.25a). The second and third terms (4.25b) do not depend on the induced charge density. In fact the second term in (4.25) is just equal to $Q\varphi(\mathbf{r}_1)$, where $\varphi(\mathbf{r})$ is given by (4.35). In this subsection we will present an analytical expression for the last term in (4.25), specific for the functional $G[n]$ in a form given by (4.7) but with the correlation term dropped out (see Ying, Smith and Kohn, 1975 for justification), and for our equilibrium density $n_0(z)$ (4.28). The second order functional derivative of $G[n]$ (4.7) is (Ying, Smith and Kohn, 1975)

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\delta^2 G[n]}{\delta n(\mathbf{r})\delta n(\mathbf{r}')} \right|_{n=n_0} &= \frac{1}{3} \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') \left[(3\pi^2)^{2/3} n_0^{-1/3}(\mathbf{r}') - \left(\frac{3}{\pi} \right)^{1/3} n_0^{-2/3}(\mathbf{r}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{|\nabla' n_0(\mathbf{r}')|^2}{12n_0^3(\mathbf{r})} + \frac{\nabla'^2 n_0(\mathbf{r}')}{12n_0^2(\mathbf{r})} \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{36} \nabla' \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}') \cdot \frac{\nabla' n_0(\mathbf{r}')}{n_0^2(\mathbf{r}')} - \frac{1}{36} \frac{\nabla'^2 \delta(\mathbf{r}' - \mathbf{r})}{n_0(\mathbf{r}')} \end{aligned} \quad (4.41)$$

where the correlation term was neglected. Substituting (4.41) into the last term of (4.25c) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_2 &:= \frac{1}{6} \left\{ \int d\mathbf{r} \left[(3\pi^2)^{2/3} n_0^{-1/3}(\mathbf{r}) - \left(\frac{3}{\pi} \right)^{1/3} n_0^{-2/3}(\mathbf{r}) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. - \frac{1}{12} \left(\frac{|\nabla n_0|^2}{n_0^3} - \frac{\nabla^2 n_0}{n_0^2} \right) \right] \cdot n_1^2(\mathbf{r}) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{36} \int d\mathbf{r} \left\{ (-\nabla) \cdot \left[\frac{\nabla n_0}{n_0^2} n_1^2(\mathbf{r}) \right] - \nabla^2 \left[\frac{n_1^2(\mathbf{r})}{n_0} \right] \right\} \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.42)$$

The last integral in (4.42) can be reduced, by divergence theorem, to give

$$\begin{aligned} & - \int d\mathbf{r} \nabla \cdot \left\{ \frac{\nabla n_0}{n_0^2} n_1^2(\mathbf{r}) + \nabla \left(\frac{n_1^2}{n_0} \right) \right\} \\ &= -2 \int_{z=L} dS \cdot \frac{n_1(\mathbf{r}) \frac{\partial}{\partial z} n_1(\mathbf{r})}{n_0} \Big|_{z=L}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.43)$$

It can be easily shown that this integral vanishes for our equilibrium density $n_0(z)$ and $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ satisfying

$$n_1(\mathbf{r}) \Big|_{z=L} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} n_1(\mathbf{r}) \Big|_{z=L} = 0. \quad (4.44)$$

In the next subsection we will demonstrate that $n_1(z)$ used in the present work indeed satisfies (4.44). We can simplify (4.42) further noting that for n_0 given by (4.28) (for $|z| \leq L$),

$$\frac{|\nabla n_0|^2}{n_0^3} - \frac{\nabla^2 n_0}{n_0^2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\pi}{2L} \right)^2 \frac{n_+}{n_0^2}. \quad (4.45)$$

The term due to $G[n]$ in the energy expansion (4.25) is finally written as

$$\Delta G_2 = \frac{1}{6} \left\{ \int d\mathbf{r} \left[(3\pi^2)^{2/3} n_0^{-1/3}(\mathbf{r}) - \left(\frac{3}{\pi} \right)^{1/3} n_0^{-2/3}(\mathbf{r}) - \frac{1}{24} \left(\frac{\pi}{2L} \right)^2 \frac{n_+}{n_0^2} \right] n_1^2(\mathbf{r}) \right\}. \quad (4.46)$$

This is as far as we can progress without introducing the induced density fluctuation $n_1(\mathbf{r})$. In the present work our choice of the form of $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ is guided by knowledge of the hydrodynamic model. $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ is obtained separately for a charge inside and outside a metal. The second order energy shift (4.25c) is interpreted as the self-energy of an external charge Q . Outside a metal it will give the 'image' potential.

4.4.2 Charge Q inside the metal

Consider a charge Q at z_1 inside the semi-infinite metal jellium, where $z_1 < -L$. The first order density disturbance $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ induced by the charge Q is found from the inhomogeneous hydrodynamic equation (see section 3.1),

$$[\beta^2 \nabla^2 - (\omega_p^2 - \omega^2)] n_1(\mathbf{r}) = -\omega_p^2 \left(\frac{Q}{e} \right) \delta(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_1). \quad (4.47)$$

The solution is

$$n_1(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{k_0^2}{2} \left(\frac{Q}{e} \right) \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \int \frac{d^2 \kappa}{\gamma} e^{i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot (\boldsymbol{\rho} - \boldsymbol{\rho}_1) - \gamma|z - z_1|} \quad (4.48a)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{(2\pi)^2} \int d^2 \kappa C(\kappa) e^{i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \boldsymbol{\rho} - \gamma|z|} \quad (4.48b)$$

where $\gamma^2 = k_0^2 + \kappa^2$ and $k_0 = \omega_p/\beta$ is the Thomas-Fermi screening length (see section 3.2). The first term (4.48a) is the particular solution and the second

(4.48b) is the general solution of this homogeneous equation. The coefficient $C(k)$ is obtained from the boundary condition of vanishing normal current. This gives in the static limit ($\omega = 0$) and for a charge on the z -axis ($\rho_1 = 0$)

$$C(\kappa) = \left(\frac{Q}{e}\right) \frac{(\gamma - \kappa)^2}{2\gamma} e^{-\gamma|z_1|}.$$

Equation (4.48) is rewritten

$$n_1(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{k_0^2 Q}{4\pi e} \left\{ \int d\kappa \kappa J_0(\kappa\rho) \gamma^{-1} e^{-\gamma|z-z_1|} + k_0^{-2} \int d\kappa \kappa J_0(\kappa\rho) \gamma^{-1} (\gamma - \kappa)^2 e^{-\gamma(|z|+|z_1|)} \right\}. \quad (4.49)$$

The first integral in (4.49) is solved exactly and this gives

$$\int d\kappa \kappa J_0(\kappa\rho) \gamma^{-1} e^{-\gamma|z-z_1|} = \frac{\exp(-k_0 R_-)}{R_-} \quad (4.50)$$

where $R_- := (\rho^2 + |z - z_1|^2)^{1/2}$. The second integral in (4.49) is solved approximately (Erdélyi *et al.*, 1954),

$$\frac{1}{k_0^2} \int d\kappa \kappa J_0(\kappa\rho) \frac{(\gamma - \kappa)^2}{\gamma} e^{-\gamma(|z|+|z_1|)} \approx \frac{1}{k_0} \frac{|z| + |z_1|}{R_+^3} [1 + k_0 R_+] \exp(-k_0 R_+) \quad (4.51)$$

where $R_+ := (\rho^2 + (|z| + |z_1|)^2)^{1/2}$. The main assumption is advanced at this point that the induced density $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ is well represented by the expression (4.49) which is reduced with the help of (4.50) and (4.51). Furthermore the induced density $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ is to be treated variationally and we introduce a variational parameter α representing a screening length in metal. No longer is the screening length given by the Thomas-Fermi k_0 ; instead k_0 is substituted by α ($k_0 \rightarrow \alpha$) and α is found from minimization of the second order energy shift (4.25c). Thus, the induced charge density $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ due to a charge Q at z_1 ($z_1 < -L$) is taken in the form (in atomic units)

$$n_1(\mathbf{r}) = \begin{cases} AQ \frac{\alpha^2}{4\pi} \left\{ \frac{\exp(-\alpha R_-)}{R_-} + \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{|z|+|z_1|}{R_+^3} [1 + \alpha R_+] \exp(-\alpha R_+) \right\} & z < -L \quad (4.52a) \\ AQ \frac{\alpha^2}{4\pi} \{f_1(\rho, z) + f_2(\rho, z)\} & |z| \leq L \quad (4.52b) \\ 0 & z > L \quad (4.52c) \end{cases}$$

where $\mathbf{r} = (\boldsymbol{\rho}, z)$, A is the normalization constant evaluated numerically through the condition of charge neutrality (4.20). The first line of this formula (4.52a) describes the density fluctuation in the region of uniform density $n_0(\mathbf{r})$, for $z < -L$. In the inhomogeneous surface layer, $|z| \leq L$, we expect a different response of an electron gas. In this region we assume that $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ can be expressed as a sum of two polynomials of third degree in z . This is written,

$$f_1(\boldsymbol{\rho}, z) = a_0(\rho) + a_1(\rho)z + a_2(\rho)z^2 + a_3(\rho)z^3 \quad (4.53a)$$

$$f_2(\boldsymbol{\rho}, z) = b_0(\rho) + b_1(\rho)z + b_2(\rho)z^2 + b_3(\rho)z^3 \quad (4.53b)$$

where $f_i(\rho, z)$, $i = 1, 2$ and their first derivatives are subject to continuity conditions (for all ρ)

$$\begin{aligned} & \left. \{n_1^{(i)}(\mathbf{r}) = f_i(\boldsymbol{\rho}, z)\} \right|_{z=-L} \\ & \left. \left\{ \frac{\partial}{\partial z} n_1^{(i)}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} f_i(\boldsymbol{\rho}, z) \right\} \right|_{z=-L} \\ & \left. \left\{ f_i(\boldsymbol{\rho}, z) = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} f_i(\boldsymbol{\rho}, z) = 0 \right\} \right|_{z=L} \end{aligned} \quad (4.54)$$

where $n_1^{(i)}(\mathbf{r})$ stands for the first ($i = 1$) and the second ($i = 2$) term in curly brackets in (4.52a). The system of equations (4.54) is easily solved and leads to the following expressions for coefficients $a_l(\rho)$, $b_l(\rho)$, $l = 0, 1, 2, 2$

$$\begin{aligned} a_0 &= G(2 + LH) \\ a_1 &= -G\left(H + \frac{3}{L}\right) \\ a_2 &= -G\frac{H}{L} \\ a_3 &= G\frac{1 + LH}{L^3} \end{aligned} \quad (4.55)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} G &= \frac{1}{4} \frac{\exp\{-\alpha(\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{1/2}\}}{(\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{1/2}}, \\ H &= \frac{L + z_1}{(\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{1/2}} [\alpha + (\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{-1/2}], \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 b_0 &= P(2R + LS) \\
 b_1 &= -P\left(S + \frac{3R}{L}\right) \\
 b_2 &= -P\frac{S}{L} \\
 b_3 &= P\frac{R + LS}{L^3}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4.56}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 P &= -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\exp\{-\alpha(\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{1/2}\}}{\alpha(\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{3/2}} \\
 R &= (L + z_1)(1 + \alpha(\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{1/2}) \\
 S &= 1 + \alpha(\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{1/2} - \alpha^2(L + z_1)^2 \\
 &\quad + \frac{3(L + z_1)^2}{(\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{1/2}} [\alpha + (\rho^2 + (L + z_1)^2)^{-1/2}] .
 \end{aligned}$$

The second order energy shift ΔE_2 (4.25c) is now evaluated numerically using the induced density fluctuation in the form (4.52). ΔG_2 is represented by (4.46). ΔE_2 was minimized with respect to the screening parameter α . The multiple integrals (dimension $D \leq 4$) were evaluated by NAG* Quadrature and NAG** minimization procedure was used. The results for the screening parameter α^{-1} are depicted in Fig.4.2 for a charge $Q = 1$ embedded in Au jellium. It is seen from the graph that the screening becomes slightly less effective in the vicinity of the surface electronic inhomogeneity, for $z_1 > -2.6\text{\AA}$. This implies that approximately up to the second last atomic layer the screening is as effective as in the bulk material. The value of α^{-1} (of the order of ~ 0.78 a.u.) in bulk is about 30% lower than the Thomas-Fermi screening length ($k_0^{-1} = 1.1$ a.u. for Au). The difference is

* ©Numerical Algorithm Group (1984): D01FCF; NAGFLIB: 1748/0:Mk8: Jan. 1981.

** ©Numerical Algorithm Group (1984): E04ABF; NAGFLIB: 1480/0:Mk6: May 1977.

to be expected since our $G[n]$ contained two extra terms (the exchange and first order gradient correction — the second and fourth terms in (4.7)) compared with the usual Thomas-Fermi form (3.19). The self-energy of the static charge Q inside and outside the jellium Au surface is depicted in Fig.4.3. It will be discussed in the next section.

4.4.3 Charge Q outside the jellium surface

The charge density fluctuation $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ induced in a jellium metal by an external charge Q placed at z_1 , $z_1 \geq L$, is postulated here to be of the form (in atomic units)

$$n_1(\mathbf{r}) = A_{ex} \frac{Q}{(2\pi)^2} \int d^2\kappa (\gamma - \kappa) e^{-\kappa z_1} e^{i\kappa \cdot \rho} \begin{cases} e^{\gamma z} \\ f_3(z; \kappa) \end{cases}, \quad \begin{matrix} z < -L \\ |z| \leq L \end{matrix} \quad (4.57)$$

where the form of $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ for $z < -L$ is obtained from an exact solution of the homogeneous hydrodynamic equation (3.20) subject to the boundary conditions of vanishing normal current at $z = -L$. $f_3(z)$ is taken, as in the previous section, to be the polynomial of the third degree in z ,

$$f_3(z; \kappa) = d_0(\kappa) + d_1(\kappa)z + d_2(\kappa)z^2 + d_3(\kappa)z^3. \quad (4.58)$$

The coefficients are immediately obtained from the continuity conditions of $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ at $z = -L$ and decaying form of $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ at $z_1 = L$, analogous to (4.54). They are given through the relations

$$\begin{aligned} d_0(\kappa) &= \delta(2 + \gamma L) \\ d_1(\kappa) &= -\delta\left(\gamma + \frac{3}{L}\right) \\ d_2(\kappa) &= -\delta\frac{\gamma}{L} \\ d_3(\kappa) &= \delta\frac{1 + \gamma L}{L^3} \end{aligned} \quad (4.59)$$

where $\delta = \frac{1}{4} \exp(-\gamma L)$ and $\gamma = \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \kappa^2}$. The normalization constant A_{ex} is in the present case obtained from the charge neutrality condition (4.20) in the

Fig. 4.2. The variational screening length α^{-1} as a function of the position of charge Q , z_1 . The screening becomes less effective in the region close to the jellium edge.

analytical form

$$A_{ex} = e^{\alpha L} [1 + L\alpha + \frac{1}{3}L^2\alpha^2]^{-1}. \quad (4.60)$$

Here α is the parameter, but unlike in the previous section it is *not* treated variationally. It can be shown that for $\alpha \rightarrow \infty$ the self-energy ΔE_2 of a charge Q approaches the classical image form. For the purpose of the present work ΔE_2 was computed numerically for two values of α : $\alpha = 1.0$ and $\alpha = 200.0$. The computations were performed for the Au jellium surface. The case $\alpha = 1.0$ corresponds approximately to the usual bulk screening in Au and for $\alpha = 200.0$ nearly all induced charge is well localized in the layer $|z| \leq L$. This 'corresponds' to the classical picture of an ideal conductor when all induced charge is distributed over an infinitely thin sheet at $z = 0$. The contribution of the Coulomb self-interaction energy $\Delta E_{2\text{Coul}}$ in (4.25c) consists of three terms

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{2\text{Coul}} &= \frac{1}{2} \int d\mathbf{r} d\mathbf{r}' \frac{n_1(\mathbf{r})n_1(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|} \\ &= \Delta E_{C_1} + \Delta E_{C_2} + \Delta E_{C_3}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.61)$$

These terms for $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ given by (4.57) are written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{C_1} &= \frac{1}{2} A_{ex}^2 \int_0^\infty d\kappa \frac{(\gamma - \kappa)^2}{\gamma(\kappa + \gamma)} \exp\{-2(\kappa z_1 + \gamma L)\} \\ \Delta E_{C_2} &= \frac{1}{2} A_{ex}^2 \int_0^\infty d\kappa \int_{-L}^L dz \int_{-L}^L dz' (\gamma - \kappa)^2 f_3(z; \kappa) f_3(z'; \kappa) \exp\{-2\kappa z_1 - \kappa|z - z'|\} \\ \Delta E_{C_3} &= A_{ex}^2 \int_0^\infty d\kappa \int_{-L}^L dz \int_{-L}^L dz' (\gamma - \kappa)^2 f_3(z'; \kappa) \\ &\quad \exp\{-2\kappa z_1 + \gamma z - \kappa|z - z'|\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.62)$$

We quote these results explicitly since the speed and accuracy of the numerical multidimensional integration routines depend strongly on the number of dimensions and it is always desirable to reduce all the integrals to the lowest dimensional form. Similar reductions were also used for the computations in the previous section.

The final results for the interaction potential (ΔE_2 (4.25c)) of the charge Q with a metal jellium are presented in Fig.4.3. It should be noted that ΔE_2 deep inside the metal has a value agreeing with a formula $\Delta E_2(z \rightarrow \infty) = -\frac{Q^2}{2}\alpha$; this result coincides with predictions of the hydrodynamic model (Mahanty *et al.*, 1986). Our value of the potential inside the metal is higher by about 30% than that given by Mahanty *et al.*, (1986) on the basis of quantum mechanical self-energy treatment with inclusion of hydrodynamic dispersion. The difference can be attributed to the effects of recoil associated with quantum mechanical virtual and real emission and reabsorption of plasmons by the particle (Mahanty *et al.*, 1986) which is not described within the present formalism. We expect however that the inclusion of this effect would lower the potential curve inside the metal, thus producing even more satisfactory agreement between our work and that of Mahanty *et al.*(1986). We were not able to produce a continuous potential curve in the region $|z| < L$, since the induced density disturbance $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ when the charge Q is in the region of surface inhomogeneity is not known at the present time. In Fig.4.4 we present the absolute values of the relative contributions from all three terms in (4.25c), for a charge outside the metal. The term due to $G[n]$ is not negligible only at small distance from the surface. The two most important contributions are the terms of electrostatic nature. They produce saturation of ΔE_2 to the image potential form.

4.4.4 Concluding remarks; work function and effective one-electron surface potential

The formalism introduced in section 4.2 of this chapter could in principle be used to evaluate the interaction potential of a static charge with a metal surface of arbitrary geometry. The problem which would have to be addressed then concerns the choice of the most appropriate family of trial functions $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ describing the

Fig.4.3. Interaction potential of a charge $Q = 1$ with the induced charge density in the surface region of Au jellium. Outside the jellium ($z > 0$) solid line represents results obtained from (4.25c) and (4.57) for $\alpha = 1.0$; dashed line: $\alpha = 200.0$; dotted line: classical image potential.

induced charge fluctuation in metal. Here we have demonstrated how the method works using the simplest example of a semi-infinite jellium metal surface and a very simple model of equilibrium electronic density $n_0(\mathbf{r})$. The trial function for the induced density $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ was assumed to be well-described by the form obtained from the hydrodynamic model, supplemented continuously by a polynomial expression in the surface inhomogeneity region. The method presented here could in principle be also used in a self-consistent calculation. It has to be emphasised that our work differs from the work of Lang and Kohn (1973) on induced surface charge and the image potential. First of all Lang and Kohn assumed that the external perturbing charge is localized on an infinitely thin sheet parallel to the jellium edge ($\rho^{ext}(\mathbf{r}) = Q\delta(z - z_1)\exp(i\mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{v})$), consequently their induced density was a function of the perpendicular coordinate z only, whereas our $n_1(\mathbf{r})$ describes the response to the localized *point* charge ($\rho^{ext}(\mathbf{r}) = Q\delta(\mathbf{r} - z_1)$) and has truly three-dimensional character. Secondly, the interaction potential of Lang and Kohn was obtained using the classical linear response expression (1.4). It is immediately seen that the expression (1.4) is just one half of the first term in our expansion (4.25c). From Fig.4.4 we see that (1.4) is indeed equivalent to the sum of the first two terms in (4.25c) (they are of opposite sign). But the most important observation is that the potential energy given by (1.4) neglects the third term in (4.25). Although its contribution is rather small, it becomes increasingly important very close to the jellium surface. This term will certainly affect in an important way the saturation value of the interaction potential at $z = 0$.

The analysis of the interaction potential based on (4.25c) presented so far was applicable for an *identifiable* charge Q . The results obtained for a charge Q outside the metal are valid also for Q being an electron. However, inside the jellium an effective *one-electron* potential is given by the Kohn-Sham (1965) expression (4.9), where in the present context φ is the electrostatic potential due to a surface charge

Fig.4.4 Relative contribution of three terms in expression (4.25c) to the total induced energy shift ΔE_2 outside the Au jellium surface; solid line — $|e_1/\Delta E_2|$, dashed line — $|e_2/\Delta E_2|$, dash-dotted line — $|e_3/\Delta E_3|$; where e_1 , e_2 and e_3 are the first, second and third term in expression (4.25c) respectively.

distribution (4.34–4.35). For the local form of E_{xc} given in (4.7) the one-electron potential is written as (Smith, 1969),

$$v_{eff}(z) = \varphi(z) - \left(\frac{3}{\pi}\right)^{1/3} n_0^{1/3}(z) - \frac{0.056n_0^{2/3}(z) + 0.0059n_0^{1/3}(z)}{(0.079 + n_0^{1/3}(z))^2}. \quad (4.63)$$

In Fig.4.5 we present the results for the effective one-electron potential v_{eff} obtained from (4.63) and (4.35) and we compare them with Smith's (1969) results. Smith interpreted v_{eff} outside the jellium as the equivalent of the 'image potential'. His v_{eff} exhibited an exponential decay outside the jellium and that was due to the particular choice of the (unperturbed) density profile (4.29). Our results (Fig.4.5) demonstrate that v_{eff} will vanish at $z = L$, where L is the distance from the jellium edge where the equilibrium density $n_0(z)$ becomes zero. The image potential arises from the induced charge distribution $n_1(r)$ and Smith's approach using the unperturbed equilibrium profile is not able to account for it. It has to be stressed that the effective potential v_{eff} has a meaning only in the regions of nonzero electronic density, since it is used self-consistently in Kohn-Sham equations to evaluate the density $n(r)$.

A very important problem related to the present analysis is the evaluation of the work function. This topic has been studied extensively before. Worth mentioning here are works of Smith (1969) and Lang and Kohn (1971) who used the density functional formalism. It is well known (Lang and Kohn, 1971) that the jellium model represents too idealized a system to describe the work function of real metals across the periodic table. The self-consistent calculations which take into account the periodic structure of the underlying lattice show a great improvement over the computed values for a jellium (Lang and Kohn, 1971). In the present work we did not attempt to go beyond the jellium model and we realize shortcomings of this idealization, especially in the context of work function calculations. It is

Fig.4.5 Effective one-electron potential in surface region of Au jellium. Solid line — our work (eq.(4.63)); dashed line — Smith's (1969) results.

however important to observe that unlike the calculations of Lang and Kohn (1971) the computations of Smith (1969) were not self-consistently solved and hence did not include the effect of the image potential on the work function.

The work function Φ , within the limited application of the model we use here will be given by the Smith expression (Smith, 1969, eq.(2.4)) *plus* the value of the image potential at $z = L$

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi = & -\varphi(-\infty) - \frac{1}{2}(3\pi^2)^{2/3}n_+^{2/3} \\ & + \frac{0.056n_+^{2/3} + 0.0059n_+^{1/3}}{(0.079 + n_+^{1/3})^2} + \left(\frac{3}{\pi}\right)^{1/3}n_+^{1/3} \\ & + \Delta E_2[n; z_1 = L]. \end{aligned} \quad (4.64)$$

In Table 4.5 the results for the work function of selected metals are given. Although the agreement with experimental data for some metals is satisfactory (and better than Smith's values) it has to be stressed that this theory overestimates the work function for alkali metals and is too insensitive to follow the trends observed experimentally. The *only* parameter of the present theory is the radius r_s , related to the bulk electronic density $n_0(-\infty)$ and this, obviously is insufficient data to describe the work function of real metals adequately.

Table 4.5 Work function of selected metals. Comparison of results obtained from our expression (4.64) with Smith's (1969) (S) work and experimental values.

Metal	r_s [a.u.]	Work function [eV]		
		(S)	(4.64)	Experiment*
Ag	3.02	3.19	4.84	4.26
Au	3.01	3.19	4.8	5.1
Cu	2.67	3.32	4.75	4.65
Mg	2.65	3.33	4.75	3.66

* from CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics (1987);

CHAPTER 5. INTERACTION OF A CHARGED PARTICLE WITH A DIELECTRIC SURFACE

5.1 Brief review of other work (Introduction)

Hitherto we were concerned with the interaction potential of the charged particle with metals. In this chapter we demonstrate how the general formalism developed in Chapter 2 can be applied to study the interaction potential of an external charge near a *dielectric-vacuum* interface. The modes responsible for the interaction with dielectrics are optical phonons and excitons (see e.g. Mahan, 1974). The problem of coupling of electrons to long-wavelength optical phonons was first studied by Lucas *et al.*, (1970a,b) in the context of the investigation of electron energy loss spectra. The evaluation of the interaction between an electron and a dielectric was a necessary part of calculations of probability of inelastic electron scattering from surface excitations (Wang and Mahan, 1972). It also formed an essential ingredient of theory of surface polarons (Sak, 1972; Evans and Mills, 1972, 1973). A comprehensive treatment of this topic has been presented by Sols and Ritchie (1986) on the basis of the self-energy (eq. 2.19) formalism of Manson and Ritchie (1981). Our object here is to show how the known results for dielectric solids are rederived within the unifying framework of our self-energy formalism developed in section 2.2. Our expression for the self-energy (at $T = 0$, eq. 2.41) is fully determined when the 'coupling constants' $\varphi_\lambda(\mathbf{r})$ (see 2.21d) are known. The coupling constants depend on the geometry of the solid sample and the type of modes present in the system. The *spatial dispersion* of long-wavelength optical phonons and excitons was neglected in all the works quoted above. We will outline the steps necessary to incorporate the spatial dispersion of these modes in the coupling constants. The interaction potential of a charge near a spatially dispersive dielectric solid would thus ensue in a straightforward

manner from (2.41).

5.2 The image potential at the surface of a spatially nondispersive insulator.

The classical long-wavelength optical polarization modes in ionic crystal slabs of finite thickness L were obtained in a well known series of papers by Fuchs and Kliewer (1965; Kliewer and Fuchs, 1966a,b). A very illustrative exposition of the quantization procedure for the free polarization Hamiltonian using Fuchs and Kliewer modes was presented by Lucas *et al.*, (1970b). Another approach can be found in Wang and Mahan (1972). The quantization procedure yields the coupling constants Γ_κ in the interaction Hamiltonian (1.7). We simply quote the results for Γ_κ for a semi-infinite insulator (Sols and Ritchie, 1986)

$$\Gamma_\kappa^2 = \frac{\pi e^2 \hbar \omega_s}{A \kappa} \eta_s \quad (5.1)$$

where A is the surface area, ω_s is the frequency of surface excitation and the factor η_s is

$$\eta_s = \frac{\epsilon_0 - 1}{\epsilon_0 + 1} - \frac{\epsilon_\infty - 1}{\epsilon_\infty + 1} \quad (5.2)$$

for the surface optical phonons, and

$$\eta_s = \frac{\epsilon_\infty - 1}{\epsilon_\infty + 1} \quad (5.3)$$

for the surface exciton; here ϵ_0 is the static dielectric constant of the lattice and ϵ_∞ is the dielectric constant corresponding to frequencies much higher than the phonon frequencies, but still lower than the exciton frequencies. Using the nondispersive model (5.1)–(5.3) we can identify the *surface modes* coupling constant $\varphi_\lambda(\mathbf{r})$ in our Hamiltonian (2.21d) (for $|Q/e| = 1$) as

$$\varphi_\lambda(\mathbf{r}) \equiv \varphi_\kappa(\mathbf{r}) = \Gamma_\kappa e^{i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \boldsymbol{\rho}} e^{-\kappa|z|} \quad (5.4)$$

where the mode index λ denotes the type of undispersed mode and the wave vector parallel to the surface κ .

The classical interaction energy of a charge with only the surface modes of a dielectric is immediately obtained from our expression (2.34) for a static, massive ($M \rightarrow \infty$) particle

$$\begin{aligned}\Sigma_c(z) &= -\frac{e^2 \epsilon_0 - 1}{4z \epsilon_0 + 1}, \quad z > 0 \quad (\text{outside the dielectric}) \\ &= \frac{e^2 \epsilon_0 - 1}{4z \epsilon_0 (\epsilon_0 + 1)}, \quad z < 0 \quad (\text{inside the dielectric.})\end{aligned}\quad (5.5)$$

The surface contribution to the self-energy for the more general case of the charged particle moving with the velocity $\mathbf{v} = \frac{\hbar}{M}(\kappa_0, k_{z0})$ is obtained by substituting (5.4) into our general formula (2.41). This gives

$$\Sigma_{\kappa_0}(z) = -\frac{e^2 Q_s^2}{(2\pi)^2} \eta_s \int d^2 \kappa \int dk \frac{e^{-\kappa|z|}}{Q^2 + k^2} \frac{e^{ikz}}{\kappa^2 + k^2 + 2k_{z0}k + 2\kappa_0 \cdot \kappa + Q_s^2 - i0^+} \quad (5.6)$$

where $Q_s = \frac{2M\omega_s}{\hbar}$.

Expression (5.6) is identical with the result of Sols and Ritchie (1986, eq.6), and hence *all* the results obtained by those authors are also obtainable here, starting with equation (2.41).

As an example we give the expression for the self-energy derived from (5.6) when the charge is incoming normal to the surface and can excite only the virtual surface phonons and excitons (i.e. below the threshold case, $k_0 < Q_s$). It separates naturally into real and imaginary parts (Sols and Ritchie, 1986)

$$\begin{aligned}Re\Sigma_s(z) &= -\frac{e^2 \omega_s}{2v} \eta_s f\left(\frac{2\omega_s|z|}{v}\right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} e^2 Q_s \eta_s [\cos(k_{z0}z)A_1(z) - \text{sgn}(z) \sin(k_{z0}z)A_2(z)]\end{aligned}\quad (5.7a)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Im}\Sigma_s(z) = & \text{sgn}(z) \frac{e^2 \omega_s}{2\nu} \eta_s g\left(\frac{2\omega_s |z|}{\nu}\right) \\ & - \frac{1}{2} e^2 Q_s \eta_s [\sin(k_{z0} z) A_1(z) + \text{sgn}(z) \cos(k_{z0} z) A_2(z)] \end{aligned} \quad (5.7b)$$

where $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ are the auxiliary functions to the exponential integral (Abramowitz and Stegun, 1965 p.232) and the integrals A_1, A_2 are given by

$$A_1(z) = \mu(1 - 2\nu^2) \int_0^\infty \frac{x}{(1+x^2)^{1/2}} \frac{\exp\{-(x+(1+x^2)^{1/2})\mu Q_s |z|\}}{1+(2\mu\nu x)^2} dx \quad (5.8a)$$

$$A_2(z) = 2\mu^2 \nu \int_0^\infty \frac{x \exp\{-(x+(1+x^2)^{1/2})\mu Q_s |z|\}}{1+(2\mu\nu x)^2} dx. \quad (5.8b)$$

Here $\nu = k_0/Q_s$ and $\mu = (1 - \nu^2)^{1/2}$. The above-the-threshold case is also given in Sols and Ritchie (1986) and in Manson and Ritchie (1981) and will not be reproduced here. The interaction of a charge with *bulk, nondispersive* modes of insulator is derived in a completely analogous way as described here. The coupling constant is now given by

$$\varphi_\lambda(\mathbf{r}) = \Lambda_\kappa e^{i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \boldsymbol{\rho}} \sin(pz), \quad p > 0 \quad (5.9)$$

where $\Lambda_\kappa^2 = \frac{4\pi e^2 \hbar \omega_b}{q^2 V} \eta_b$, V is the volume, ω_b is the bulk mode frequency and $\eta_b = (\epsilon_\infty^{-1} - \epsilon_0^{-1})$ for the optical phonons and $\eta_b = (1 - \epsilon_\infty^{-1})$ for the exciton. We refer for the detailed results to Sols and Ritchie (1986).

The self-energy of a static charge near an insulator without spatial dispersion is derived from (5.7) and the expressions for the bulk modes contribution. This yields

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{\boldsymbol{\kappa}_0=0}(z) &= \Sigma_s(z) + \Sigma_b(z), \\ \Sigma_s(z) &= -\frac{e^2}{4|z|} \sum_l \eta_{sl} S(Q_{sl}|z|) \end{aligned} \quad (5.10)$$

$$\Sigma_b(z) = -\frac{e^2}{2} \sum_l \eta_{bl} Q_{bl} - \frac{e^2}{4z} \sum_l \eta_{bl} S(Q_{bl}Z) \quad (5.11)$$

where l denotes optical phonon (o) or exciton (e) mode, $Q_{ij} = \left(\frac{2M\omega_{ij}}{\hbar}\right)^{1/2}$, and $S(t) = 1 - 2 \int_1^\infty dx \frac{e^{-xt}}{x^3}$. The constants η_{ij} were given in the text above and the frequencies of modes are

$$\omega_{so}^2 = \frac{\epsilon_0 + 1}{\epsilon_\infty + 1} \omega_t^2, \quad \omega_{se}^2 = \frac{\epsilon_\infty + 1}{2} \omega_e^2 \quad (5.12a)$$

$$\omega_{bo}^2 = \frac{\epsilon_0}{\epsilon_\infty} \omega_t^2, \quad \omega_{be}^2 = \epsilon_\infty \omega_e^2 \quad (5.12b)$$

where ω_t is the transverse optical phonon frequency and $\hbar\omega_e$ is the effective excitation energy.

This completes the discussion of the interaction of a charged particle with a non-dispersive, semi-infinite dielectric solid. The specific results presented here are not new (Sols and Ritchie, 1986) but the main point is that all of these results, including (5.6), are implicitly encompassed in our general expression for the self-energy (2.41).

5.3 Modes in a dielectric with spatial dispersion, and the self-energy

The self-energy of a charge near a surface of a *spatially dispersive** dielectric can be obtained from (2.41) in a way analogous to that presented in a previous section, provided that normal modes to which the particle is coupled and the coupling constants $\varphi_\lambda(\mathbf{r})$ (2.21d) are known. The latter problem is difficult and a detailed discussion is not attempted here (see e.g. Agranovich and Ginzburg, 1984). We will briefly indicate the formal steps for finding the normal polarization modes of dispersive, semi-infinite dielectric.

Let us consider a dielectric in the continuum approximation. The macroscopic Maxwell's equations describing the electromagnetic field are

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \frac{1}{c} \dot{\mathbf{E}} + \frac{4\pi}{c} \dot{\mathbf{P}} \quad (5.13a)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{1}{c} \dot{\mathbf{H}}. \quad (5.13b)$$

* Here, and in the following, dispersive means spatially dispersive.

There are no macroscopic currents in this insulating medium, and the magnetic permeability μ is assumed to be 1. The polarization vector $\mathbf{P}$ in the dispersive dielectric will be assumed to satisfy the phenomenological equation of motion

$$\ddot{\mathbf{P}} + (\omega_0^2 - B^2 \nabla^2) \mathbf{P} = \chi \mathbf{E} \quad (5.14)$$

where χ is the electric susceptibility and ω_0 is the characteristic frequency: long-wavelength limit of optical phonon frequency or exciton frequency. This equation is the vector analogue of the hydrodynamic equation of motion for the charge density in metal (3.20) but it also expresses the coupling of the polarization vector $\mathbf{P}$ to the electric field $\mathbf{E}$.

In eq.(5.14) the dispersion coefficient B has significance only in the long wavelength limit. In general, in an optically anisotropic crystal $B^2 \nabla^2$ can be replaced by an expression of the type $(\mathbf{B} \nabla)^2$ which is a second rank tensor with symmetries appropriate to the crystal. The value of B can in principle be empirically determined by fitting the quadratic expression, $\omega^2 = \omega_0^2 + B^2 k^2$, to the experimental dispersion curves near $k = 0$. Eliminating the magnetic field $\mathbf{H}$ from (5.13) leads to the wave equation

$$-\nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) = \frac{1}{c^2} \ddot{\mathbf{E}} + \frac{4\pi}{c^2} \ddot{\mathbf{P}}. \quad (5.15)$$

This equation combined with (5.14) is easily solved for the *homogeneous, nondispersive* dielectric if oscillatory form of solutions is considered, i.e. $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}_0 e^{i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t)}$, $\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{P}_0 e^{i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t)}$, $\mathbf{P}_0 = \text{const.}$, $E_0 = \text{const.}$ This results in the dispersion relations for longitudinal and transverse modes being a fourth order polynomial of ω . The modes represented by those solutions are called phonon-polaritons or exciton-polaritons, depending on the microscopic mechanism determining the values of macroscopic constants. Now if we introduce the surface and the dispersion term in (5.14) is retained ($B \neq 0$), then the solution of the system

of equations (5.14), (5.15) is far from trivial. In such a case additional boundary conditions (ABC) must be introduced* to secure the solubility of this system. There is a certain degree of arbitrariness as to what are the most appropriate, physical ABC's. This is a well known problem (e.g. Pekar, 1958a,b, 1968; Mahan, 1974; Hopfield and Thomas, 1963; Agranovich and Ginzburg, 1984; Ruppin, 1984). Suppose the system (5.14), (5.15) with ABC's is solved. In order to determine the spectrum of phonon-polariton or exciton-polariton we have to make connection with *microscopic* dynamics by relating the material constants, say χ , with the parameters of lattice dynamics or exciton dynamics. This is again a problem in its own right and extensive treatment exists in the literature (Born and Huang, 1968; Maradudin *et al.*, 1971; Knox, 1963).

If the normal polarization modes $\mathbf{P}_\lambda(\mathbf{r})$ are derived by following the steps described above, they can be canonically quantized (Lucas *et al.*, 1970b) and the coupling constants (potentials due to λ -th polarization modes) are obtained from the relation

$$\varphi_\lambda(\mathbf{r}) = - \int d\mathbf{r}' \frac{\nabla' \cdot \mathbf{P}_\lambda(\mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|}. \quad (5.16)$$

Having obtained this, the self-energy of a charge would be then derived from (2.41).

* Obviously the usual boundary conditions on the dielectric-vacuum interface $\lim_{z \rightarrow 0^+} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} E_z + 4\pi P_z \\ E_x \\ E_y \end{array} \right\} = \lim_{z \rightarrow 0^-} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} E_z \\ E_x \\ E_y \end{array} \right\}$ must hold as well.

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APPENDIX

This appendix contains the tables of interaction potential of a charged particle close to the surface of a metallic sphere. The radius of the sphere takes the values $R \in \{10, 20, 50, 100\}[k_1^{-1}]$ (Tables A2, A3, A4 and A5 respectively). For each radius the parameter $k_2/k_1 \in \{1.0, 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4\}$. The value k_1 was taken for Ag. Although the expression (3.71), for the potential of a charge in the vicinity of a flat metal surface, is trivial to compute numerically we list the values in Table A1 for the sake of completeness.

The energy units are $Q^2 k_1 = 2a_0 k_1 [Ry]$ (see a caption to Figure 3.9).

TABLE A1

z*k1	Potential
0.00	-0.33333334E+00
1.00	-0.12826085E+00
2.00	-0.84014904E-01
3.00	-0.62724113E-01
4.00	-0.50094020E-01
5.00	-0.41712714E-01
6.00	-0.35739401E-01
7.00	-0.31264830E-01
8.00	-0.27787086E-01
9.00	-0.25006131E-01
10.00	-0.22731473E-01
11.00	-0.20836306E-01
12.00	-0.19232932E-01
13.00	-0.17858753E-01
14.00	-0.16667890E-01
15.00	-0.15625946E-01
16.00	-0.14706625E-01
17.00	-0.13889480E-01
18.00	-0.13158372E-01
19.00	-0.12500389E-01
20.00	-0.11905082E-01
21.00	-0.11363902E-01
22.00	-0.10869788E-01
23.00	-0.10416854E-01
24.00	-0.10000159E-01
25.00	-0.96155210E-02
26.00	-0.92593765E-02
27.00	-0.89286728E-02
28.00	-0.86207778E-02
29.00	-0.83334103E-02
30.00	-0.80645837E-02
31.00	-0.78125595E-02
32.00	-0.75758102E-02
33.00	-0.73529879E-02
34.00	-0.71428987E-02
35.00	-0.69444816E-02
36.00	-0.67567901E-02
37.00	-0.65789773E-02
38.00	-0.64102834E-02
39.00	-0.62500244E-02
40.00	-0.60975831E-02
41.00	-0.59524010E-02
42.00	-0.58139717E-02
43.00	-0.56818348E-02
44.00	-0.55555708E-02
45.00	-0.54347966E-02
46.00	-0.53191617E-02
47.00	-0.52083451E-02
48.00	-0.51020516E-02
49.00	-0.50000100E-02
50.00	-0.49019700E-02

TABLE A2

Radius of the sphere is $10.0 \cdot k_1$ The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.0 The number of surface modes is 4The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.1 The number of surface modes is 4The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.2 The number of surface modes is 5The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.3 The number of surface modes is 5The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.4 The number of surface modes is 6

k_2/k_1	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4
$z \cdot k_1$	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5
0.00	-0.10780959E+00	-0.11378060E+00	-0.13776759E+00	-0.14389959E+00	-0.16788439E+00
1.00	-0.59448833E-01	-0.62487599E-01	-0.71123707E-01	-0.73951930E-01	-0.81349306E-01
2.00	-0.35745403E-01	-0.37447726E-01	-0.41038360E-01	-0.42517132E-01	-0.45274994E-01
3.00	-0.22969651E-01	-0.23999242E-01	-0.25701426E-01	-0.26554385E-01	-0.27781547E-01
4.00	-0.15543071E-01	-0.16205154E-01	-0.17111438E-01	-0.17642466E-01	-0.18279075E-01
5.00	-0.10956612E-01	-0.11403901E-01	-0.11936311E-01	-0.12287197E-01	-0.12660429E-01
6.00	-0.79820853E-02	-0.82966168E-02	-0.86354120E-02	-0.88783937E-02	-0.91181860E-02
7.00	-0.59741873E-02	-0.62027579E-02	-0.64323660E-02	-0.66070417E-02	-0.67716847E-02
8.00	-0.45730971E-02	-0.47437970E-02	-0.49072091E-02	-0.50366491E-02	-0.51552835E-02
9.00	-0.35678470E-02	-0.36982861E-02	-0.38190877E-02	-0.39174348E-02	-0.40060336E-02
10.00	-0.28293530E-02	-0.29309889E-02	-0.30229892E-02	-0.30992914E-02	-0.31672965E-02
11.00	-0.22756958E-02	-0.23562260E-02	-0.24279736E-02	-0.24882319E-02	-0.25415724E-02
12.00	-0.18532261E-02	-0.19179673E-02	-0.19750089E-02	-0.20233278E-02	-0.20659099E-02
13.00	-0.15258347E-02	-0.15785492E-02	-0.16246283E-02	-0.16638900E-02	-0.16983877E-02
14.00	-0.12686299E-02	-0.13120369E-02	-0.13497646E-02	-0.13820397E-02	-0.14103411E-02
15.00	-0.10640868E-02	-0.11001888E-02	-0.11314373E-02	-0.11582436E-02	-0.11817158E-02
16.00	-0.89963386E-03	-0.92993044E-03	-0.95607352E-03	-0.97854306E-03	-0.99819755E-03
17.00	-0.76610109E-03	-0.79173194E-03	-0.81379798E-03	-0.83278843E-03	-0.84938687E-03
18.00	-0.65669813E-03	-0.67854110E-03	-0.69731309E-03	-0.71348333E-03	-0.72760843E-03
19.00	-0.56632812E-03	-0.58506755E-03	-0.60115052E-03	-0.61501307E-03	-0.62711674E-03
20.00	-0.49111780E-03	-0.50729308E-03	-0.52116066E-03	-0.53311872E-03	-0.54355567E-03
21.00	-0.42809045E-03	-0.44213099E-03	-0.45415824E-03	-0.46453227E-03	-0.47358393E-03
22.00	-0.37493466E-03	-0.38718541E-03	-0.39767241E-03	-0.40671952E-03	-0.41461140E-03
23.00	-0.32983848E-03	-0.30082732E-03	-0.30891575E-03	-0.31589478E-03	-0.32198021E-03
25.00	-0.25838379E-03	-0.26674762E-03	-0.27389737E-03	-0.28006659E-03	-0.28544503E-03
26.00	-0.22996514E-03	-0.23738982E-03	-0.24373470E-03	-0.24920941E-03	-0.25398169E-03
27.00	-0.20537063E-03	-0.21198553E-03	-0.21763685E-03	-0.22251302E-03	-0.22676302E-03
28.00	-0.18399568E-03	-0.18990919E-03	-0.19496011E-03	-0.19931808E-03	-0.20311600E-03
29.00	-0.16534491E-03	-0.17064834E-03	-0.17517724E-03	-0.17908464E-03	-0.18248955E-03
30.00	-0.14901008E-03	-0.15378072E-03	-0.15785390E-03	-0.16136797E-03	-0.16442985E-03
31.00	-0.13465288E-03	-0.13895649E-03	-0.14263033E-03	-0.14579972E-03	-0.14856104E-03
32.00	-0.12199157E-03	-0.12588432E-03	-0.12920696E-03	-0.13207323E-03	-0.13457026E-03
33.00	-0.11079032E-03	-0.11432042E-03	-0.11733315E-03	-0.11993194E-03	-0.12219579E-03
34.00	-0.10085085E-03	-0.10405984E-03	-0.10679822E-03	-0.10916023E-03	-0.11121767E-03
35.00	-0.92005718E-04	-0.94929524E-04	-0.97424277E-04	-0.99576043E-04	-0.10145024E-03
36.00	-0.84112938E-04	-0.86782732E-04	-0.89060536E-04	-0.91025084E-04	-0.92736122E-04
37.00	-0.77051633E-04	-0.79494568E-04	-0.81578643E-04	-0.83376020E-04	-0.84941379E-04
38.00	-0.70718517E-04	-0.72958316E-04	-0.74868946E-04	-0.76516663E-04	-0.77951612E-04
39.00	-0.65025014E-04	-0.67082469E-04	-0.68837427E-04	-0.70350828E-04	-0.71668746E-04
40.00	-0.59894906E-04	-0.61788296E-04	-0.63403202E-04	-0.64795771E-04	-0.66008412E-04
41.00	-0.55262398E-04	-0.57007833E-04	-0.58496455E-04	-0.59780075E-04	-0.60897799E-04
42.00	-0.51070511E-04	-0.52682233E-04	-0.54056737E-04	-0.55241909E-04	-0.56273871E-04
43.00	-0.47269757E-04	-0.48760387E-04	-0.50031552E-04	-0.51127580E-04	-0.52081889E-04
44.00	-0.43817031E-04	-0.45197778E-04	-0.46375181E-04	-0.47390330E-04	-0.48274188E-04
45.00	-0.40674682E-04	-0.41955531E-04	-0.43047696E-04	-0.43989323E-04	-0.44809142E-04
46.00	-0.37809740E-04	-0.38999600E-04	-0.40014137E-04	-0.40888806E-04	-0.41650308E-04
47.00	-0.35193259E-04	-0.36300101E-04	-0.37243812E-04	-0.38057396E-04	-0.38765696E-04
48.00	-0.32799766E-04	-0.33830731E-04	-0.34709715E-04	-0.35467476E-04	-0.36127159E-04
49.00	-0.30606787E-04	-0.31568292E-04	-0.32388025E-04	-0.33094687E-04	-0.33709870E-04
50.00	-0.28594455E-04	-0.29492273E-04	-0.30257683E-04	-0.30917498E-04	-0.31491885E-04

TABLE A3

Radius of the sphere is $20.0 \cdot k_1$ The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.0 The number of surface modes is 9The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.1 The number of surface modes is 10The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.2 The number of surface modes is 11The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.3 The number of surface modes is 12The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.4 The number of surface modes is 13

k_2/k_1	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4
$z \cdot k_1$	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5
0.00	-0.12934619E+00	-0.14452094E+00	-0.15970697E+00	-0.17490154E+00	-0.19010273E+00
1.00	-0.79509255E-01	-0.85928510E-01	-0.91908473E-01	-0.97482749E-01	-0.10268258E+00
2.00	-0.52561042E-01	-0.55624863E-01	-0.58340993E-01	-0.60757362E-01	-0.62914829E-01
3.00	-0.36790725E-01	-0.38435211E-01	-0.39852139E-01	-0.41082375E-01	-0.42158533E-01
4.00	-0.26923140E-01	-0.27903182E-01	-0.28736833E-01	-0.29454024E-01	-0.30077501E-01
5.00	-0.20397443E-01	-0.21033961E-01	-0.21573275E-01	-0.22036421E-01	-0.22438885E-01
6.00	-0.15882089E-01	-0.16324016E-01	-0.16698410E-01	-0.17020134E-01	-0.17299950E-01
7.00	-0.12640488E-01	-0.12963136E-01	-0.13236728E-01	-0.13472034E-01	-0.13676809E-01
8.00	-0.10242154E-01	-0.10486787E-01	-0.10694395E-01	-0.10873029E-01	-0.11028494E-01
9.00	-0.84231020E-02	-0.86140042E-02	-0.87760781E-02	-0.89155326E-02	-0.90368624E-02
10.00	-0.70145613E-02	-0.71669186E-02	-0.72962712E-02	-0.74075368E-02	-0.75042921E-02
11.00	-0.59046785E-02	-0.60284809E-02	-0.61335642E-02	-0.62239113E-02	-0.63024305E-02
12.00	-0.50169907E-02	-0.51190869E-02	-0.52057108E-02	-0.52801468E-02	-0.53448000E-02
13.00	-0.42978121E-02	-0.43830577E-02	-0.44553498E-02	-0.45174361E-02	-0.45713330E-02
14.00	-0.37085656E-02	-0.37805000E-02	-0.38414724E-02	-0.38938093E-02	-0.39392199E-02
15.00	-0.32209668E-02	-0.32822293E-02	-0.33341299E-02	-0.33786579E-02	-0.34172755E-02
16.00	-0.28139079E-02	-0.28665051E-02	-0.29110433E-02	-0.29492375E-02	-0.29823486E-02
17.00	-0.24713895E-02	-0.25168726E-02	-0.25553694E-02	-0.25883692E-02	-0.26169670E-02
18.00	-0.21811157E-02	-0.22207007E-02	-0.22541915E-02	-0.22828896E-02	-0.23077515E-02
19.00	-0.19335190E-02	-0.19681714E-02	-0.19974779E-02	-0.20225821E-02	-0.20443244E-02
20.00	-0.17210720E-02	-0.17515669E-02	-0.17773484E-02	-0.17994264E-02	-0.18185428E-02
21.00	-0.15377925E-02	-0.15647584E-02	-0.15875490E-02	-0.16070607E-02	-0.16239510E-02
22.00	-0.13788829E-02	-0.14028338E-02	-0.14230705E-02	-0.14403914E-02	-0.14553822E-02
23.00	-0.12404631E-02	-0.12618231E-02	-0.12798659E-02	-0.12953056E-02	-0.13086658E-02
24.00	-0.11193715E-02	-0.11384928E-02	-0.11546408E-02	-0.11684563E-02	-0.11804089E-02
25.00	-0.10130131E-02	-0.10301905E-02	-0.10446937E-02	-0.10570997E-02	-0.10678312E-02
26.00	-0.91924458E-03	-0.93472622E-03	-0.94779496E-03	-0.95897203E-03	-0.96863912E-03
27.00	-0.83628470E-03	-0.85028059E-03	-0.86209296E-03	-0.87219394E-03	-0.88092919E-03
28.00	-0.76264482E-03	-0.77533376E-03	-0.78604126E-03	-0.79519615E-03	-0.80311226E-03
29.00	-0.69707428E-03	-0.70860926E-03	-0.71834146E-03	-0.72666137E-03	-0.73385470E-03
30.00	-0.63851723E-03	-0.64902972E-03	-0.65789795E-03	-0.66547834E-03	-0.67203161E-03
31.00	-0.58607807E-03	-0.59568159E-03	-0.60378191E-03	-0.61070514E-03	-0.61668972E-03
32.00	-0.53899392E-03	-0.54778684E-03	-0.55520253E-03	-0.56153994E-03	-0.56701764E-03
33.00	-0.49661220E-03	-0.50468016E-03	-0.51148362E-03	-0.51729727E-03	-0.52232185E-03
34.00	-0.45837258E-03	-0.46579034E-03	-0.47204483E-03	-0.47738888E-03	-0.48200725E-03
35.00	-0.42379214E-03	-0.43062523E-03	-0.43638615E-03	-0.44130806E-03	-0.44556131E-03
36.00	-0.39245325E-03	-0.39875927E-03	-0.40407532E-03	-0.40861680E-03	-0.41254103E-03
37.00	-0.36399351E-03	-0.36982328E-03	-0.37473741E-03	-0.37893521E-03	-0.38256224E-03
38.00	-0.33809751E-03	-0.34349597E-03	-0.34804614E-03	-0.35193277E-03	-0.35529075E-03
39.00	-0.31448987E-03	-0.31949688E-03	-0.32371678E-03	-0.32732107E-03	-0.33043493E-03
40.00	-0.29292952E-03	-0.29758052E-03	-0.30150010E-03	-0.30484766E-03	-0.30773958E-03
41.00	-0.27320478E-03	-0.27753139E-03	-0.28117732E-03	-0.28429100E-03	-0.28698074E-03
42.00	-0.25512937E-03	-0.25915983E-03	-0.26255597E-03	-0.26545617E-03	-0.26796138E-03
43.00	-0.23853890E-03	-0.24229850E-03	-0.24546622E-03	-0.24817121E-03	-0.25050769E-03
44.00	-0.22328796E-03	-0.22679941E-03	-0.22975789E-03	-0.23228406E-03	-0.23446601E-03
45.00	-0.20924764E-03	-0.21253139E-03	-0.21529786E-03	-0.21765998E-03	-0.21970014E-03
46.00	-0.19630341E-03	-0.19937788E-03	-0.20196789E-03	-0.20417925E-03	-0.20608912E-03
47.00	-0.18435330E-03	-0.18723511E-03	-0.18966270E-03	-0.19173530E-03	-0.19352527E-03
48.00	-0.17330631E-03	-0.17601052E-03	-0.17828840E-03	-0.18023310E-03	-0.18191256E-03
49.00	-0.16308110E-03	-0.16562137E-03	-0.16776105E-03	-0.16958769E-03	-0.17116515E-03
50.00	-0.15360482E-03	-0.15599353E-03	-0.15800547E-03	-0.15972300E-03	-0.16120617E-03

TABLE A4

Radius of the sphere is 50.0*k1

The ratio k2/k1 is 1.0 The number of surface modes is 24

The ratio k2/k1 is 1.1 The number of surface modes is 26

The ratio k2/k1 is 1.2 The number of surface modes is 29

The ratio k2/k1 is 1.3 The number of surface modes is 31

The ratio k2/k1 is 1.4 The number of surface modes is 34

k2/k1	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4
z*k1	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5
0.00	-0.14300668E+00	-0.15653434E+00	-0.17346539E+00	-0.18700034E+00	-0.20392795E+00
1.00	-0.94068332E-01	-0.10010807E+00	-0.10681822E+00	-0.11207250E+00	-0.11786220E+00
2.00	-0.66256875E-01	-0.69256223E-01	-0.72270118E-01	-0.74643110E-01	-0.77002360E-01
3.00	-0.49287497E-01	-0.50951198E-01	-0.52504549E-01	-0.53754514E-01	-0.54915555E-01
4.00	-0.38250995E-01	-0.39273136E-01	-0.40184554E-01	-0.40936138E-01	-0.41609262E-01
5.00	-0.30668036E-01	-0.31351705E-01	-0.31946145E-01	-0.32445608E-01	-0.32885467E-01
6.00	-0.25213891E-01	-0.25702182E-01	-0.26121396E-01	-0.26477658E-01	-0.26789083E-01
7.00	-0.21141014E-01	-0.21507248E-01	-0.21819697E-01	-0.22086764E-01	-0.22319383E-01
8.00	-0.18005328E-01	-0.18290190E-01	-0.18532398E-01	-0.18739919E-01	-0.18920292E-01
9.00	-0.15530322E-01	-0.15758077E-01	-0.15951325E-01	-0.16116993E-01	-0.16260774E-01
10.00	-0.13536417E-01	-0.13722459E-01	-0.13880074E-01	-0.14015159E-01	-0.14132258E-01
11.00	-0.11902579E-01	-0.12057179E-01	-0.12187996E-01	-0.12300046E-01	-0.12397079E-01
12.00	-0.10544547E-01	-0.10674845E-01	-0.10784984E-01	-0.10879254E-01	-0.10960821E-01
13.00	-0.94019921E-02	-0.95131179E-02	-0.96069645E-02	-0.96872333E-02	-0.97566348E-02
14.00	-0.84306555E-02	-0.85263942E-02	-0.86071818E-02	-0.86762354E-02	-0.87359021E-02
15.00	-0.75973726E-02	-0.76805817E-02	-0.77507467E-02	-0.78106849E-02	-0.78624466E-02
16.00	-0.68768299E-02	-0.69497069E-02	-0.70111212E-02	-0.70635561E-02	-0.71088160E-02
17.00	-0.62493899E-02	-0.63136529E-02	-0.63677781E-02	-0.64139676E-02	-0.64538197E-02
18.00	-0.56995995E-02	-0.57566108E-02	-0.58046046E-02	-0.58455443E-02	-0.58808534E-02
19.00	-0.52151426E-02	-0.52659961E-02	-0.53087872E-02	-0.53452750E-02	-0.53767338E-02
20.00	-0.47860916E-02	-0.48316755E-02	-0.48700171E-02	-0.49026997E-02	-0.49308693E-02
21.00	-0.44043623E-02	-0.44454049E-02	-0.44799143E-02	-0.45093213E-02	-0.45346607E-02
22.00	-0.40633109E-02	-0.41004148E-02	-0.41316024E-02	-0.41581714E-02	-0.41810598E-02
23.00	-0.37574315E-02	-0.37910997E-02	-0.38193911E-02	-0.38434866E-02	-0.38642396E-02
24.00	-0.34821267E-02	-0.35127819E-02	-0.35385345E-02	-0.35604629E-02	-0.35793454E-02
25.00	-0.32335309E-02	-0.32615309E-02	-0.32850472E-02	-0.33050671E-02	-0.33223032E-02
26.00	-0.30083731E-02	-0.30340227E-02	-0.30555601E-02	-0.30738918E-02	-0.30896719E-02
27.00	-0.28038690E-02	-0.28274294E-02	-0.28472083E-02	-0.28640404E-02	-0.28785273E-02
28.00	-0.26176360E-02	-0.26393320E-02	-0.26575424E-02	-0.26730370E-02	-0.26863711E-02
29.00	-0.24476246E-02	-0.24676511E-02	-0.24844571E-02	-0.24987547E-02	-0.25110570E-02
30.00	-0.22920641E-02	-0.23105903E-02	-0.23261348E-02	-0.23393574E-02	-0.23507333E-02
31.00	-0.21494174E-02	-0.21665914E-02	-0.21809990E-02	-0.21932530E-02	-0.22037945E-02
32.00	-0.20183451E-02	-0.20342967E-02	-0.20476769E-02	-0.20590556E-02	-0.20688433E-02
33.00	-0.18976758E-02	-0.19125191E-02	-0.19249681E-02	-0.19355538E-02	-0.19446584E-02
34.00	-0.17863807E-02	-0.18002169E-02	-0.18118197E-02	-0.18216849E-02	-0.18301691E-02
35.00	-0.16835541E-02	-0.16964726E-02	-0.17073046E-02	-0.17165135E-02	-0.17244327E-02
36.00	-0.15883952E-02	-0.16004757E-02	-0.16106039E-02	-0.16192137E-02	-0.16266172E-02
37.00	-0.15001946E-02	-0.15115081E-02	-0.15209924E-02	-0.15290541E-02	-0.15359858E-02
38.00	-0.14183216E-02	-0.14289318E-02	-0.14378255E-02	-0.14453847E-02	-0.14518840E-02
39.00	-0.13422143E-02	-0.13521781E-02	-0.13605294E-02	-0.13676269E-02	-0.13737289E-02
40.00	-0.12713705E-02	-0.12807393E-02	-0.12885911E-02	-0.12952638E-02	-0.13010002E-02
41.00	-0.12053405E-02	-0.12141606E-02	-0.12215519E-02	-0.12278328E-02	-0.12332321E-02
42.00	-0.11437207E-02	-0.11520338E-02	-0.11589997E-02	-0.11649188E-02	-0.11700068E-02
43.00	-0.10861478E-02	-0.10939918E-02	-0.11005642E-02	-0.11061485E-02	-0.11109486E-02
44.00	-0.10322945E-02	-0.10397037E-02	-0.10459114E-02	-0.10511856E-02	-0.10557189E-02
45.00	-0.98186504E-03	-0.98887072E-03	-0.99473993E-03	-0.99972628E-03	-0.10040120E-02
46.00	-0.93459166E-03	-0.94122231E-03	-0.94677698E-03	-0.95149587E-03	-0.95555161E-03
47.00	-0.89023170E-03	-0.89651329E-03	-0.90177525E-03	-0.90624526E-03	-0.91008698E-03
48.00	-0.84856470E-03	-0.85452101E-03	-0.85951021E-03	-0.86374833E-03	-0.86739064E-03
49.00	-0.80939009E-03	-0.81504289E-03	-0.81977760E-03	-0.82379939E-03	-0.82725568E-03
50.00	-0.77252508E-03	-0.77789435E-03	-0.78239134E-03	-0.78621106E-03	-0.78949361E-03

TABLE A5

Radius of the sphere is $100.0 \cdot k_1$

The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.0 The number of surface modes is 49
 The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.1 The number of surface modes is 54
 The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.2 The number of surface modes is 59
 The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.3 The number of surface modes is 64
 The ratio k_2/k_1 is 1.4 The number of surface modes is 69

k_2/k_1	1.0	1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4
$z \cdot k_1$	V1	V2	V3	V4	V5
0.00	-0.14765459E+00	-0.16287892E+00	-0.17809789E+00	-0.19331011E+00	-0.20851431E+00
1.00	-0.99385079E-01	-0.10603564E+00	-0.11221200E+00	-0.11795129E+00	-0.12328742E+00
2.00	-0.71581613E-01	-0.74800102E-01	-0.77636510E-01	-0.80144404E-01	-0.82368860E-01
3.00	-0.54440968E-01	-0.56185353E-01	-0.57677108E-01	-0.58961972E-01	-0.60075889E-01
4.00	-0.43191887E-01	-0.44246344E-01	-0.45136263E-01	-0.45894930E-01	-0.46547247E-01
5.00	-0.35393602E-01	-0.36092696E-01	-0.36680138E-01	-0.37179249E-01	-0.37606998E-01
6.00	-0.29731642E-01	-0.30229325E-01	-0.30646918E-01	-0.31001038E-01	-0.31303662E-01
7.00	-0.25460834E-01	-0.25834150E-01	-0.26146989E-01	-0.26411659E-01	-0.26637050E-01
8.00	-0.22137346E-01	-0.22428267E-01	-0.22671612E-01	-0.22876888E-01	-0.23051006E-01
9.00	-0.19484354E-01	-0.19717609E-01	-0.19912266E-01	-0.20075941E-01	-0.20214204E-01
10.00	-0.17321826E-01	-0.17512992E-01	-0.17672117E-01	-0.17805474E-01	-0.17917676E-01
11.00	-0.15528242E-01	-0.15687677E-01	-0.15820044E-01	-0.15930622E-01	-0.16023304E-01
12.00	-0.14018856E-01	-0.14153749E-01	-0.14265458E-01	-0.14358495E-01	-0.14436198E-01
13.00	-0.12732862E-01	-0.12848377E-01	-0.12943808E-01	-0.13023063E-01	-0.13089035E-01
14.00	-0.11625540E-01	-0.11725486E-01	-0.11807870E-01	-0.11876109E-01	-0.11932736E-01
15.00	-0.10663285E-01	-0.10750539E-01	-0.10822311E-01	-0.10881614E-01	-0.10930685E-01
16.00	-0.98203642E-02	-0.98971390E-02	-0.99601690E-02	-0.10012130E-01	-0.10055012E-01
17.00	-0.90767464E-02	-0.91447720E-02	-0.92005188E-02	-0.92463788E-02	-0.92841322E-02
18.00	-0.84166066E-02	-0.84772552E-02	-0.85268738E-02	-0.85676126E-02	-0.86010733E-02
19.00	-0.78272806E-02	-0.78816543E-02	-0.79260703E-02	-0.79624715E-02	-0.79923063E-02
20.00	-0.72985151E-02	-0.73475089E-02	-0.73874728E-02	-0.74201702E-02	-0.74469167E-02
21.00	-0.68219213E-02	-0.68662694E-02	-0.69023958E-02	-0.69319072E-02	-0.69560039E-02
22.00	-0.63905711E-02	-0.64308814E-02	-0.64636779E-02	-0.64904305E-02	-0.65122380E-02
23.00	-0.59986931E-02	-0.60354730E-02	-0.60653629E-02	-0.60897119E-02	-0.61095293E-02
24.00	-0.56414419E-02	-0.56751182E-02	-0.57024568E-02	-0.57246999E-02	-0.57427776E-02
25.00	-0.53147205E-02	-0.53456548E-02	-0.53707426E-02	-0.53911310E-02	-0.54076797E-02
26.00	-0.50150415E-02	-0.50435420E-02	-0.50666348E-02	-0.50853821E-02	-0.51005804E-02
27.00	-0.47394189E-02	-0.47657498E-02	-0.47870666E-02	-0.48043552E-02	-0.48183555E-02
28.00	-0.44852811E-02	-0.45096702E-02	-0.45293996E-02	-0.45453864E-02	-0.45583194E-02
29.00	-0.42504020E-02	-0.42730469E-02	-0.42913520E-02	-0.43061725E-02	-0.43181510E-02
30.00	-0.40328455E-02	-0.40539182E-02	-0.40709410E-02	-0.40847128E-02	-0.40958344E-02
31.00	-0.38309200E-02	-0.38505709E-02	-0.38664353E-02	-0.38792611E-02	-0.38896108E-02
32.00	-0.36431410E-02	-0.36615023E-02	-0.36763171E-02	-0.36882867E-02	-0.36979390E-02
33.00	-0.34682012E-02	-0.34853894E-02	-0.34992503E-02	-0.35104429E-02	-0.35194630E-02
34.00	-0.33049446E-02	-0.33210627E-02	-0.33340545E-02	-0.33445398E-02	-0.33529852E-02
35.00	-0.31523456E-02	-0.31674853E-02	-0.31796830E-02	-0.31895228E-02	-0.31974444E-02
36.00	-0.30094913E-02	-0.30237341E-02	-0.30352047E-02	-0.30444540E-02	-0.30518969E-02
37.00	-0.28755666E-02	-0.28889856E-02	-0.28997887E-02	-0.29084965E-02	-0.29155010E-02
38.00	-0.27498418E-02	-0.27625023E-02	-0.27726914E-02	-0.27809014E-02	-0.27875034E-02
39.00	-0.26316615E-02	-0.26436223E-02	-0.26532454E-02	-0.26609970E-02	-0.26672286E-02
40.00	-0.25204357E-02	-0.25317498E-02	-0.25408501E-02	-0.25481787E-02	-0.25540687E-02
41.00	-0.24156321E-02	-0.24263473E-02	-0.24349638E-02	-0.24419012E-02	-0.24474758E-02
42.00	-0.23167689E-02	-0.23269286E-02	-0.23350966E-02	-0.23416717E-02	-0.23469543E-02
43.00	-0.22234094E-02	-0.22330530E-02	-0.22408046E-02	-0.22470434E-02	-0.22520552E-02
44.00	-0.21351570E-02	-0.21443202E-02	-0.21516846E-02	-0.21576108E-02	-0.21623711E-02
45.00	-0.20516504E-02	-0.20603659E-02	-0.20673694E-02	-0.20730047E-02	-0.20775311E-02
46.00	-0.19725601E-02	-0.19808578E-02	-0.19875247E-02	-0.19928886E-02	-0.19971970E-02
47.00	-0.18975850E-02	-0.19054921E-02	-0.19118445E-02	-0.19169551E-02	-0.19210601E-02
48.00	-0.18264494E-02	-0.18339910E-02	-0.18400492E-02	-0.18449230E-02	-0.18488378E-02
49.00	-0.17589006E-02	-0.17660996E-02	-0.17718823E-02	-0.17765342E-02	-0.17802711E-02
50.00	-0.16947063E-02	-0.17015839E-02	-0.17071081E-02	-0.17115522E-02	-0.17151223E-02